

Grant 869580

ArcticHubs

Deliverable title and number: D 5.1 Future scenario reports

Work Package: WP5

Type of Deliverable¹: Report Dissemination Level²: Public

Lead Beneficiary: Natural Resources Institute Finland Luke

Lead Author(s): Seija Tuulentie, Pasi Rikkonen, Taru Rikkonen, Esa Inkilä, Kristine Lyngedersen, Gun Lidestav, Per Sandström, Stefan Sandström, Audun Iversen, Roy Robertsen, Ragnheidur Bogadóttir, Elisa Vang, Rannveig Ólafsdóttir, Anna Gudrun Edvardsdóttir, Michael V. Bishop, Janne Miettinen, Pasi Rautio

Review(s): [1°/18.12.2023]

Reviewer(s): Jukka Teräs, Ivana Zivojinovic]

Delivery: Due date: 31/12/2023 Submission Date: 29/12/2023

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the author's views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

¹ **Deliverable Type:**

R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc. OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

² **Dissemination Level:** PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web

CO: Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement

EU-RES: Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)

EU-CON: Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)

EU-SEC: Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2015/444/EC)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869580.

Table of contents

Executive summary	4
1. Introduction	6
1.1 Theoretical starting points for foresight work	6
1.1.1. Toolbox for future anticipation	7
1.1.2. Delphi method as a main source of future information	8
1.1.3. The foresight process in WP5	8
1.2 Application for ArcticHubs project	10
2. Local community engagement	12
3. Scenario building processes in different hub regions	14
3.1 Inari, Finland	15
3.2 Forestry, Northern Sweden and Finland	16
3.3 Malå, Sweden	17
3.4 Suðuroy, Faroe Islands	19
3.5 Nuuk, Greenland	20
3.6 Varanger, Norway	21
3.7 Westfjords, Iceland	22
3.8 Youth, Arctic	23
4. Results	25
4.1 Opportunities for the Arctic development	25
4.2 Threats for the Arctic development	28
4.3 Region-specific futures	30
4.3.1. Inari, Finland (Tourism and indigenous cultures hubs)	31
4.3.2. Northern Finland and Sweden (Forestry hub)	32
4.3.3. Malå, Sweden (Forestry hub)	34

4.3.4.	Suðuroy, Faroe Islands (Tourism and fish farming hubs)	35
4.3.5.	Nuuk, Greenland (Tourism and indigenous hubs)	37
4.3.6.	Varanger, Norway (Fish farming, tourism and mining hubs)	37
4.3.7.	Westfjords, Iceland (Fish farming and tourism hubs)	39
4.3.8.	Arctic youth	42
4.4	Hub-specific future narratives: Tourism, Fish farming & fisheries, Mining and Indigenous culture	43
4.4.1.	Tourism	43
4.4.2.	Fish farming and fisheries	44
4.4.3.	Mining	45
4.4.4.	Indigenous culture	45
5.	Conclusions	47
6.	References	48
7.	Appendices	50

Executive summary

The overall objective of working package 5 – Applying ArcticHubs results for creating sustainable future pathways – is to map the futures of ArcticHubs project’s regions by complementing existing socio-economic and environmental data including the data produced in the ArcticHubs’ WPs 1-4 with the knowledge and views of local decision-makers, authorities, economic actors, and residents including indigenous peoples and the youth. The work has been carried out in keen cooperation with local community members with an emphasis on reconciliation of different activities to develop desirable future pathways. This project report summarises the scenarios made for regions with one or several hub industries and combines also the future perspectives of different hub industries and indigenous cultural issues across Arctic areas.

Futures studies is the systematic study of possible, probable, and preferable futures, and analysis of their potential impacts on society. Several methods have been used in the foresight work also to engage the local people. These include Delphi method, scenario planning methods, future workshops and scanning the changes in operational environment. Methods have been used in various ways in different regional context due to the examined needs and also project resources.

When Delphi survey has been applied the statements have been formulated together with local stakeholders and the respondents have represented widely both local, regional, and national land use experts. Delphi results have been used together with other data in local workshops which have served as a second round for the Delphi process. In all the cases, threats and opportunities have been examined. Youth and indigenous peoples' representatives have been specifically invited to the workshops.

The results show that as the main opportunities in the Arctic by 2035 identified are nature as such, and sustainable use of natural resources. Also, indigeneity, localness and strengthening of local identities are important. All this is expected to lead to increasing attractiveness of the studied areas both among visitors and permanent residents. The main threats are regarded as land use conflicts and difficulties in reconciling natural resource use. Global and foreign companies are also seen in many cases as a threat. Concerning demographic issues, too rapid

pace of change can be also a threat.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869580.

The future scenarios of each participating region showed that the most common issues dealing with different scenarios, either threat, opportunity, or Business As Usual (BAU) scenarios, are climate change, which is seen both negative and positive, population change including people moving to and from the Arctic because of the climate or jobs for example, the development of technology and digitalization framing the overall future of the Arctic, and tourism and its effects to the local environment and society in the future.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869580.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869580.

1. Introduction

In ArcticHubs project, future work aims at creating scenarios for hub industries, based on recognised threats and opportunities *in seven Arctic regions*, and investigating how the different hub industries are seen to develop *across the Arctic* by the year 2035. The eighth scenario work examines the Arctic youth perspectives on the same time perspective. The second stage, task 5.2., is the evaluation of the created scenarios both by locals and researchers. The scenario process will be fulfilled by wider future forums (task 5.4) in the locations where scenarios are made and in other wider forums, and based on these, the policy recommendations for decision-makers and authorities will be made.

The general goals of the task 5. 1 were the following: 1) to explore the different outcomes associated with “what if” questions based on the materials provided by WPs 1-4; 2) to set common visions to the hubs and their surrounding areas for future development by building scenario narratives of possible futures and 3) to increase possibilities for adaptation of the hub regions against future social, economic and environmental changes in order to create more resilient communities.

1.1 Theoretical starting points for foresight work

Futures studies (also referred as futures research, foresight, futurism, futures thinking, and futurology) is the systematic study of possible, probable, and preferable futures, and analysis of their potential impacts on society. The methods and tools of futures studies are used to analyse and structure today’s problems and challenges in a future-oriented way for decisionmaking aiming at a systematic, participatory, holistic, future intelligence gathering and medium-to-long-term vision building process (Bell, 1997). The use of futures studies’ methods enhances anticipatory consciousness, which in term improves the foresight to be prepared and act faster or earlier, making the organization or individual more effective in dealing with change. The ability to anticipate gives time to better understand threats and opportunities, develop more creative strategies, create new opportunities, and create and share vision for organizational change (Glenn & Gordon, 2009). The value of futures studies is less in forecasting accuracy than in usefulness in planning and opening minds to consider new possibilities and changes in operational environment. Its purpose is not to know the future but

to help us make better decisions today via its methods that force us to anticipate opportunities and threats and consider how to address them.

Because of different interests, geopolitical pressures, and socio-economic activities there are many challenges in the future of Arctic land use. The local voices are important to be part of the future plans and decisions, and for discovering the voices futures studies methods can be successfully used. There are already guidelines and legal norms for improving participation and decision-making processes on land-use planning for Arctic Countries, such as Finland (see e.g. Piipponen & Kurikka, 2020). These include methods like citizen juries, opinion polls, participatory workshops etc. in addition to traditional way of taking part in a representative democracy. However, the possibilities and effectiveness of participation vary a lot. As part of the WP5 research, different in-depth analytical futures research methods are being used and tested to assess understanding of land use conflicts, areas and issues over land. They help to assess drivers and trends impacting the Arctic, local stakeholders, policy makers and citizens' perceptions, and to identify future development opportunities and choices.

1.1.1. [Toolbox for future anticipation](#)

In ArcticHubs' WP5 work the approach was defined as a foresight process that used several methods for future anticipation. These include Delphi method, scenario planning methods, future workshops and scanning the changes in operational environment.

Scenario planning refers to several techniques that aims to construct alternative future developments (preferred, probable and also avoidable futures) based on the knowledge of current situation i.e. starting from the current situation (see e.g. Van der Heijden, 1996). Scenarios are hypothetical sequences of events, built with the intent of attracting attention to causal processes and points of decision (Kahn and Wiener, 1967). This is done in order to show how they may evolve step by step starting from the present situation. A scenario is thus an internally consistent story about the path from the present to the future. According to Van der Heijden (1996), at least two scenarios are needed to reflect uncertainty. More than four has proven organisationally impractical. Each of the scenarios must be plausible. That means that they must grow logically (in a cause-effect way) from the past and the present. Furthermore, they must be internally consistent. Events within a scenario must be related through cause-

effect lines of argument which cannot be flawed. Scenarios must also be relevant to the issues under scrutiny e.g. in decision-making processes.

One of the scenario methods is Delphi technique, and it is often used to construct scenarios (see e.g. Rikkinen & Tapio, 2009, Rikkinen et al., 2021). Scenario planning can also include evaluating the impacts of each scenario, and this impact assessment can be conducted through qualitative and/or quantitative methods. Furthermore, horizon scanning which means the anticipation of changes, driving forces and trends in the operational environment, is often used as a starting point of foresight scrutiny. This may also include forecasts i.e. projections based on historical data and/or argued expert views on most probable future (usually referred as Business-As-Usual, BAU), describing more "passive" future states. These kinds of forecasts are usually used as a bases for foresight processes. For more information on futures studies methods, see Glenn & Gordon (2009).

1.1.2. Delphi method as a main source of future information

In this WP5 we have applied a Delphi application that allows to meet the aims of gathering important future views in different Hubs. Delphi method concentrates on gathering and categorising expert future views through surveys, interviews, and also in latter phases of the process, workshops. The aim of the method is to help and stimulate a group of chosen experts of local practices and regional and national decision-makers and authorities to work as a whole when dealing with complex future topics and/or problems (see Linstone & Turoff, 1975, Bell 1997, Kuusi 1999). There are three key principles in Delphi method, namely: 1) anonymity, 2) successive iteration of future questions and topics, and feedback of results and 3) interactivity of future views. Delphi method usually aims to present desirable and probable future development, certainty estimation of probable future, and importance assessments of most influential driving forces, trends, or changes in operational environment. Common for all the foresight methods is the participatory nature within the implementation of a foresight process.

1.1.3. The foresight process in WP5

When preparing the foresight process three preparatory internal scenario clinics were organised in order to share and discuss the WP5 plan's implementation. During the first phase

the principles of a Delphi method were discussed based on the expertise within the ArcticHubs researchers. Already in the beginning of the foresight process the resources on this work were discussed in each of the Hubs, and as a conclusion, each of the Hubs then planned the implementation of the process based on that.

When preparing the foresight process three internal scenario clinics within ArcticHubs project were organised between November 2022 and May 2023 in order to prepare, share and discuss the WP5 plan's implementation. The scenario clinics were meant for those responsible researchers in WP5 who then started to conduct the foresight process in particular Hubs (see chapter three for Hubs' list). During the first planning phase the principles of a Delphi method were discussed based on the expertise within the ArcticHubs researchers. For the help of each Hub to plan the implementation, a general guide for Delphi-based scenario process was formulated and discussed based on Delphi method literature (see

Figure 1, also available at <https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs/participatory-tools>).

Already in the beginning of the foresight process the resources on this work were discussed in each of the hub regions, and as a conclusion, each of the hub regions then planned the implementation of the process based on that. This meant that the implementation of the scenario processes in

each region varied. Each of the foresight

Figure 1. Delphi method and scenario processes are presented more precisely in [planning](#). chapter three.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869580.

1.2 Application for ArcticHubs project

In the ArcticHubs project the scenario building process included several methods, and in most of the process we co-operated strongly with the local actors and residents. The main 'umbrella' in scenario planning was Delphi technique that in practise consisted of materials utilised from WP's 1-4, expert surveys, interviews, use of statistics and other sources of information, and future workshops organised as an iterative process. These scenario processes varied in the conducted eight hub and regional processes, and they are explained in detail in the following chapters, especially in chapter three. The common elements as aims to follow for each of the foresight processes were the following steps (in chronological order):

1. Local level discussions through workshops, webinars, stakeholder meetings or interviews for scenario preparation purposes i.e. validating findings (future topics) from earlier WPs and identifying new emerging and regionally relevant issues and future topics for scenario building process
2. Review of relevant foresight literature search on hub and region-specific research conducted. This was done in order to utilise local/regional/national foresight reports & strategic plans and programmes in identifying Hubs relevant future topics
3. As a result, from steps 1 and 2 key future topics and questions for the Hubs and regions were further elaborated through hub's research group
4. Expert survey, workshop(s) or interviews on future threats and opportunities in Hubs or regions. Those hubs that conducted expert surveys, future statements were prepared as part of the process involving local, regional, national participants to contribute to scenario construction
5. Future workshops to construct alternative future scenarios (e.g. feedback reports of the results were prepared for workshop participants from step 4 results)

As said, the implementation in each of the hubs and regions varied based on the resources available. Furthermore, what was common for all the processes was the question of threats and opportunities that was posed to respondents in surveys and discussed in future workshops. The constructed scenarios are further elaborated in task 5.2. (e.g. feedback session, workshop or webinar, by researchers) in order to evaluate the impacts of alternative future developments, and to build on the identified opportunities and tackling the threats. In the WP5.1 there were altogether six hub regions 1) Inari, Finland, 2) Malå, Sweden, 3) Suðuroy, Faroe Islands, 4) Nuuk, Greenland, 5) Varanger, Norway, and 6) Westfjords, Iceland), and two

thematic scenario processes (1) Forestry, Northern Sweden and Finland and 2) Youth, Arctic, in where these foresight methods were applied.

Also, an important starting point for foresight process was the data and findings from the earlier conducted parts within WP's 1-4. The most important input for the task 5.1 were the findings on geopolitics and global economic drivers (WP1), environmental concerns (WP2), and societal challenges (WP3) that were then operationalised as future statements in Delphi surveys.

Future scenarios were built with specific attention to such crucial issues as demographic changes (including gender and age issues), global interests in the Arctic and local and indigenous communities' needs. The most important outcomes were the constructed scenarios for hubs and for the most important ArcticHubs regions at large.

Altogether multi-actor approach was used in foresight work in WP5. It distinguishes between three groups: (1) global industries, SMEs, international and European actors (including public administration, international organisations, NGOs), (2) indigenous and local communities and stakeholders in the hub regions and (3) regional and national authorities outside the hub regions within an interest in the topic.

2. Local community engagement

In all the hubs, we engaged with the locals strongly, also taking the views of indigenous peoples and youth into account when relevant. Depending on the hub region, the scenario processes consisted of a Delphi survey and one or several workshops. Also, PPGIS data (WP4) and interviews (WP1 and WP3) were used to get an overview of local perspectives – especially if there were no resources to make a Delphi survey. We also used local languages in the processes.

For most of those processes, which conducted Delphi survey, national and regional experts were invited as respondents. In all processes, local land-use experts were involved. Local level expertise is here understood as *vernacular expertise* which, according to Lowe et al. (2019), means the expertise that people have about the places in which they live and work, how these places function and how they relate to the wider world. Delphi survey results and materials from previous work packages were used as a basis for workshop discussions to contextualise the future perspectives of the regions and hubs.

Contrary to Delphi surveys, the workshop participants were in most of the workshops only locals. In the workshops they, thus, had a possibility to comment and evaluate both the locals' and outsiders' views of the future of the region or hub. Workshop participants were selected e.g. by asking the local recipients of the Delphi survey of their willingness to participate the workshops (Inari, FI), using the snowball method to identify interested local participants (Malå, SE) or engaging at least partly the same group throughout different ArcticHubs' work package workshops (Westfjords, IS).

Exceptions of only-local workshop participation were Forestry workshop, Nuuk workshops, and Arctic youth workshop, which by definition was aimed at enabling the discussion of young people over national borders, especially because the youth are the ones the future affects the most. Forestry workshop had a wider geographical reach as well and it consisted of forest experts from national level and from local level, representing e.g. municipalities, nature conservation associations and reindeer herders. In Greenland, also Greenlandic national and regional actors were taken onboard due to the size of the society.

In addition to the Arctic youth workshop, young people were specifically targeted in other processes as well. For example, in Suðuroy, FO, workshop and survey were conducted with

young upper-secondary school students, around 80 people participated in the workshop, and 73 of the workshop participants also submitted their responses to the survey. Similarly, in Westfjords, IS, high-school students were targeted with a workshop of their own.

Indigenous peoples were present in their home regions (Inari, FI; Malå, SE; Varanger, NO and Nuuk, GL) and also in the Arctic youth workshop around half of the participants were of indigenous origin. In Greenland, in order to create flow in the group dialogues, simultaneous interpretation was deselected. Instead, participants were asked to state their language preference when registering, so that Greenlandic-speaking and Danish-speaking groups could be formed, respectively. Two third of the participants chose to participate in a Greenlandic speaking group, so two Greenlandic-speaking and one Danish-speaking group were formed, each of which was placed in their own room. In Westfjords, there was a particular effort to reach the residents of foreign origin (comprising employees in fish farming, fish processing factory, and in kindergarten), and five of them did participate to the workshop of altogether 13 participants.

3. Scenario building processes in different hub regions

The implementation in each of the Hubs and their surrounding regions varied based on the resources available. It was defined in ArcticHubs project that ‘hubs’ are important socioeconomic nodes in a geographical network and their surroundings. Some of the hubs had a special emphasis on concentrating in the scenario process on regional development as a whole. Therefore, the focus was not on a certain livelihood, but on future development in a region as a whole. The hubs where the scenario work was done are presented in Table 1. There were altogether eight hubs covering the participating regions and partner countries in ArcticHubs project.

Table 1. The list of Hubs and their focus in scenario processes.

Location and countries	The focus of hubs and regions
1. Inari, Finland	A Tourism and Indigenous hub in municipality of Inari, Northern Finland
2. Northern Finland and Sweden (based on Kemi, Finland)	A Forestry Hub in Västerbotten, Norrbotten and Lapland in northern Sweden and Finland, based on Kemi region
3. Malå, Sweden	Forestry, mining and Indigenous hub in Västerbotten, northern Sweden
4. Suðuroy, Faroe Islands	The tourism and fish farming hub in Faroes
5. Nuuk, Greenland	Tourism and Indigenous People Hub in Nuuk, Greenland
6. Varanger, NO	The fish farming, tourism and indigenous hub in northern Norway

7. Westfjords, Iceland	The fish farming and tourism hub in in northwestern Iceland
8. Youth, Arctic	The youth Arctic futures with an emphasis on Indigenous communities

3.1 Inari, Finland

In Inari the future work started with discussions with local stakeholders to identify relevant topics for a Delphi survey which was the first part of the process. In Delphi survey future views of the Inari region as part of the Arctic were sought. The survey was conducted on the Maptionnaire survey platform, and it sought for answers on the future possibilities and threats to the area, as well as responses on different future statements. The survey was sent to approximately 150 respondents from local to national level, who somehow were related to Inari by substance of the work, expertise or as a part-time or full-time resident. The future statements had to be evaluated by the likelihood of them to happen, and by the importance of them to the Inari region. A total of 31 respondents participated the survey, and the results served as a base for the future workshops.

The preliminary invitation to the workshops was sent in the Delphi survey, and then again closer to the workshops. There were two workshops conducted, with 20-30 participants in each workshop, and the general aim of the workshops was to outline various future scenarios for the Inari region until 2035. The aim of the first workshop on the 25th of April 2023 was to structure the future scenarios, which take into account the threats and opportunities highlighted in the survey. In addition, based on the future statements and importance assessments, participants selected the most significant drivers of change by theme. Subsequently, participants considered how these drivers of change would develop until 2035, using three different approaches on future: future based on opportunities, future based on threats, and the most likely future (BAU - Business As Usual). After the workshop, the research group formulated the drafts of these scenarios, which the participants could comment and edit in the next workshop. In addition, the aim of the second workshop on the 4th of May 2023 was to evaluate scenario impacts (both scenario specific and general) on the Inari region, and

to identify needs for decision-making. As said, in the second workshop it was still possible to comment and edit the scenarios themselves. The process of the future work in Inari is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The progress of the Inari, Finland foresight process.

3.2 Forestry, Northern Sweden and Finland

To initiate the scenario process in Kemi, Finland, we decided to broaden the scope by considering the impact of the new pulp mill in Kemi not only locally but also across borders. Therefore, we opted to encompass the entire Northern region of Sweden and Finland in the foresight process. When thinking about the development of the region as a starting point of the foresight process, forestry is a major land user both in northern Finland and Sweden, and together with the wood processing industries it makes up an essential part of the regional economy. Although the prospect of a significantly increased demand of timber because of major investments in sawmills (e.g. Malå) and pulp mills (e.g. Kemi) are well in line with the regional sustainability efforts, and the “green transition”, there are also other land use interests and perspectives to be considered.

The data gathering for the scenario construction was conducted by two main sources: first, the expert survey conducted in summer 2023, and second, a workshop held in Kukkolaforsen, Sweden on the 29th of August 2023. The foresight process consisted of three phases. First, there were local meetings and discussions with key stakeholders in order to identify factors

and drivers influencing the future of the regions. Based on these discussions a survey was prepared that included future statements relevant to the regions and asked about key threats and opportunities. Considering the ongoing expansion of wood processing industries, also forest resource assessments on both the Finnish and Swedish counties were conducted. In the second phase, the results of the survey and the forest resource assessments and survey were presented for review in a workshop. Together with the workshop participants the most significant drivers of change were prioritized, and their future directions were discussed and drafted. Using this as a foundation, in the third phase the research team has drafted scenario outlines, which are further refined based on the feedback received (see Figure 3 below).

Figure 3. The progress of the forest land use and forest industry scenario analysis of Northern Sweden and Finland.

3.3 Malå, Sweden

The foresight process in the Malå hub was carried out in six steps between March 2022 and November 2023 (Figure 4). A final workshop will be carried out in May 2024, with the aim of developing the meaning and application of the Lean Forestry concept, as a very specific tool

for implementing sustainable forest management in reindeer husbandry areas. First, through five key informants, valuable information was attained on which people should be invited for the workshop. Secondly, in the first workshop the results from SKA22 (Swedish forestry impact analyzes 2022) were introduced, which refer to productive forest land in Norrbotten and Västerbotten counties, and present simulations of four future forestry and forest development scenarios based on different assumptions about the future. However, as there was no representation from any nature conservation organisation, a separate meeting with the local section of Naturskyddsföreningen (The Swedish Society for Nature Conservation) in the city of Skellefteå (eight participants) was organised. An additional workshop was also carried out with four Malå municipal planning representatives. Taken together, these discussions and meetings provided a battery of co-created statements for the next phase, i.e. the survey to stakeholders and experts in the Malå region (phase three).

Fourth, the results of the survey were presented at the second workshop end of May 2023, where the participants advised the research team to make an additional effort to receive more responses, as they perceived that some perspectives were not properly represented. Thus, a third exhortation was sent out in the beginning of June. Beginning of August, another seven completed answers were received, and the survey was finally closed with a response rate of 44%. During the second workshop, the two scenarios 'Focus on Growth' and 'Focus on Diversity', drafted by the researchers, based on survey results on key threats and opportunities, in combination with the Malå region specific forest resource assessment was presented, discussed and modified by the 15 participants. Thus, the fifth stage, turned into a further development of the extended survey results, followed by public presentations in Malå Future Summit and Fair. Thanks to this sixth stage, it was possible to receive further inputs from stakeholders and the general public. The whole foresight process in Malå is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The progress of the foresight process in Malå, Sweden.

3.4 Suðuroy, Faroe Islands

In the Suðuroy case, the research team has endeavoured to engage the local community in ways that are respectful to time expenditure of participants, and the social entanglements of smaller communities with the themes addressed in the ArcticHubs project. The future scenario work has been based on material collected throughout the project period. The aim has been to identify and articulate future visions and knowledge from local experts and stakeholders, especially in tourism and fish farming, but to also allow alternative perspectives from broader civil society. To accomplish this, data material for the future scenario work has been collected through five main rounds of data collection, each round of results feeding into the following rounds (see Figure 5) below.

Figure 5. The progress of scenario work in Suðuroy, Faroe Islands.

3.5 Nuuk, Greenland

In Nuuk, two separate workshops were organised, where the participants' physical meeting was put in focus and supplementary online study was deselected. The personal attendance with active participation in group dialogue was put in focus, and therefore there were no introductory and time-consuming presentations, and the groups rather did not present presentations in the forum. In order to initiate the group dialogue, dialogue forms were prepared for both workshops. For workshop 1, the following five open conversation topics were included in the dialogue form:

- Local tourism: Opportunities, threats and business as usual and the drivers behind them.
- The local Greenlandic culture: Opportunities, threats, and business as usual and the drivers behind them.
- The local hunting and fishing industry: Opportunities, threats, and business as usual and the drivers behind them.
- Climate change: Opportunities, threats and business as usual and the drivers behind them.
- Nature- and culturally sustainable business development: Opportunities, threats, and business as usual and the drivers behind them.

In the planning phases, only the first two topics, Tourism and The Local Greenlandic Culture, were chosen as talking points, but in case the dialogue should standstill/stall, the other three

topics were added. For workshop 2, the following two conversation topics were included in the dialogue form:

- The positive and negative effects of 1) The opportunity-oriented future scenario, 2) The threat-oriented future, 3) The BAU-oriented future scenario.
- Most desirable future scenarios and measures/Actions for realization

The dialogue form was attached to the invitation so that participants could prepare. The process is explained in the Figure 6 below.

Figure 6. The progress of the Nuuk, Greenland, scenario process.

3.6 Varanger, Norway

The scenarios in Varanger, Norway are based on three main sources of gathered data: A PPGIS survey reached 412 people in the region. In addition there were two wider workshops organised, in Bugøyenes in May 2022 and in Kirkenes in June 2023, while a scenario shaping workshop was held in Kirkenes in November 2023, followed by interviews with stakeholders not able to attend.

The foresight process consisted of four phases. First, in the Bugøyenes workshop, factors and drivers influencing the future of the area were identified, with views presented from both researchers and stakeholders. In the Kirkenes workshop, results from the PPGIS survey were also presented and discussed. In the scenario shaping workshop all drivers identified in

workshops and survey was discussed, the most significant drivers of change were prioritized, and their future directions were discussed and drafted. The research team then drafted scenario outlines, which were further refined based on the feedback received. The whole process is shown in Figure 7 below.

Figure 7. The progress of Varanger, Norway, scenario process.

3.7 Westfjords, Iceland

The Westfjords foresight process consisted of three phases, and the forecast survey building started the process. To align topics with partner countries for comparison, the planned future topics and statements were formulated from the findings of the Inari Delphi study (see section 3.1), and then tailored to the Westfjords hub, incorporating insights from Icelandic drivers, trends, and change factors identified through discussions and interviews with researchers and stakeholders. Secondly, two on-site workshops followed in Patreksfjörður 22nd and 23rd of November 2023. They aimed at discussing the planned future topics (threats and opportunities) and formulated statements. Facilities in the municipality's community center were kindly provided by the Vesturbyggð municipality. A total of 13 participants participated in the workshops. Part of them belong to the same focus group as had participated with us in other WPs namely, public sector, private sector, senior citizens, and residents of foreign origin. Thirdly, two Maptionnaire surveys were conducted concentrating on future topics and statements. The progress of the future work in Westfjords is shown in Figure 8 below.

Figure 8. The progress of Westfjords, Iceland, scenario process.

3.8 Youth, Arctic

The Arctic youth workshop was a joint initiative by ArcticHubs and ACAF projects. ACAF (“Youth and indigenous peoples’ involvement in climate change adaptation in the Arctic and Barents region”; <https://www.acaf.fi/>) is another project coordinated by Luke and it is supported by the Ministry for Foreign Affairs of Finland. The workshop was organized with the Sámi Education Institute, a partner of the ArcticHubs project based in Inari. With a shared goal of addressing the three complex issues facing the Arctic region, the workshop facilitated dialogue between indigenous youth and those from the majority population, fostering a holistic understanding of the challenges that need to be tackled. The workshop included activities designed to spark discussions, encourage networking, and facilitate innovative thinking. Participants began by introducing themselves and sharing insights from their respective home villages, showcasing the rich diversity and unique perspectives of the workshop. The workshop began by introducing the participants and sharing insights from their respective home villages, showcasing the rich diversity and unique perspectives of the workshop. The workshop included three stages: 1) defining the most important threats and possibilities in the Arctic by 2035, 2) creating threat and opportunity scenario stories to the Arctic until 2035, and 3) concretizing how to avoid or reach these scenarios (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. The progress of Arctic youth futures' scenario process.

4. Results

In the result section, we have analysed the materials from scenario processes – both Delphi surveys and workshop reports – by using qualitative content analysis. No software was used as the material was not very large and the scenario processes have been discussed in the research group several times. Qualitative content analysis basically means examining language intensely for the purpose of classifying text into an efficient number of categories that represent similar meanings (Hsieh & Shannon 2015).

In the opportunities and threats section, we are looking especially the most common themes which have been raised in the context of many regions and hub industries while in the section of scenario processes, we summarise the results from each process. The wider description of these scenario processes can be found in the appendices.

4.1 Opportunities for the Arctic development

In most of the scenario regions, the abundance and accessibility of clean and diverse *nature* and large protected areas were emphasized and seen as an opportunity for the development. For tourism, the meaning of nature is related to natural phenomena such as snow, northern lights, and darkness or activities such as skiing and fishing or other experiences (Inari, FI; Suđuroy, FO; Malå, SE; Varanger, NO; Westfjords, IS). Nature is also something which is seen as attracting people to move to the areas.

The effects of *climate change* were seen as manifold but on the positive side were the possibilities of growth of domestic tourism (the Faroes) and more year-round tourism due to less sea-ice (Nuuk, Greenland). Most positive climate change effects were seen in the Forestry Delphi survey where increasing growth of forests, a place for future food production for Europe and an increase in the attractiveness of the region were brought up. The expectation of climate change related rise in attractiveness of northern areas was discussed also in Malå and in Inari. A hope that mild climate brings more jobs, inhabitants and businesses was mentioned. In Varanger hub, milder winters were expected to lead to better growing conditions for salmon in the North affecting positively aquaculture development, and sustainable transport of sea food via the north-east passage was regarded as an advantage. Novel species such as pink salmon may bring new economic opportunities to Varangerfjord if they are harvestable.

In addition, successful climate change adaptation was seen as an opportunity in Varangerfjord future scenario work.

In the Malå Delphi, the statement that was considered most important by the respondents was “Forest is an important key to the solution of both the climate crisis and the preservation of biological diversity”. The increase in climate-smart products along green transition from forests was expected in Malå while also issues of alternative forest management methods (lean forestry) was raised. In Nuuk, Greenland, the possibilities of locally produced food instead of imported were discussed in relation to climate change mitigation. In Inari’s vision related to forestry, is that old-growth forests are protected, and firewood and building materials come from local forests.

Extractive *natural resource use* was discussed most in relation to Malå scenario work. Forestry, mining, innovations, and re-industrialization were seen as opportunities given that sustainability issues were emphasized throughout, meaning e.g. that more of the values from the extraction has to stay in the region. Wind power is seen both as an opportunity and a threat. In Forestry Delphi survey (held in Northern Sweden and Finland), it was seen as an opportunity while in Malå renewable energy production was regarded positive as such, but wind power was an exception – at least for some; for some others it was seen as a possibility to generate money for the municipality. Here it is important to note that Malå already have four wind power plants established near the small town. Green transition was seen as changing the situation and creating new interesting jobs both in the traditional natural resource-based industry but not least in the supplier industry and services (Varanger). In Greenland, a well-coordinated annual cycle with various tourist activities was seen to be needed to ensure good coexistence between different resource users and business activities.

Demographic issues have been recognised as a crucial challenge to the Arctic region (Megatrends 2011). This theme was referred many times in scenario work by emphasising positive population development and possibilities of remote work for staying in the region (Varangerfjord; Youth). In addition to the promises of climate change in attracting new residents, improvement of education and remote work were seen as parts of positive future. It was mentioned e.g. in Varangerfjord and Malå that increasing education possibilities create more attractive jobs for women and attract young people to stay and return. These are the groups which have often been recognised as lacking in Arctic and remote rural regions (Heleniak 2021). Improved housing conditions were seen especially in Inari as an opportunity for demographic development. In Forestry Delphi survey, the statement “North tempts more people” was the third most supported, and in Malå the lack of workforce both in industry and for public service are underlined.

Especially the Youth group was emphasising *indigenous* issues. In the Sámi area of Malå, the positive future vision was that dialogue between the reindeer herding communities and the industries works, making it possible to live on reindeer husbandry. In Greenland, the Indigenous topics were referred to as Greenlandic cultural issues and many formulations contained a desire for the future of a country with a strong culture and a people with a proud identity. For example, a wish was formulated for the government to create loan facilities for local Greenlanders to ensure a locally anchored tourism industry. The vision was that diverse Greenlandic culture will flourish and stand stronger, and the intergenerational knowledge and experience transfer will be carried out in families and between residents and newcomers: “There is a common interest in using and strengthening the Greenlandic culture, both the original Inuit culture and the modern Greenlandic culture in the tourism industry, but also regardless of the tourism industry.” In Inari and Malå, appreciation of the Sámi people and the survival of Sámi culture as a vital force was seen as an opportunity. Parts of the positive future in Inari were also the strengthening of Sámi land use rights and national consensus of the Act of Sámi Parliament.

A lot of emphasis was put also on *localness and strengthening of local identities*. In the Youth workshop, the situation where local communities’ voice is heard was seen as an opportunity for better politics and decision-making. Also in Greenland, revitalizing local culture and having community dialogue of new drivers versus local ways of life was seen as prerequisite for better future. In the Faroes, localness of tourism industry was seen as an opportunity compared to international fish farming industry. In Greenland, a future scenario was that Greenlanders and local newcomers who today prefer to eat international dishes or have grown up with nonGreenlandic dishes will find it valuable and attractive to eat reintroduced Greenlandic dishes in 2035. This applies to local handicrafts as well.

Changing consumer behaviour toward sustainability and climate change mitigation was raised as an opportunity in the Faroes’ workshop and also raised in the Forestry workshop. In the Faroes, this was in relation to fish farming and the basic demand was seen that production should be sustainable. Arctic youth workshop participants saw the reduction of consumption as an opportunity.

4.2 Threats for the Arctic development

Climate change was raised as one of the most important threat issues in almost all regions. It was seen as threatening local industries and nature in Inari, causing invasion of new species and collapse of local fish and king crab stocks in Varangerfjord, and increasing health problems

and viruses and the loss of biodiversity by the Arctic youth workshop. In the Faroes' scenario work, carbon footprint of long-distance travelling was also seen as a climate change related threat while in Malå a tourism-related worry was that effects on the length of ski season.

The threat of *global and foreign companies and investors* coming to the area was raised in several regions. In Forestry workshop, the point of view was that national political decisions might favour foreign companies and in Malå the wind power and mining-related worry was about financial benefits going to global corporations instead of local economy. In Greenland, this topic was one of the biggest threats: Greenland was feared to be opened to foreign investors and outside actors which are invited to “a big self-service table” and local Greenlandic population will be left as outside spectators without any say. However, there were divided opinions as some welcomed rapid capacity development with foreign investors. In any case, the need for better regulation and control over rapidly increasing tourism and other activities was demanded in Nuuk. In the Faroes, the workshop participants painted a worrying picture of the situation that tourism enterprises that have been developed by local entrepreneurs are becoming profitable, and are then bought up by outside investors, which means that locals lose control.

Land use and natural resource related *conflicts* were expected to emerge in several scenario work processes. In Forestry Delphi survey, land use conflicts were on the top of the threat list expecting to cause strong polarization, exclusion of indigenous Sámi people and disputes over forest land use. These same worries were raised in Inari workshop: disputes were expected to lead to the lack of trust between the Sámi and Finnish population and, thus, make cooperation difficult. In the Faroes, nature-based tourism was seen as potentially conflicting if the local landowners and other stakeholders are not heard. Also, political opposition to the growth of the fish farming industry was also considered a threat in the Faroes. In Varangerfjord, the concern about conflict was about the competition of resources with Russia. In relation to natural resource use, *overconsumption* (Inari) and increase of consumerism (Youth group) were seen as negatively impacting local and indigenous communities.

Pace of change and demographic issues were raised in many ways. While depopulation, outmigration and lack of young people is commonly seen as a threat (mentioned e.g. in Malå, Westfjords and Varangerfjord) there are such areas as Nuuk and Inari where tourism is developing and which are attracting newcomers. In these latter ones, the threat of too rapid changes was discussed in scenario work. In Nuuk, this issue was raised in the context of traditional ways of life which were seen as threatened due to nature protection and change

from traditional livelihoods to new industries, especially tourism. In Inari, rapid increase in the number of residents was seen as being problematic from local infrastructure and natural values point of view. Increase of population was in relation to climate change as well. Youth group ended up to the threat scenario where climate change is pushing people toward the Arctic in search of better conditions from other parts of the world, but this migration has its challenges, because these vulnerable areas cannot tolerate so many people.

Land ownership was a concern in relation indigenous peoples' lives as well in Inari, Malå as in Nuuk, though in a different ways. In Nuuk, a recognized threat was that there is a movement from collective ownership to owner-oriented interaction with nature which might lead to the disregard of the original Inuit culture. In Inari, the trampling of the land use rights of the indigenous Sámi was seen as a threat but, on the other hand, preventing land use and zoning in the Sámi area because of unclear land use rights worried as well. In Malå, the intensification of forestry in combination with mining, hydro power, wind power, tourism and infrastructure was regarded as threatening both reindeer husbandry and the Sámi culture. See the summary of all opportunities and threats on Table 2.

[Table 2. Summary of opportunities and threats.](#)

Theme (+opportunity, -threat)	Nature	Climate change	Natural resource use	Global investments	Demography	Indigenous issues
Scenario process						
Forestry, FI, SE	+ nature-based livelihoods; public access - Green transition threatening	+ increases forest growth and attractiveness of the region; lifestyle change	+ society secures use; locals benefit; resource efficiency increases - disputes	- Green transition investments cause conflicts; wind and solar power profits go outside local communities	+ many "economic legs" attracting more people	
Inari, FI	+ clean, diverse, attractive	+ attraction of mild climate - lack of mitigation; restrictions; increase in pests	+ sustainable policy - unsustainable policy; threat to nature; conflicts	+ investments to the area - Lack of investments; foreign investors with no benefits to locals	+ increase in population along tourism jobs - lack of housing; aging population	+ balance between indigenous rights and freedom of livelihoods; cultural centre for the Sámi; appreciation of the Sámi culture - appropriation of the Sámi culture; land use modes causing problems
Malå, SE	+ nature-based activities	+ climate-smart products; new residents - reindeer husbandry suffers; shorter ski season	+ existence of nat res; sustainable use - exploitation; restrictions	- Benefits go to global corporations		+ good dialogue; Sámi culture profiling the region - cumulative land use effects causing pressure to the Sámi lands
Nuuk, GL	+ way of life - vulnerability	+ more local food	+ zoning for good coexistence; potential - traditions lost; locals neglected	+ foreign investors in harmony with Greenlandic culture - foreign investors		+ development in harmony with Inuit and Greenlandic culture + revivalisation of Inuit culture through tourism - tourism industry prioritized on the cost of indigenous Greenlanders
Suðuroy, FO	+ experiences in nature - carrying capacity	+ multi-trophic aquaculture; changing consumer behavior; domestic tourism; self sufficiency - Extreme weather events; air traffic		- Foreign and outside investors	- aging population	
Varanger, NO	+ nature-based activities	+ north-east passage - invasive species	+ new food resources; green transition jobs - difficult to reconcile; overexploitation; competition			
Westfjords, IS	+ conservation; attraction	- cc as such			+ nature attracts new residents - depopulation	
Youth, INT	+ nature conservation - nature suffering	- refugees; extreme weather events, uncertainty	+ recycling - increase in demand; conflicts		+ remote work attracts returning migrants	+ indig and local peoples' voice heard more - consumerism's negative impact on indig communities

4.3 Region-specific futures

As part of the future work, different scenarios were constructed in every region and hub, where the work was done. Depending on the region, it varied, how the scenarios were drafted. The research group formulated the drafts of the scenarios based on either a survey and a workshop, or only a workshop. These scenarios would be then sent to the participants, who could still influence, comment, and change the scenarios, by another workshop, email or via virtual meeting. The processes of each hubs and future works can be seen in in Section 3.

4.3.1. Inari, Finland (Tourism and indigenous cultures hubs)

The scenario building process of Inari (see section 3.1), resulted in three different scenarios presented on Table 3, and named as follows: Scenario 1 (Emphasizing opportunities): ‘Harmony of Clean Nature and Livelihoods’, Scenario 2 (Emphasizing threats): ‘Land trampled by exploitation and masses’, Scenario 3 (Most likely future development): ‘Middle path-Stability with Local Strengths’. The first scenario, which emphasized opportunities of Inari region by 2035, highlighted a future with a strong economy based on sustainable practices with self-sufficient energy production, and all-year-round nature-based tourism grounded on the local conditions and Sámi culture.

The second scenario emphasizing threats highlighted a future with the continuing conflicts on land use, uncontrolled tourism and lack of housing, while climate change, and exploitation of natural resources are causing suffering nature and people.

The third scenario emphasized the sustainable innovations and diversified use of forests, which enhances the well-being of the community, but also highlighted the continuing challenges in reconciling land use modes, the environmental toll of tourism and concerns on external decision-making.

Table 3. Keywords of the Inari region’s scenarios.

Hubs	Region	Name of the scenario	Key words
Tourism, indigenous cultures	Inari, FI	Harmony between clean nature and livelihoods	Strong economy based on local conditions, conflicts mitigated, lack of workforce and housing solved, more jobs and people, Sámi culture and livelihoods flowering, more conservation acts, Lake Inari a national park, new sustainable fuels, selfsufficient and sustainable energy production, all year round nature-based and sustainable tourism, tourist tax

Tourism, indigenous cultures	Inari, FI	Land trampled by exploitation and masses	Lack of workforce and housing, polarization, weak dependency ratio, decisions made elsewhere, Sámi culture and languages weaken, nature-based livelihoods cannot adapt, over-grazing, extreme weather, mining, nature suffers, invasive species and pests, problems of availability of energy, no forestry, mass tourism not in control, Arctic Railway
Tourism, indigenous cultures	Inari, FI	The middle way - stability through local strengths	Education, more people, conflicts on land use, lack of Sámi language teaching, Sámi culture and Arctic interest, nature-based livelihoods suffer: more focus on tourism, winter tourism suffers, more focus on summer tourism lack of workforce, nature suffers due climate change, regional pricing of energy, biogas and small-scale energy production, multiuse of forests

4.3.2. Northern Finland and Sweden (Forestry hub)

The scenario building process of the forestry hub in Northern Finland and Sweden, which was based on Kemi (see more in section 3.2), resulted in five different scenarios: Forestry growth conditioned by green transition, Local drawbacks from external land use control, Empowered northern communities, Climate and nature first, and Locally conflicting land use interests (see Table 4).

The first scenario 'Forestry growth conditioned by green transition' emphasized a future where the forestry growth in Northern Finland and Sweden faces constraints from EU biodiversity goals, but targeted programs promote sustainable practices, job creation, and innovation.

In the second scenario ‘Local drawbacks from external land use control’ EU regulations are impacting forestry in Northern Finland and Sweden, challenging timber's green energy status. Tourism rises amid environmental concerns, affecting forestry's societal acceptance.

The third scenario ‘Empowered northern communities’ highlights a society which prioritizes sustainable resource use, enhancing decision-making inclusivity and promoting economic growth in northern areas through biobased circular economy and tourism.

In the fourth scenario ‘Climate and nature first’ the development of the area is strongly influenced by biodiversity and climate regulations, fostering sustainable practices, indigenous involvement, and carbon sequestration.

The fifth scenario ‘Locally conflicting land use interests’ highlights a future with the continuing conflicts over land and forest use, and different livelihoods, while EU regulations affect the development.

Table 4. Keywords of the Northern Finland and Sweden’s scenarios.

Hub	Region	Name of the scenario	Key words
Forestry	Northern Finland and Sweden	Forestry growth conditioned by green transition	Increased forest growth, more jobs, wind power, adapted forestry methods due climate change and biodiversity loss, compensation programs, lean forestry participatory planning, alternative forest products
Forestry	Northern Finland and Sweden	Local drawbacks from external land use control	EU regulation on biodiversity and climate change, use of wood decreases, geopolitical instability, multi-use of forests, polarization, state of environment and nature improves, ecological compensations, wind and solar power, co-planning methods, circular economy, green transition
Forestry	Northern Finland and Sweden	Empowered northern communities	harmonious use of natural resources, local benefit, sustainable tourism, more jobs, multi-use of forests, more people, biodiversity, wood as sustainable material, participatory methods, less conflicts, green transition

Forestry	Northern Finland and Sweden	Climate and nature first	EUs climate and conservation regulations, sustainable practices and technology, locals and indigenous people involved in decision-making, sustainable tourism and forest use, land use heavily restricted, more areas protected, ecological compensations, no green transition as such, consumption of wood decreasing, effective recycling, change of lifestyles
Forestry	Northern Finland and Sweden	Locally conflicting land use interests	Disputes and conflicts on EU regulations, land use, restorations and carbon sequestration, green transition, wind power implementation; wood use decreases, decision done elsewhere, decrease in labor availability and employment, new methods for collaborative planning, economic value of non-timber products increase

4.3.3. Malå, Sweden (Forestry hub)

The results from the scenario building process in Malå, Sweden, described in section 3.3, are represented on Table 5. There were two scenarios drafted by researchers based on survey results on key threats and opportunities in combination with the Malå region specific forest resource assessment. The scenarios were named as Focus on growth and Focus on Diversity, which highlighted different development strategies in the future.

In the scenario 'Focus on Diversity' Malå region prioritizes sustainable development within the ecological boundaries, emphasizing local food sources, renewable energy, responsible land use, and cooperation efforts.

The second scenario 'Focus on Growth' highlights the North which thrives with improved infrastructure, investments in green industries, job creation, and community development, where challenges include external control, climate impact, and labor scarcity.

Table 5. Keywords of the Malå region’s scenarios.

Hub	Region	Name of the scenario	Key words
Forestry, mining, indigenous culture	Malå, SE	Focus on Diversity	Restructuring of industries and management of natural resources to ecologically sustainable, precompensation restorations, multiple use of forests, CCF-methods, carbon sequestration, raising awareness and confidence about the Malå region's possibilities.
Forestry, mining, indigenous culture	Malå, SE	Focus on Growth	Values created stays in the region, new jobs in sawmills/wood processing and mining, immigration and increased tax power, attractive living environments in urban areas and the countryside supporting remote work, small business, increased self-sufficiency in food and better crisis preparedness, developed infrastructure, hydropower, lack of workforce, climate change, threat to reindeer husbandry

4.3.4. Suðuroy, Faroe Islands (Tourism and fish farming hubs)

The scenario building process in Suðuroy, Faroe Islands, described in section 3.4, resulted in four different scenarios: Business-as-usual, Isolation and recession, Alternative sustainability, and Technofix to current problems (see Table 6).

In the first scenario, “Business-as-usual”, Suðuroy has continued on its development trajectory and has been successful in attracting some outside investments, which have improved the infrastructure, including the construction of the subsea tunnel, but which have also risen the ecological footprints of the local economy. To address these problems, green energy investments have been implemented causing conflicts on land use.

The second scenario, “Isolation and recession” highlights the future, where the proposed subsea tunnel is stalled due to economic challenges, affecting industries, tourism, and population growth, straining welfare services.

The third scenario “Alternative sustainability” focuses on legislation which concentrates on sustainability, raising environmental awareness, and innovations which reshape Suðuroy,

moving away from the proposed tunnel and large-scale fish farming to focus on eco-friendly industry and renewable energy.

In the fourth scenario “Technofix to current problems” the technological development has finally managed the problems of the development, including the subsea tunnel, green energy, offshore industry, and digitized services, fostering economic growth and tourism.

Table 6. Keywords of the Suðuroy region’s scenarios.

Hub	Region	Name of the scenario	Key words
Tourism, fish farming	Suðuroy, FO	Business-as-usual	new investments, infrastructure; subsea tunnel, ecological footprints rising, green energy, land use conflicts, population stable
Tourism, fish farming	Suðuroy, FO	Isolation and recession	no subsea tunnel, economic recession, partial collapse of fisheries, no all-year-round tourism, population aging and not grown, problems in welfare services
Tourism, fish farming	Suðuroy, FO	Alternative sustainability	sustainability, environmental awareness, sustainable innovations, no subsea tunnel, fish viruses etc., end of large-scale fish farming, eco-friendly industries, renewable energy
Tourism, fish farming	Suðuroy, FO	Technofix to current problems	technological development and solutions, subsea tunnel, electrification of transport, renewable energy, increasing carbon footprints, relocating marine related industries, migrant workforce, tourism

4.3.5. Nuuk, Greenland (Tourism and indigenous hubs)

The scenario building process in Nuuk, Greenland, described in section 3.5 resulted in 35 different scenarios, divided by opportunity and threat scenarios, all working with five themes: local tourism, the local Greenlandic culture, the local hunting and fishing industry, climate change, and ecologically and culturally sustainable business development.

The opportunity scenarios were named as followed: Broad support for holistic tourism development, Year schedule of tourist activities – when and where, Joint coordinated cruise tourism and other tourist activities, High-quality dissemination manuals, Tourism Act, Tax and

fee arrangement, Restriction of tourism and zoning of the country, Community dialogue on how favorite areas for traditional use should be accessed, Control and monitoring, Loan options for locals to ensure local anchoring of tourism, Spread the tourist flow and spread the earnings to many, Diverse culture, Diverse culture, Strengthening the diverse Greenlandic culture, Skin sewing houses, Artists and cultural actors will be key players in the tourism industry, Tourism as a subject and more tourism education, Community dialogue on how new drivers affect locals ways of life, Professional structural conditions strengthen the local hunting and fishing industry, Increased equal cooperation with fishermen and hunters, The municipality's fishing plan, Increased consumption of local foods, Less sea ice and year-round tourism, Not only sustainable but also regenerative, and Expensive travel destination targeted adventure tourists.

The threat scenarios were named as followed: Lack of regulation, coordination and overview of tourist activities, Opening the country to foreign investors, Local anchorage or spectator of the development, Rapid pace of development will risk pushing local anchorage aside, From an embarrassed people to a proud people, Unique handicraft products or mass-produced souvenirs, Catch and fishing quotas and bans can have unintended consequences, From hunting to halibut fishing and now what?, We do not own, but borrow the right to use land and fjord area, Lack of reciprocal considerations will create conflicts of interest, The Navy's unnecessary navigation in the fjord, and Waste in nature.

4.3.6. Varanger, Norway (Fish farming, tourism and mining hubs)

The scenario building process of Varanger region in Norway described in section 3.6, including fish farming, tourism and mining hubs resulted in five scenarios (see Table 7). The key driver of the first scenario 'Green growth' is green transition, and the scenario describes a future where the need for new solutions have resulted in economic growth and optimism in the region, and Varangerfjord is the starting point for transportation of goods through the east passage, from west to east. Both fisheries and aquaculture have developed positively. Global warming has impacts on wild fish stocks and winter tourism.

The key drivers of the second scenario 'Arctic Urbanity' are identity and culture, which are being used for growing the region. The scenario represents a vision how people-oriented change may drive development. In this scenario, the key concerns are attracting young people to the area.

The key driver of the third scenario 'Traditionalist Trap' is the preservation of traditional industries, which restricts the growth of new industries with young, educated workforce.

The key drivers of the fourth scenario ‘Ghost Town’ are the increasing demand for food and economic growth, and climate change. These drivers are putting too much pressure on the ecosystem of the area, and it results in an environmentally unsustainable use of the resources of the fjord, with loss of ecosystem services. This has implications on the economic and social situation, as well as the cultural identity, and the demand for resources drivers into geopolitical conflicts transforming Varanger into a military defense hub.

The focus of the fifth scenario ‘Emerging Coexistence’ is the social license for aquaculture, which results in a successful coexistence between the new and traditional industries, where cooperation between different industries creates synergies.

Table 6. The keywords of Varangerfjord future scenarios.

Hub	Region	Name of the scenario	Key words
Fish farming, tourism and mining	Varangerfjord, NO	Green growth	EU legislation, fishing and aquaculture industry, social license to operate (SLO), new aquaculture sites and technologies, traditional and new fisheries, economic growth, spin off effect, technology providers, new inhabitants, positive view, Sámi rights, coastal planning, local knowledge, closed and semi-closed systems, best practices, critical performance indices, local identity, zero waste, circular bioeconomy
Fish farming, tourism and mining	Varangerfjord, NO	Arctic Urbanity	Young people, combination of naturalistic and urban lifestyle, global influences, arts, transforming, industries, creative studies, cultural heritage, pride, identity, storytelling, international attention
Fish farming, tourism and mining	Varangerfjord, NO	The traditionalist trap/Ghost towns	Traditional fisheries, fishing tourism, lost jobs, pressure on wild fish stocks, Sámi rights, fish processing, limited activity, stagnation, decline, population pyramid, outmigration, gender misbalance, Varanger landscape, vulnerable system, former residents, reduced tax income
Fish farming, tourism and mining	Varangerfjord, NO	Blue desert	worst case combination, changing climate, aquaculture, fisheries, overexploitation, eutrophication, decrease, natural resources disappeared, unstable ecosystem, moratorium, geopolitical instability, carrying capacity, jellyfish invasions, toxic algae blooms, denied access, conflicts, loss of cultural identity

Fish farming, tourism and mining	Varangerfjord, NO	Emerging coexistence	Efficient, productive, fisheries and aquaculture, cooperation, synergy effects, constructive dialog, common knowledge basis, municipality planning processes, ownership, trust, local authorities, facilitation, meeting places, technological development, profitability, year-round workplaces, environmental, resilient local economy, monitoring technology, multidisciplinary education programs, sustainability, cultural identity, social environment
----------------------------------	-------------------	----------------------	--

4.3.7. Westfjords, Iceland (Fish farming and tourism hubs)

The first scenario ‘Transportation infrastructure development - a pivotal factor for the region’s future prosperity’ highlights a future where better transportation infrastructure improves the connections between settlements, making the road system more reliable, resilient and safe, supporting the overall development of the area and making it more attractive for new businesses and services.

The second scenario ‘Community-based controlled development of industries’ highlighted a future, where land uses and industries’ development is controlled by the community through public participation based on social license to operate frameworks (SLO). This results in limited business growth with longer consultation phases, more local acceptance and citizen empowerment, transparency and communication by economic players and possibly the implementation of more sustainable practices.

The third scenario ‘Interaction of economy, infrastructure and transportation’ sees a future, where strong global companies in aquaculture coexist with small family-owned tourism companies which are confronted to lack of robust infrastructure and reliable, year-round transportation system, affecting their competitiveness and viability.

In the fourth scenario ‘The viability of the communities’, demographic issues such as a widening gender gap, threatens the viability of the region, and the economy is mainly concentrating in fisheries and aquaculture, and foreign residents are not actively participating in the communities, and a more sustainable development of communities is needed.

The fifth scenario ‘Aquaculture-driven community development’ sees a future where the development of aquaculture and fish processing facilities increases and provides more revenues for the municipalities, attracting more residents. Beyond a certain population threshold, the diversity of employment and business opportunities increases, but there is a

high reliance on fisheries and aquaculture, exposing the community to market fluctuations, potential resource overuse and environmental factors.

The sixth scenario ‘Tourism-driven community development’ highlights a future, where tourism is being developed through the consolidation and expansion of infrastructure, services, and available activities related to natural and cultural heritage of the area. The capacity of the area increases to accommodate more cruise ships in the region as well as more exclusive products. Employment in the area is more diverse but remains highly seasonal and low-paid, which is a limit to attract permanent residents and new families.

Table 7. Keywords of the Westfjords region’s scenarios.

Hubs	Region	Name of the scenario	Keywords
Aquaculture and tourism	Westfjords, IS	Transportation infrastructure development - a pivotal factor for the region future prosperity.	Infrastructure, maintenance, increased access, connections, reliability, security, tunnels under the mountains/fjords, national policy, harbour developments, air travel infrastructure, public transportation system, pedestrian and cyclists, lack of funding
Aquaculture and tourism	Westfjords, IS	Community-based controlled development of industries	Social License to Operate, public participation, Corporate Social
			Responsibility, destination branding, image of the Westfjords, sustainable practices, setting limits in size (e.g. cruise ships) and numbers, establishing standards and requirements, suitable infrastructure, moderate speed of change
Aquaculture and tourism	Westfjords, IS	Interaction of economy, infrastructure and transportation	Strong global companies in aquaculture, small family-owned companies in tourism, lack of infrastructure, unstable transportation, viability of industries and livelihoods are threatened
Aquaculture and tourism	Westfjords, IS	The viability of the communities	Demographic issues (e.g. widening gender gap), women and young people moving away, viability is threatened, monotonous economy; mostly jobs in primary production in fisheries and aquaculture, jobs that require education and specialization needed, far away from more urbanized communities with more service and cultural activities, foreign migrants not participating in communities’ activities

Aquaculture and tourism	Westfjords, IS	Aquaculture-driven community development	Development of aquaculture on land / off-shore, fish processing facilities and plants, further processing of seaproducts, increased value creation, diversity of employment and business opportunities, vulnerability to climate change, incentives for sustainability, reputational damage and prejudice from ill-practices can affect the markets
Aquaculture and tourism	Westfjords, IS	Tourism-driven community development	Development of tourism infrastructure, accommodation, transportation, services, restaurants, cruise ships, excursions, fishing, retreat, workcation, geothermal resorts, hotel development, wellness tourism, landscape therapy, wilderness tourism, national parks and nature trails, recreational areas, cultural heritage, local food and drink products, seasonality and precarity of jobs often low-paid

4.3.8. Arctic youth

The results of the scenario building process of the common Arctic youth workshop held in Inari, Finland, and described in section 3.8, concluded to two different scenarios, one emphasizing threats: ‘What have we done – the crisis of everything’, and the other one emphasizing opportunities: ‘The Arctic Dream’.

The first scenario is living in a future, where the Arctic is near to its tipping point with climate change effects, biodiversity loss, and cultural decline. Natural resources are being exploited, fostering conflicts, and urbanization is diminishing rural areas. In the second scenario the Arctic is thriving with collaborative politics, cleaner environments, and empowered communities and Sámi culture, fostering harmony and sustainability.

Table 9. Keywords of the arctic youth scenarios.

Hub	Region	Name of the scenario	Key words
-----	--------	----------------------	-----------

All	International (youth)	What have we done - crisis of everything	Extreme weather events, climate change, health problems, nature and naturebased livelihoods suffer, traditional culture and knowledge fades away, uncertainty, migration towards the Arctic, conflicts, rural areas dwindling, consumerism, overcrowded mass tourism, technological development on energy production, carbon capture, polarization
All	International (youth)	The Arctic Dream	Better politics, locals and indigenous peoples involved in decision-making, collaboration, open communication, education, self-sufficiency, care for the environment, remote work, more people, strong communities, conservation of nature, conflicts mitigated, harmonious relationship between people and nature

4.4 Hub-specific future narratives: Tourism, Fish farming & fisheries, Mining and Indigenous culture

When looking at the hub industries across the Arctic, it is obvious that in their future prospects they have both similarities and differences which are analysed here on the basis of all scenario reports. From the scenario reports we have read what has been discussed of different hub industries regardless which hub has been in focus. Here the focus is on tourism, fish farming and fisheries, mining, and indigenous culture. Forestry futures are not discussed here as the forestry scenario work done in northern Finland and Sweden covered forestry futures well.

4.4.1. Tourism

In the rapid growth of Arctic tourism such issues as overtourism, social and ecological sustainability of cruise ship tourism, changing snow conditions and questions related to the future of air traffic have been raised in tourism research (Jóhannesson et al. 2022; Ólafsdóttir et al 2020; Saarinen & Varnajot 2019). In their spatial study on the Arctic tourism footprint based on social media data, Runge et al (2020) found out that the increase has indeed been rapid in some places while large parts of the Arctic remain untouched by tourism.

In our Arctic youth workshop, altogether 14 young people from Greenland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden, and Finland gathered discussing the future of the Arctic region, and tourism emerged as a central part of the future threat scenario. Their justification for talking about tourism instead e.g., of mining was that they saw tourism usually marketed as a benefactor for remote regions. However, the downsides of tourism have seldom been pointed out. The disadvantages of tourism which this group of young people raised were that “must-see” places and especially wilderness areas become overcrowded, cruise tourism is not socially sustainable, nature will suffer and there is no funding to build the needed infrastructure.

The emphasis on high quality nature-based tourism was present in all scenarios. Well-planned and regulated tourism growth benefitting local communities was seen as an opportunity. While high revenue, low impact tourism was seen as an opportunity, mass tourism was regarded as threat to nature and local life (Inari, FI), small communities (Nuuk, GL) and resulting to the erosion of biodiversity (Suđuroy, FO).

Mainly tourism was seen positively as a green business (Malå, SE; Varanger, NO) and also a new opportunity in a situation where e.g. fisheries and fish farming have been taken over by outside investors (Suđuroy, FO). An often-mentioned benefit of tourism is that it offers jobs for young people and attracts new inhabitants to the areas although it can also compete of work force between extractive industries.

The threats of tourism based on the results are especially related to the fact that local decision-making power is lost, and the profits go outside the region. In Nuuk, these doubts were the strongest and a new tourism act was demanded. Also, the idea of entrance fees and additional taxes were raised. Similarly, in Suđuroy, the need for planning was emphasised. In addition to local planning the need for regional and national discussion and control over the development of tourism was recognised. If properly planned, more tourists could visit. Both in the Faroes and in Greenland tourism is recently getting more importance in economy.

Another threat expressed in relation to tourism in many scenario processes was the antagonism between tourism actors and other land users. In an ideal situation, discussions and negotiations between forestry and other livelihoods such as reindeer husbandry and tourism have been developed towards suitable solutions (Forestry, FI, SE). In Nuuk, involving locals to tourism planning and directing tourism activities to specific zones was seen an answer. Also, planning of cruise tourism should take place in consultation with other users, especially Greenlandic fishermen and hunters.

4.4.2. Fish farming and fisheries

Fish farming and fisheries were in focus especially in four scenario processes, i.e. Westfjords, Nuuk, Suđuroy and Varanger. Environmental consequences, possible unsustainability and reputation of fish farming were present in the discussions. Also, tensions between industries such as fisheries and tourism (Nuuk, GL) and fish farming and fisheries (Varanger, NO) were expressed.

In Westfjords, fish farming was seen as the most important opportunity for the region but prejudices due to negative news on the industry were seen as a threat. Similarly, to Nuuk, fisheries was seen as a traditional industry to Varangerfjord and fishing was seen as possible to combine with fishing tourism. In Varanger, most agree that more local management of fish resources is needed, and that better consultation with the local population is important for fisheries development. In Varanger's "Traditionalist trap" scenario traditional fisheries were prioritized over aquaculture while in "Green growth" and "Coexistence between aquaculture and fisheries" scenarios improvements in aquaculture technology were seen as reducing impact on fisheries and creating local identity around seafood region.

4.4.3. Mining

The only scenario process where mining was explicitly touched upon was Malå, Sweden, although not as a main topic. Also, in Inari, Finland and in Forestry scenario process mining was discussed. In Malå, the vision was that all the natural assets (minerals, soil, water and forests) should be managed properly i.e. with consideration to the living environment. Major investments in mining and the sawmill guarantee jobs, competitiveness, innovations, and confidence in the future. Yet, caution should be applied in allowing new mines as they may have a negative impact on the quality of the water resources which was seen as the most important environmental threat. Water protection was raised in relation to mining also in Inari with the threat scenario where mining industry comes to Inari and destroys the extremely important Lake Inari and its catchment area.

In Inari, mines were coupled with other "unsustainable natural resources policy" such as wind power but also with mass tourism. The fear was expressed that decision-makers' opinions would change positively towards mines and wind power although at the present state policy is that no wind farms or mines will be established to the Finnish Sámi region. In Norway, the discussion on 'green colonialism' has been going on especially in relation to wind power (Normann 2021) while in Finland it has been related to mining as well (Sorvali et al. 2023).

4.4.4. Indigenous culture

Indigenous hubs in the scenario work were Inari, Nuuk, Malå, and Varanger. What is common for all these hubs is that land use situations are complex and the pressures to the traditional land and sea use modes are multiple.

Malå represents a complex situation of forestry, mining and wind power developments, and infrastructure projects overlapping with the land use needs of Sámi reindeer husbandry. It becomes obvious that strong emphasis on the development of extractive industries causes threats to the future of the Sámi livelihoods. The threats expressed include the combined effects of infrastructure, forest felling and hydropower, and the mines splitting Sámi reindeer herding villages and wind turbines disturbing the reindeer's grazing peace. The tensions in the area are visible in the opposite threat expressed in Malå scenario work, namely the threat that the Sámi people and the environmental movement put an end to forest management and mineral extraction. This draws a picture resembling that from Inari region which was formulated that disputes between different groups and businesses are a major threat in relation to land use and natural resource policy. It was feared that conflicts would also cause the erosion of cooperation and trust between different actors and that conflicts would grow between the Sámi and the Finns (Inari, FI).

The tensions between original Inuit culture and modern Greenlandic culture were expressed in Nuuk scenario work where the worry was that tourism images are based on the frozen tradition and not to a new narrative of proud people. In the best case, tourism was seen as having a power to reintroduce revitalised cultural values and traditions from the Inuit culture. The future opportunities of indigenous cultures are related exactly to this identity level, proudness of people (Nuuk, GL), uniqueness of indigenous culture which have a prominent role in profiling the region (Malå, SE) and growing appreciation of vital indigenous culture (Inari, FI).

Several questions common also to other Indigenous hub regions were raised in Nuuk, Greenland, for further discussions: 1) how external drivers affect local living conditions and what needs to be done to preserve important parts of culture, ways of life and natural conditions, 2) how to deal with land and sea areas of local indigenous users, if these areas come into play for tourist activities, 3) how the principle of collective common ownership of the land and its natural resources is to be understood and 4) how the rights of indigenous peoples (ILO Convention 169) are to be understood and complied with when making decisions

about the use of natural resources that will have consequences on indigenous peoples' ways of life.

5. Conclusions

Different regions and hubs have had slightly different scenarios processes but the question of threats and opportunities in each of the hubs has been included in all scenario work. In the scenarios, different forces of change were taken widely into account. Vulnerability of nature and the need for sustainable use of natural resources are common to most of the scenario processes. Climate change seemed to worry most the Youth group while in other scenario processes the positive sides of climate change were raised. Business actors seemed to see the possibilities of climate change related green transition while the modes green transition takes worried e.g. reindeer herders.

The negative sides of tourism were raised by the Youth group more than others. However, in tourism almost all tourism hubs emphasized high-level tourism instead of mass tourism though this difference was vaguely defined. Especially emerging tourism areas of the Faroes and Greenland were emphasizing restrictions and sustainable planning of tourism.

In Nuuk, GL and Suðuroy, FO, foreign investments were worrying workshop participants more than in other regions. When it comes to the hub industries, tourism and reindeer herding were seen as more local and sustainable than mining and fish farming where the threat of foreign investments was more present. Outside regulation was a topic in regions belonging to EU.

Many scenarios addressed the themes which were seen having both opportunities and threats. This applies as well to the development of industries such as tourism, fish farming and forestry, as to big societal and environmental changes such as climate change, population change or technological change. The most difficult question might be the overall change of lifestyles which was raised in the youth workshop and also referred to in other workshops. However, generally, emphasis on local level and local identities – or local proud as it was formulated in Nuuk, GL – was extremely important. Tackling population changes is of utmost important from this perspective. All this puts pressures on local decision-makers and to the need to combine the wider global change to local way of life. Thus, the ArcticHubs future work process continues by evaluating the scenarios made and introducing them to the decisionmakers and raising a discussion how to consider them in land use planning and in developing the livelihoods.

6. References

- Bell, W. 1997. Foundations of futures studies – Human science for a new era. Volume I. New Brunswick: Transaction publishers.
- Glenn, J. C. & Gordon, T.J. (2009). Futures Research Methodology Version 3.0 Millennium Project. Available at <https://www.millennium-project.org/publications-2/futuresresearch-methodology-version-3-0/>
- Heleniak, T. (2021) The future of the Arctic populations, *Polar Geography*, 44:2, 136-152, DOI: 10.1080/1088937X.2019.1707316
- Hsieh, H. F., & Shannon, S. E. (2005). Three approaches to qualitative content analysis. *Qualitative health research*, 15(9), 1277-1288.
- Jóhannesson, G. T., Welling, J., Müller, D. K., Lundmark, L., Nilsson, R. O., de la Barre, S., Granås, B., Kvidal-Røvik, T., Rantala, O., Tervo-Kankare, O. & Maher, P. (2022). Arctic Tourism in Times of Change: Uncertain Futures – From overtourism to Restarting Tourism. Nordic Council of Ministers.
- Kahn, H. and Wiener, A.J. 1967. *The Year 2000: A framework for speculation on the next thirty-three years*. New York: MacMillan.
- Kuusi, O. 1999. Expertise in the future use of generic technologies. Epistemic and methodological considerations concerning Delphi studies. Helsinki: HeSE Print.
- Linstone, H. A., and Turoff, M. 1975. *The Delphi method: Techniques and applications*. Available https://www.foresight.pl/assets/downloads/publications/Turoff_Linstone.pdf
- Lowe, P., Phillipson, J., Proctor, A., & Gkartzios, M. (2019). Expertise in rural development: A conceptual and empirical analysis. *World Development*, 116, 28-37.
- Megatrends. (2011). TemaNord Copenhagen: Nordic Council of Ministers; 2011. Available from: <http://www.norden.org/no/publikasjoner/publikasjoner/201152>
- Normann, S. (2021). Green colonialism in the Nordic context: Exploring Southern Saami representations of wind energy development. *Journal of community psychology*, 49(1), 77-94.
- Ólafsdóttir, R., Tuulentie, S., Hovgaard, G., Zinglensen, K., Svartá, M, Poulsen, H. & Søndergaard, M. (2020) The contradictory role of tourism in the northern peripheries: Overcrowding, overtourism and the importance of tourism for rural development. In McDonagh, J. & Tuulentie, S. (eds) *Sharing Knowledge for Land Use Management Decision-Making and Expertise in Europe's Northern Periphery*. Edward Elgar Publishing, Cheltenham, 86-99.
- Piipponen Sirkka-Liisa & Kurikka Päivi. (2020). *Opas kuntalaisten osallistumisen arviointiin*. Available at <https://www.kuntaliitto.fi/julkaisut/2020/2059-opas-kuntalaistenosallistumisen-arviointiin>
- Rikkonen, P & Tapio, P. (2009). Future prospects of alternative agro-based bioenergy use in Finland - constructing scenarios with quantitative and qualitative delphi data. *Technological forecasting and social change* Parkkinen, M., Varho, V & Tapio, P. (2021). Five transition pathways to renewable energy futures—scenarios from a Delphi study on key drivers and policy options. *European journal of futures research* 9 1: 12 p. 76 7: 978-990. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2008.12.001>
- Rikkonen, P., Lauttamäki, V., <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40309-021-00185-0>
- Sorvali, J., Lyytimäki, J., Lähteenmäki-Uutela, A., Huttunen, S., Inkilä, E., Weckroth, M. & Tuulentie, S. (2023) Reiluus puntarissa: Kuusamon tuulivoima- ja kaivossuunnitelmat alueellisina kestävyyskiistoina oikeudessa, mediassa ja mielipiteissä. [Fairness on the

scale: the Kuusamo wind power and mining plans as regional sustainability disputes in law, media and opinions; in Finnish with English abstract]. *Alue&Ympäristö*, 52:2, 67-88.

7. Appendices

Scenario reports (below)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869580.

1.

Inari future paths Survey and workshop phase results

ArcticHubs project (<https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs>)

Pasi Rikkonen, Taru Rikkonen, Esa Inkilä, Pasi Rautio and Seija Tuulentie

Finnish report 19.6.2023 translated to English 18.12.2023

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869580.

Table on contents

1. Background and Objectives of Foresight Work	3
2. Introduction to the Foresight Process Step by Step	3
3. Results of the survey	4
3.1. Summary of the key opportunities for the positive development of Inari region/hub until 2035.	6
3.2 Summary of the key threats to the development of Inari region/hub until 2035	8
Other threats mentioned in the survey included Russia's impact on the Finnish economy, the threat of war, risks posed by reindeer husbandry to the local environment and other	

livelihoods, and a new pandemic.	10
3.3. Key results of the survey's future statements	10
Figure 10. Probability estimates by respondents for future statements related to tourism (five statements considered most important/significant).	13
4. Workshop I results	13
5. Workshop II results.....	16
Based on the discussions from workshop II, the scenarios were named as follows:	16
5.1 Scenario descriptions	16
Scenario 2: Land trampled by exploitation and masses'	18
Scenario 3: 'Middle path – stability with local strenghtes'	19
5.2 Future table	22
5.3 General Impacts of the Scenarios	25
6. Examination of scenario impacts in relation to future preparedness	26
6.1 Impacts and preparedness measures of the scenario "Harmony of clean nature and livelihoods" in different divisions in the Inari region	26
6.2 Impacts and preparedness measures of the scenario "The land trampled by exploitation and masses" in different divisions in the Inari region.....	29
6.3 Impacts and preparedness measures of the scenario "Middle path – stability with local strenghts" in different divisions in the Inari region	30
7. Summary	32
7.1 Conclusion	32
7.2 Examination of the method	33

1. Background and Objectives of Foresight Work

In the ArcticHubs project coordinated by the Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke) and funded by the EU (<https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs/>), sustainable solutions are developed to coordinate competing industries and land use practices in Arctic hub locations, taking into account the cultures of indigenous peoples, especially the Sámi in Fennoscandia and the Inuit in Greenland. The project focuses on key industries in the Arctic region, such as tourism, aquaculture, mining, and forestry, which hold significant societal and economic value in the regions. The project analyzes these industries in terms of their impact on ecosystem services and the well-being of local communities. In the ArcticHubs project, participatory foresight work is conducted for a total of seven defined hubs, assessing future opportunities, threats, and contemplating preparedness for the future.

2. Introduction to the Foresight Process Step by Step

The foresight process of the project consisted of five phases, exploring the future up to the year 2035. Initially, we engaged in discussions to locally identify factors and drivers influencing the future of the area. Based on this, in the second phase, we prepared a survey containing future statements relevant to the region, addressing key threats and opportunities. In the third phase, these results were brought for examination in Workshop I, where the most significant drivers of change were also prioritized, and their future directions were considered. In the fourth phase, the research team drafted scenario outlines based on the preceding phases, which were then discussed in the fifth phase, Workshop II. During this workshop, the scenario outlines were commented on, and their impacts were assessed (Figure 1).

Figure x: Progress of Inari scenario analysis in spring and early summer 2023.

3. Results of the survey

In the first phase, opinions about the future of the Inari region as part of the Arctic area were sought through a survey. Future development propositions for the Inari area until 2035 were formulated with the input of those familiar with the region.

The survey was conducted on the Maptionnaire survey platform and consisted of two separate sections. In Section 1, open-ended questions were used to explore the future possibilities and threats for the Inari area. Respondents were asked to first list what they considered to be the three most significant opportunities and then the three most significant threats to the positive development of the Inari area from the 2020s until 2035.

In Section 2, statements about future changes in the Inari area until 2035 were presented. Various future-related statements were assessed in two ways: first, respondents were asked to indicate how likely they thought the statement would come true, and second, how important or significant they perceived this statement to be for the future development of the Inari area.

A total of 31 respondents participated in the survey, and they identified their backgrounds in terms of work and expertise in the following groups (see Figure 2). The survey also inquired about the themes and questions that were most important to the respondents, as presented in Figure 3.

Figure x: Respondent background according to occupation or expertise in the survey.

Figure 3. Most important themes chosen by the respondents.

3.1. Summary of the key opportunities for the positive development of Inari region/hub until 2035.

Tourism

Tourism and the growth of tourism are considered one of the key factors for the positive future development of the Inari region. According to the survey, it is assumed to be sustainable, responsible, and well-managed. Inari is envisioned to become a center for highquality and sustainable tourism, where tourism services are developed in collaboration with experience industries, such as the film industry. Year-round tourism would be developed in partnership with the local community. A positive development is seen in organizing smallscale reindeer safaris in various locations during the winter. The expansion of program and content services is also seen as an opportunity. The pristine nature of the area particularly attracts nature-conscious eco-tourists, and the further development of tourism is aligned with the needs of nature. Safety is also seen as an opportunity for the region's development.

- Sustainable nature tourism
- Development of gold tourism
- Culture-oriented tourism
- Year-round tourism
- Cross-border tourism

The Sámi and culture

The location of the administrative center for Sámi culture in Inari, as well as the appreciation of Sámi people and the preservation of Sámi culture as vibrant, are seen as opportunities. Respecting traditional livelihoods and developing the area in collaboration with the Sámi people in accordance with the Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC) principle. Strengthening Sámi land rights through legislation and reaching an agreement on the Sámi Parliament Act are considered key factors for positive development according to the survey. Reverting to the traditional Sámi way of life is perceived as a positive development. Multiculturalism is also seen as an opportunity.

- Agreement on the Sámi Parliament Act
- Preservation of Sámi culture as vibrant
- Genuine respect of nature values
- Multiculturalism

Livelihoods

The harmonization of various livelihoods and land use patterns often emerged as a key opportunity for the region's development. Striking a balance between the rights of indigenous peoples, protection of private property, and economic freedom is seen as a positive development. Collaborative efforts and building stronger trust among regional stakeholders are also viewed as opportunities. The Arctic location is considered internationally unique for specialized industries such as automotive and cold testing. Regional, national, and international collaboration was also highlighted. Business activities related to winter conditions and serving as a testing ground for cold-resistant new technologies are generally seen as having a positive impact on the region. Forest industry supporting the green transition, opportunities brought by NATO, and investments in the region are also seen as opportunities.

- Arctic research
- Harmonization of livelihoods
- Arctic testing activities
- Sustainable natural resource policies
- Cross-border trade
- Safety for tourists and livelihoods
- Developing gold mining as ecologically sustainable small-scale mining
- Creating new employment opportunities

Planning and infrastructure

The maintenance of functional transportation connections and infrastructure is seen as an opportunity for the positive development of the area. Increasing plot availability, along with sustainable and long-term energy solutions that enable reasonable living costs, are also considered opportunities according to the survey. Developing the digital availability of services and having good remote connections are also seen as opportunities. A positive development

is perceived, according to one respondent, as slowing down growth and emphasizing conservation, rather than continuous economic growth or population influx.

- Maintenance of infrastructure
- Development of digital availability of services
- Sustainable and long-term energy solutions enabling reasonable living costs

Housing

The growth of the population, demographic structure, and personnel policies are considered a key opportunity for the area's development. The availability of housing is seen as important to attract workforce to the area. The increasing trend of remote work is also viewed as an opportunity. The pristine natural state of the area, along with its abundant fish species, attracts Finns who love nature and fishing to settle in Inari permanently and establish businesses. Job opportunities generated by tourism and the resulting population growth are also seen as opportunities. Ensuring healthcare services for local residents and visitors is considered a positive development for the future.

- Population growth
- Demographic structure and personnel policies
- Ensuring education for children and adults and providing sufficient resources for it • Developing remote work opportunities

Nature

According to the survey, factors contributing to the area's attractiveness include features such as clean nature, waters, lakes, forests, mountains, peace, silence, darkness, and the Northern Lights. These are perceived as key opportunities for the area's development. There is a variety of activities for those interested in nature-themed topics such as birds, plants, mushrooms, and insects. Innovations stemming from nature, such as superfoods or mysticism, are also seen as opportunities. One respondent sees the possibility of establishing Lake Inari National Park and systematically protecting the unique lake nature. Genuine respect for natural values and sustainable utilization of nature's resources are also seen as opportunities. Numerous small lakes, rivers, and ponds are considered an opportunity for positive development as recreational destinations.

- Clean and diverse nature
- Sustainable utilization of natural values
- Extent and diversity of protected areas
- Attractiveness factors: untouched nature (forests, lakes, mountains), peace, silence, darkness, snow, northern lights, etc.

3.2 Summary of the key threats to the development of Inari region/hub until 2035

According to the survey, the most significant threats to the Inari region were seen to be problems and disputes related to natural resources and land use among different industries and groups of people. These issues were perceived to pose threats not only to the local

environment and livelihoods but also to the overall development of life in the area. Additionally, tourism and its excessive growth, leading to a decline in local quality of life, were identified as a threat. On the other hand, future threats were also seen in the deterioration of public finances, housing shortages, and consequently, a shortage of workforce.

Natural resource policy, land use issues, and disputes related to livelihoods

Environmental degradation was seen as a threat through unsustainable land grabs and natural resource policies, such as mining, wind power, etc., but also through mass tourism. The unjust management of natural resources was considered a threat. There was also a fear that policymakers' opinions might shift towards being positive about mining and wind power. In terms of natural resource and land use issues, a significant threat was perceived in their impact on the local environment and attractions, such as the disappearance of silence, wilderness, darkness, and village-like characteristics. Non-intervention in curbing biodiversity loss was also seen as a threat. Overall, overconsumption of the Earth was seen as a threat in Inari as well. On the other hand, some saw excessive protection and tightening environmental requirements from the EU as a threat to the development and living in the area.

Issues related to land use were seen as a threat in many ways. The impact of land use on the indigenous people and the deterioration of traditional livelihoods were perceived as threats. The infringement of Sámi rights in land-use matters was also seen as a threat, but on the other hand, the obstruction of land use and planning in Sámi areas was seen as a threat. Concerning land use and natural resource policy, a significant threat was perceived in conflicts between different groups and livelihoods. Conflicts were feared to also cause deterioration in cooperation and trust among various stakeholders, leading to increased tensions between Sámi people and Finns. Some respondents saw new settlements as a threat, while others were concerned that newcomers would be increasingly viewed with skepticism.

Tourism

Tourism, its excessive volume, and the transformation of Inari into a mass tourism destination were seen as threats to Inari's future in many ways. Tourism was perceived to pose a threat to both the local environment and way of life.

Too rapid development, increased attraction

The excessive increase in the attractiveness of Inari, known as a migration-gaining area, and the general idealization of economic growth and development were seen as a threat if local infrastructure and nature do not keep pace with the development.

Economic Crisis, Energy Availability, Deterioration of Public Finances, Lack of Investments, Housing Shortage, Population Decline, Workforce Shortage

Housing shortages were seen as a significant threat to the area, as potential workforce might not find housing, and the existing population may have to move away due to a lack of suitable housing. Population decline and workforce shortage or a shortage of skilled professionals were also seen as threats to Inari. The deterioration of public finances, lack of investments, and economic crises were also perceived as future threats to the area, especially if the housing situation is not addressed. Additionally, there was concern about the stagnation of tourism and other investments. Disputes over different land use forms were seen as contributing to the potential weakening of the area's development potential.

The increase in energy prices and the difficulty in obtaining energy wood were seen as a threat, potentially leading to unreasonable housing costs. On the other hand, producing energy in "wrong" areas was considered a threat.

Climate change

Climate change and the failure to address it were seen as a significant threat to the local environment and livelihoods.

Transportation

Problems caused by air traffic and growing transit traffic, the threat of the Arctic Railway.

Other:

Other threats mentioned in the survey included Russia's impact on the Finnish economy, the threat of war, risks posed by reindeer husbandry to the local environment and other livelihoods, and a new pandemic.

3.3. Key results of the survey's future statements

In the survey, respondents were asked to assess, on a scale of 1-5, the importance or significance they attributed to a specific factor or phenomenon in terms of the future of the Inari region.

Table 1. Most important/significant forces of change on a scale of 1-5:

Future Statement (phenomenon or issue in bold)	Average
In the Inari region, consensus on land use and the needs of various industries is achieved through negotiations	4,68
The condition of water bodies remains good despite increased tourism and other land use	4,68
The wilderness nature of Inari attracts an increasing number of tourists	4,58
Measures to mitigate climate change restrict international tourism in Inari	4,58
The condition of Lake Inari and its fish stock deteriorates	4,48

Harmonizing the needs of various industries in land use increases conflicts	4,42
Workforce shortage limits the growth of tourism	4,41
Decisions about land use can no longer be made at the local level (municipal level)	4,41
Tourist seasons level out, and tourism becomes a year-round source of income	4,38
The use of forest chips decreases in the Inari region due to EU guidance on forest use and difficulties in import	4,33
The problems of reconciling reindeer husbandry and other land use forms continue to grow	4,32
EU biodiversity goals and strict requirements for the protection of old forests will prevent forestry activities in Inari	4,30
Inari's dependency ratio worsens	4,25
Tourism in the Inari region turns into mass tourism , and the ecological and sociocultural carrying capacity of the area deteriorates	4,22
Reform of the Sámi Parliament Act is implemented	4,21
The attractiveness and the ability to retain residents of Inari improve, and the population increases further	4,21

Table 2: Least important/significant forces of change on a scale of 1-5.

Future Statement (phenomenon or issue in bold)	Average
Mining expands to Inari and significantly increases employment opportunities.	2,67
Changes in tourists' eating habits , such as veganism, have a negative impact on the demand for reindeer meat and reindeer products.	2,63
The planning of Arctic Railway project progresses, and the project will eventually be realized.	2,57
Advances in sensory-related technology increase virtual tourism. Aisteihin liittyvän teknologian kehittyminen lisää virtuaalimatkailua	2,50
Inari becomes an internationally attractive destination due to its proximity to the Russian border .	1,93

In addition, future statements about future changes in the Inari region until 2035 were presented. Respondents were asked to assess how likely they consider the statement to come true. There were a total of seven themes: society and economy, Sámi culture, reindeer husbandry, nature, energy, forestry, and tourism. The figures below show the probability estimates for the top five/most significant future statements.

Figure 4. Probability estimates by respondents for future statements related to society and the economy (five statements considered most important/significant).

Figure 5. Probability estimates by respondents for future statements related to Sámi culture (five statements considered most important/significant).'

Figure 6. Probability estimates by respondents for future statements related to reindeer husbandry (five statements considered most important/significant).

Figure 7. Probability estimates by respondents for future statements related to nature (five statements considered most important/significant).

Figure 8. Probability estimates by respondents for future statements related to energy (five statements considered most important/significant).

Figure 9. Probability estimates by respondents for future statements related to forestry (five statements considered most important/significant).

Figure 10. Probability estimates by respondents for future statements related to tourism (five statements considered most important/significant).

4. Workshop I results

In the first part of the Inari Futures Paths workshop, the aim was to outline various future scenarios for the Inari region. Based on statements and importance assessments, participants selected the most significant forces of change by theme. Subsequently, participants considered how these forces of change would develop by 2035, using three different future scenarios: opportunities, threats, and the most likely (BAU - Business As Usual). Initially, participants divided into three groups according to the future scenarios, after which each group was able to comment on or add to the directions of forces of change initiated by other groups for the year 2035 (using the Learning Cafe method). The tables below categorize, by theme, the most significant forces of change chosen by participants, along with a few issues that emerged during the workshops regarding how the selected forces of change may possibly impact Inari by 2035 (see Tables 1, 2 & 3).

Workshop 1 – Most significant forces of change

Table 3. Key forces of change and their impacts in the 'Opportunities' future scenario

Theme	Forces of Change	Explanation/impact
<i>Society and economy</i>	Attraction and population change	Remote work, labor shortage has been solved, more people are moving to the municipality, local services such as community facilities
<i>Reindeer herding and Sámi culture</i>	Change of reindeer herding culture	Value-added processing, traditional grazing cycles,

		leveraging tourism, increased awareness of Sámi culture.
Nature	Loss of nature	Addressing biodiversity loss, environmental education at all levels, research for preventing biodiversity loss, increased appreciation for nature.
Energy	Availability of fuels	Norwegian hydrogen trucks, environmentally friendly transportation, security of supply has been resolved, transition away from fossil-based energy.
Forestry	Climate change	Old-growth forests are protected, firewood and building materials sourced locally, traditional civic skills are honored.
Tourism	Rapid changes in tourism	Year-round tourism, tourism offerings based on local conditions, cool summers attract more tourists, customers and operators are selected based on sustainability."

Table 4. Key forces of change and their impacts in the 'Threats' future scenario

Theme	Force of change	Explanation/impac
Society and economy	Decision-making power of the EU and UN	Decisions to restrict various actions, inadequate protection to prevent climate change, the voice of locals not heard, polarization

Reindeer herding and Sámi culture	The position of Sámi culture and the impacts of climate change.	Weakening of languages and culture, reindeer husbandry unable to adapt to prevailing conditions, appropriation of Sámi culture becomes more common, deepening of conflicts.
Nature	Diverse nature use and preservation of natural features.	New harmful species, overhunting, lack of snow, extreme weather events, collapse of biodiversity.
Energy	Energy self-sufficiency	Fluctuation in energy prices, getting stuck in the use of fossil energy forms, increased costs of housing and transportation.
Forestry	Transformation in forestry	Shutdown of forestry, uncontrolled use of forests, prohibition of wood energy use, extensive forest fires, decline in the value of forested land.

Table 5. "Most likely" (BAU – business as usual) future scenario's driving forces and their effects.

Theme	Forces of change	Explanation/impacts
Society and economy	Regional and educational policy	Centralization of education, shortage of Sámi-language education, a decrease in general education subjects, increased distance learning, increased immigration to address labor shortages

Reindeer herding and Sámi culture	Sustainable grazing and reconciliation (Sámi act)	Transition from meat production to supplementary livelihoods, an increase in winter feeding, room for improvement in cooperation between the Sámi Parliament and the municipality, conflicts between reindeer husbandry and other land-use forms continue
Nature	Climate change	Increased pests and diseases, deteriorating ice conditions, summer tourism is impacting the environment, and salmon populations have suffered
Energy	Rising of prices	Increased heat storage, small-scale energy production, solar and wind power, as well as alternative production methods, have increased.
Forestry	Other values	Industrial forest management has been phased out, multi-use of forests has increased, and the number of nature conservation areas has grown.
Tourism	Efforts towards sustainable tourism	In some parts of Inari, tourism is excessive; tourism has become a burden in some places. Tourism has generally increased and is more sustainable than before.

5. Workshop II results

Based on the discussions from workshop II, the scenarios were named as follows:

- Scenario 1 (Emphasizing opportunities): 'Puhtaan luonnon ja elinkeinojen sopusointu' (Harmony of Clean Nature and Livelihoods)
- Scenario 2 (Emphasizing threats): 'Riiston ja massojen polkema maa' (Land trampled by exploitation and masses)
- Scenario 3 (Most likely future development): 'Keskkitien keino - vakautta paikallisilla vahvuuksilla' (Middle path- Stability with Local Strengths)

5.1 Scenario descriptions

Scenario 1: 'Harmony of Clean Nature and Livelihoods'

In the year 2035, Inari has attracted an increasing number of people, thanks to factors such as growing tourism, Arctic business activities, and traditional attractions like pristine nature and silence. Housing shortages and, consequently, labor shortages have been resolved, and immigration has brought additional workforce to the tourism industry. Tourism has become year-round, with sustainable nature tourism and luxury travel experiencing growth in the region. Education in deep ecological knowledge has been increased.

Due to climate change, the conditions in Europe are unsustainable during summers, making Lapland's cool summers an attractive destination. The safety and nature of Lapland also appeal to people. The tourism offerings are locally driven with local conditions. Decision-making for the municipality starts at the local level. Dialogue between various stakeholders functions well, and conflicts between industries have been reconciled.

Inari's position as a center for Sámi culture has strengthened, and Sámi culture thrives; consensus on Sámi parliamentary law has been reached. The value of traditional knowledge has risen, and in reindeer herding, pasture harmony has been achieved, and the traditional rotation of reindeer pastures has been restored. Reindeer herding and tourism mutually benefit each other.

Efforts to address environmental degradation have been made, and conservation measures have increased in Inari, including the protection of old-growth forests. Inarijärvi (Lake Inari) has been designated as a national park. Forestry is practiced in Inari to meet the local demand for firewood and building materials. Environmental education has been increased for both children and adults.

In terms of energy solutions, new fuels and vehicles have been introduced in Inari, and the road network is in excellent condition. Electric planes are used for longer flights. Energy self-sufficiency has increased with the widespread adoption of small-scale solutions, including the use of solar power with battery storage. Ground-source heat pumps are increasingly utilized, and reliance on fossil-based energy has been completely abandoned.

The society and economy

- The economic development of the region is strong and based on sustainability and unique conditions.
- Conflicts between industries have been reconciled, and local solutions are found through community discussions.
- Labor shortages and housing issues have been resolved, and remote work has increased.

- Arctic research and testing activities have strengthened, and NATO has brought additional job opportunities.
- The natural product industry is recovering, and natural products are utilized for various purposes, including medicinal uses.

Sámi culture

- Inari's position as a center for Sámi culture is strengthening, and Sámi culture is flourishing.
- Agreement has been reached on Sámi parliamentary law.

Reindeer herding

- The image of reindeer meat is strengthened, and it is innovatively processed, leading to an increase in the price per kilogram.
- The traditional rotation of reindeer pastures has been restored.
- Reindeer provide a more diverse benefit to tourism.

Nature

- Measures have been taken to address biodiversity loss, and conservation efforts have been increased.
- Lake Inari has become a national park, and the Paatsjoki triangle has been reclaimed for Finland.

Energy

- New fuels have been adopted, and the region utilizes hydrogen vehicles and drones.
- Energy self-sufficiency has increased.
- Small-scale energy production solutions have become more common, and the first biogas plant has been established.
- Fossil-based energy has been completely abandoned.
- Sustainable and long-term energy solutions have been implemented to ensure reasonable living costs.

Forestry

- Inari's old-growth forests are protected.
- Local demand for firewood and building materials is met.

Tourism

- Tourism offerings have increased, especially in year-round tourism, with a focus on specialization.
- Sustainable nature tourism and luxury travel have grown, ensuring that tourism does not disturb or harm the environment. The development of virtual tourism also contributes to environmental conservation.
- Tourists contribute to a fund through an overnight stay fee, supporting the development of services.
- A new travel carbon offset is introduced to fund the protection of old-growth forests.
- Services and products are locally sourced and adhere to local conditions.

Scenario 2: Land trampled by exploitation and masses'

In the year 2035, the consequences of climate change in the Inari region are real, impacting almost every aspect of life. Due to international agreements, significant measures have been taken in the area, affecting the availability of energy and leading to both job and housing shortages. Decision-making now occurs at the EU level, stripping locals of their influence, and conflicts between different industries and demographic groups have deepened. As a

result of biodiversity loss, new harmful species have displaced local fauna, and reindeer husbandry has struggled to adapt to the prevailing conditions, causing massive die-offs and the spread of diseases. Changes in nature have directly affected Saami culture, intensifying conflicts related to the Saami people and significantly weakening the status of the Saami languages and culture.

Russia, manipulating the water level of the Paatsjoki River, tests the resilience of the region, affecting its shores and fisheries extensively. The growth of tourism has caused significant harm to the environment, diminishing previously important attractions of the area. Additionally, Inari's waste management has failed to keep pace with the region's growth, contributing to environmental damage. Tourism revenues are flowing out of the region, and foreign investments are shaping the area's development.

Forestry has faced a massive upheaval, nearly collapsing entirely. Wood energy usage is prohibited, and the value of forestry land has plummeted. The remaining forest is being exploited uncontrollably, exacerbated by extensive forest fires due to climate change.

Society and economy

- Worsening labor shortages
- Polarization and conflicts emerge between the region's industries and people
- Increasing refugee flows from Russia create uncertainty
- Deteriorating dependency ratio (population dependency ratio has been rising)
- Local voices go unheard in decision-making

Sámi culture

- Language and culture decline, deepening conflicts
- Financial support dwindles
- Cultural appropriation

Reindeer herding

- Inability to adapt to prevailing conditions
- Overgrazing causes environmental damage
- Diseases become more prevalent
- Traditional reindeer livelihood dwindles

Nature

- Increase in extreme weather events
- Mining industry enters Inari, causing damage to the Lake Inari watershed
- Nuclear pollution and accidents in Kuolassa harm nature (e.g., lichens in the soil)
- Collapse of biodiversity leads to growing environmental problems
- Emergence of new harmful species
- Lake Inari warming to unsustainable levels, affecting fisheries

Energy

- Persistent problems in energy availability
- Fluctuating energy prices, making it unaffordable for some

Forestry

- Complete shutdown of forestry
- Ban on wood energy usage
- Extensive forest fires cause destruction
- Uncontrolled use of remaining forests increases

Tourism

- Lack of responsibility in tourism development
- Impact of pandemics, air travel, wars, and global crises on tourist flows
- Decline of the tourism sector
- Social intolerance takes hold
- Uncontrolled expansion of tourism leads to unforeseen problems
- Unexpected water pollution occurs in water transport of chemicals after the realization of the Arctic Railway
- Establishment of a NATO nuclear base in Inari results in a collapse of the municipality's tourism and overall image
- Development of Kirkkoniemi Harbor makes Inari a transit location

Scenario 3: 'Middle path – stability with local strenghtes'

In the year 2035, the development of the Inari region has required adaptation due to the challenges posed by climate change. Consumer values and attitudes emphasize environmental responsibility, positively affecting the state of nature. However, despite this, alien and invasive species have increased. Recognized health and well-being benefits from nature contribute to the growth of nature tourism and the demand for natural products. Inari's pristine wilderness continues to attract an increasing number of tourists, ensuring state funding for transportation infrastructure. Tourism seasons have stabilized, providing year-round income, although in some parts of Inari, tourism has become burdensome.

Additional housing has been constructed in the area, but it remains challenging for all newcomers to Inari to find residential solutions. Nevertheless, the population has steadily increased. Increased immigration has addressed the need for labor, and the local, international, and multicultural community in Inari serves as a resource for well-being and vitality.

Climate change has affected reindeer husbandry, and the challenges of coordinating land use persist. Collaboration between the Saami Parliament and the municipality still has room for improvement. However, the position of Saami languages and Saami culture has strengthened. Reindeer numbers have remained stable, leading to increased winter feeding.

The green transition and the electricity crisis have intensified pressure for wind power development. Small-scale energy production and alternative production methods have increased. Explorations into small-scale mining are underway. The significance of forestry has diminished due to reduced demand for wood. Industrial forest management has been phased out, and the use of forests now involves burning small wood. Private conservation areas and the number of nature reserves have grown.

Society and economy

- Education is increasingly focused on individual needs.
- Elderly marginalization is on the rise.
- Local appeal and attractiveness improve, leading to a growth in population.
- Conflicts over land use persist, including a general questioning of everyman's rights.

- State funding for infrastructure, including roads, has decreased, and cultural support has also diminished.
- The region continues to internationalize.
- The population is growing.

Sámi culture

- Interest in Sámi culture and the Arctic continues to grow.
- There is a shortage of Sámi-language education.
- Collaboration between the Sámi Parliament and the municipality still needs improvement.
- Changes in nature directly affect Sámi culture.

Reindeer herding

- Grazing areas remain fragmented.
- There is a shift in meat production towards alternative livelihoods, such as tourism.
- The use of by-products has increased.
- The presence of "räkkä" (insects, typically mosquitoes) has increased, directly affecting reindeer husbandry and tourism.

Nature

- Local species have suffered, and some have partially disappeared.
- Inari Lake fishing is now more focused on pike.
- Due to the warming of the Arctic Ocean, salmon stocks have suffered.
- Pests and diseases have increased.
- Increased precipitation has worsened spring floods.

Energy

- Collaborative energy consumption practices have increased.
- Regional electricity prices have been implemented.
- Small-scale energy production methods have increased, including small wind turbines, for example, at summer cottages.
- Energy is preserved using new preservation methods, constantly under development.
- The first biogas plant is established.

Forestry

- Multiple-use of forests has increased, including the establishment and maintenance of carbon sink forests through compensation.
- Private conservation areas are being established.
- Wood processing is marginal.
- Industrial forestry has been phased out.
- Dominance of reindeer husbandry prevents the practice of forestry. **Tourism**
- The pristine nature of Inari attracts an increasing number of tourists.
- Winter tourism has suffered due to a shortened season.
- Summer tourism has increased, with activities like birdwatching and nature observation filling in tourism's "dead periods."
- Labor shortages limit the growth of tourism.
- Tourism has become a burden in some areas.

5.2 Future table

	Scenario 1: 'Harmony of Clean Nature and Livelihoods'	Scenario 2: Land trampled by exploitation and masses'	Scenario 3: 'Middle path- Stability with Local Strengths'
Society and economy	The economy is thriving, with new taxpayers, innovations, and entrepreneurship in the area. Private investments are flourishing. Environmental education and in-depth knowledge of nature are being provided. Conflicts of interest in industries have been resolved.	The economy has suffered from challenging times, and locals no longer have influence or resources to invest in the well-being of the area. Conflicts of interest in industries have deepened.	In the national economy, cost-cutting measures are in place, with minimal investments in infrastructure such as road networks. Conflicts of interest in industries persist.
Sámi culture	Inari's position as a Sámi cultural center has strengthened, and Sámi culture is flourishing. Agreement on the Sámi Parliament Act has been reached, and educational opportunities have increased.	Conflict related to the Saami people has deepened, and the status of the Saami languages and Saami culture has significantly weakened.	Although there is still room for improvement in collaboration, the position of Saami culture and languages has strengthened.
Reindeer herding	The image of reindeer meat is positive, and it is processed innovatively. New food sources, such as rapidly growing algae, have been produced. Traditional methods are also embraced, and the traditional rotation of reindeer pastures has been restored.	Reindeer herding has struggled to adapt to changing conditions, leading to the spread of diseases and significant mass deaths among reindeer.	The reindeer population has remained stable, resulting in increased winter feeding.
Nature	Biodiversity loss has been addressed, and conservation efforts have been increased. Preserved old-growth forests serve as attractions for tourism. Deciduous forests are beginning to grow in the area. Ecosystem services are both functional and profitable. The loss and endangerment of species have been minimized through conservation efforts. The water, air, and soil are clean. However, the changing habitats, influenced by factors such as the spread of Arctic char and raccoon dogs, are making it challenging for local species, including mountain plants, to survive.	As a consequence of biodiversity loss, new harmful species have displaced local fauna, and growing conditions have altered due to climate change. Entire aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems are in crisis and have reduced productivity. The uncontrolled shift in species composition poses a significant challenge.	Climate change has an impact, and, for example, alien and invasive species have increased.
Energy	In energy solutions, new fuels and vehicles, such as hydrogen vehicles, have been introduced. Energy self-sufficiency has increased with the prevalence of small-scale production solutions (small wind, solar). Measures related to the green transition have proven effective.	The adequacy of energy remains constantly uncertain, and the price of energy fluctuates dramatically.	Small-scale energy production and alternative production methods have increased. There is pressure to adopt wind power.
Forestry	Forestry is based on local needs, including the demand for firewood and construction materials. Preserved old-growth forests serve as assets for tourism.	Forestry is undergoing a massive transformation, and it has been almost completely phased out.	The significance of forestry to the region has diminished, but the use of small wood for energy remains strong.

Tourism	It is growing significantly while respecting nature and building additional value-added services. For example, diverse benefits have been derived from reindeer in tourism. Sustainable nature tourism and luxury tourism have increased. Services and products are locally sourced and based on local conditions.	Tourism experiences a downturn due to various disruptions (environmental pollution, deterioration of the natural carrying capacity, pandemics) and decreases significantly.	Strengthens steadily. Tourism seasons have stabilized, and tourism generates year-round income.
	Scenario 1: 'Harmony of Clean Nature and Livelihoods'	Scenario 2: Land trampled by exploitation and masses'	Scenario 3: 'Middle path- Stability with Local Strengths'
Attraction of the Area:	The attractiveness of the area strengthens even further, drawing both workforce and new residents.	The attractiveness of the area decreases.	The pull and holding power of the area remains strong.
National and EU Guidance vs. Local Decision-Making Authority:	Takes into account local needs and allows flexibility in the implementation of policy actions.	EU guidance is strong and shifts decision-making away from the local and regional levels.	EU guidance and national direction engage in continuous dialogue, where local perspectives are also considered.
Population Structure	In Lapland, educated workforce is moving in, and multiculturalism is increasing. The population structure remains the same in terms of age, or even becomes younger.	The proportion of elderly in the population is increasing, and the proportion of young people is decreasing, leading to an intensified dependency ratio and acute labor shortages.	Stable growth in tourism, supported by other industries, creates jobs, and the population continues on a growth trajectory, slowing down the aging of the population structure.
Economic Structure (Raw Material and Processing Chains)	Harmonious agreements on economic needs are achieved, and new synergies are discovered at the interfaces of industries. Production chains are built locally and based on local conditions. Gathering and reindeer products are in demand, and prices are rising.	Foreign-owned mass tourism has exploited natural capital, pushing local raw material and processing activities to a marginal position. Collecting natural products and reindeer herding are unprofitable.	There is still work to be done in coordinating land use, although there is shared communication and understanding of the needs of industries.
Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation	Conditions in Southern Europe are unsustainable during the summers, and Lapland's cool summers attract people.	The consequences of climate change are real and have affected almost everyone's lives.	Mitigation and adaptation needs are recognized, and actions are taken in response to the challenges posed by climate change.

<p>Housing and</p>	<p>In the area, both hydrogen vehicles and drones are used for transportation. Electric planes are flown for longer distances. Small-scale housing and modular construction are prevalent.</p>	<p>The conflicts between different industries in the area has led to a deterioration in road conditions, as development is not seen as a shared concern. At the same time, outmigration from the area has resulted in a decline in the housing stock's</p>	<p>Despite the construction of additional housing transportation: challenging for everyone moving to Inari to find accommodation, and investments in road condition. infrastructure are</p>
---------------------------	--	--	--

5.3 General Impacts of the Scenarios

Workshop II first addressed the general impacts of the scenarios on the Inari region. The aim was to consider scenario-specific positive and negative effects for each scenario.

Table 6. Scenario-specific positive and negative effects.

Harmony of pure nature and livelihoods	
Positive	Negative
Clean nature and the rise of nature values	Excessive and uncontrolled growth in tourism
Services	Excessive and uncontrolled growth in tourism
Well-being and standard of living improve	Immigration and challenges brought by multiculturalism
Conflicts in industries are resolved, and understanding improves	Conflicts between stakeholders
Improvement in the Sámi position, acceptance of cultural diversity	
Employment grows	
The land trampled by exploitation and masses	
Positive	Negative
Innovation and creativity increase, new forms of economic culture	Services and infrastructure are deteriorating
Decline in forestry --> nature and reindeer herding benefit	Tourism is maximal
Issues with energy availability increase self-sufficiency	Sámi culture withers
More peace and space for the village and locals, fostering local culture	Decline in tourism
	Increased distress, mental health problems
	Competition between groups intensifies
	Unemployment rises
	Quality of life declines, living conditions worsen
Middle path - stability with local strenghts	
Positive	Negative
Vitality increases, attractiveness and pulling power remain good/grow	Finding consensus is challenging, land use conflicts persist
Year-round income from tourism	Things are not in our hands, decisions come from elsewhere
Nature and waterways remain in good condition, natural value rises	Nature is still being depleted and littered
New innovations, sustainable development inventions	Tourism is a burden on nature and Saami culture
Increased multifunctional use of forests, appreciation for natural products ris	Population increases, but homelessness grows
	State funding decreases, impacting infrastructure, for example, road

Scenario 1: Harmony of clean nature and livelihoods

In the Opportunity scenario, the most significant positive impacts were related to nature, services, and well-being, conflict resolution, the position of Saami culture, and employment. On the other hand, excessive nature conservation was seen as a negative impact, along with excessive and uncontrolled growth in tourism and challenges brought by immigration. Conflict resolution among different stakeholders was seen as a positive aspect in the Opportunity scenario, but there was not complete belief in their resolution, as the continuation of conflicts among stakeholders was also seen as a negative aspect in this scenario.

Scenario 2: Land trampled by exploitation and masses

In the Threat scenario, the most negative impacts were seen in the deterioration of services and infrastructure, the decline of Saami and local culture, and issues related to tourism. Maximal tourism was considered a threat to nature and local culture, but there was also a threat perceived in the decline of tourism and its negative effects on the municipality, such as worsening livelihoods and dependency ratios. It was also felt that the Threat scenario would increase mental health problems, inter-group competition, and unemployment, leading to a decline in quality of life and living conditions. The Threat scenario was seen to have positive impacts as well, such as an increase in innovativeness and creativity among residents, which could lead to new livelihood cultures. Additionally, the decline in forestry was seen to have positive effects on nature and reindeer herding, and problems related to energy availability were seen to increase energy self-sufficiency and local production. The Threat scenario was also seen to increase peace for the village and locals.

Scenario 3: Middle path – Stability with local strenghts

In the Most Likely scenario, the most positive impacts were seen in the municipality's vitality, stability, and attractiveness, the rise in the value of nature, the non-contamination of nature and water bodies, new innovations such as inventions related to sustainable development, and the increase in the multifunctional use of forests and collection of natural products. Additionally, it was seen as a positive aspect that tourism would generate year-round income due to increased summer tourism. Negative impacts included the continuing difficulty in finding reconciliation among different stakeholders and land-use practices, ongoing deterioration and pollution of nature, particularly due to tourism, which also strained Saami culture. The increase in population was seen to bring problems, including homelessness. In addition, a negative aspect of the Most Likely scenario was the perception that decisions are made elsewhere, and matters are not in local control.

6. Examination of scenario impacts in relation to future preparedness

In Workshop II, discussions were held on more detailed impacts, including various industries, Sámi culture, raw materials and processing chains, company profitability, entrepreneurship, and corporate structure, collaboration models, the adoption of new technologies, skill requirements, and the development of new economic models. Next, we will highlight more specific effects (both negative and positive) and preparedness measures for the future scenario-specifically in these areas.

6.1 Impacts and preparedness measures of the scenario "Harmony of clean nature and livelihoods" in different divisions in the Inari region

How does the scenario impact?

What are the key measures in this scenario? / What measures are taken to prepare for the realization of this scenario?

On different industries:

- + Sustainable nature tourism increases, and tourism flourishes
- + Continuity of reindeer herding is secured and thriving.
- + The price of natural products will rise.
- + Inter-industry agreement is achieved. + More collection and processing of natural products.

Measures:

- Creation of a cooperative model and forum to resolve conflicts, including "local stories." - Measures for the restoration of nature.
- Planning assistance in financing growth.
- Up-to-date training materials for entrepreneurs (responsibility and sustainability).
- Coordination of tourism with consideration for reindeer herding (emphasis on incorporating the views of local

- Labor shortage limits tourism.
- The impact of excessive growth in tourism on sustainability
- A growing gap between tourists and locals due to luxury tourism.

people, determining the type of tourism that would be best for the vitality of the village).

- Legislation designating Lake Inari as a national park.
- Maintenance of wilderness and regulation of tourism.
- Diversification of the economic structure.
- Development and branding of summer tourist destinations.
- Fishing tourism: branding pike for tourists.
- Involvement of students in tourism product development.
- Training and management of housing shortage, branding of the chef profession, etc., marketing of education.
- Focus on sustainability and cultural sensitivity.
-

On Sámi culture

- + Inari's position as a Sámi cultural center strengthens, and simultaneously Sámi culture strengthens.
- + Increase in proficiency in Saami languages.

Measures

- Consideration of diversity in Saami culture.
- Improvement of linguistic services for Northern, Inari, and Skolt Saami.
- Approval of a new Saami Parliament Act by the Finnish Parliament.
- Increase in education in Saami languages.

On raw materials and processing chains:

- + Individual reindeer herder's further processing improves.
- + Local processing of fish and berries. + New entrepreneurship in energy and the prevalence of small-scale production solutions. + Improved collaboration in the natural products industry.
- + Further processing of reindeer meat.
- + Further processing of berries, mushrooms, herbs, etc.
- The forest industry does not source raw materials from the Inari region.

Measures:

- Allotment of logging areas from state forests to local residents, organization of logging areas for local use and needs.
- Investments in small-scale production solutions.
- Supplementing wood needs from elsewhere.
- Improvement of financing opportunities for innovations.
- Strengthening cooperative activities.
- Support for reindeer meat processing facilities and shared processing facilities for natural berries and herbs.

On business profitability

- + Resolution of economic conflicts.
- + Year-round tourism.
- + New entrepreneurship.
- Excessive tourism causes environmental impacts, deteriorating the operating conditions for businesses.

Measures:

- Availability of land for businesses through planning and citizen participation.
- Negotiations recognizing Saami rights in accordance with the Akwe kon process.
- Strengthening marketing in Europe and globally.
- Affordable addition of craft spaces for entrepreneurs.
- Municipal planning to allocate land for businesses

On entrepreneurship and business structure (innovation):

- + Local origin
- + Collaborative entrepreneurship at the interfaces of businesses.
- + Diverse service chains.
- + Household energy self-sufficiency. + Tourism focuses on undisturbed product development.
- + Tourist spending directed towards service maintenance.
- + Introduction of new workforce. - Conflicts between entrepreneurs.

Measures

- Municipal investments in image building.
- Economic development investments.
- Business counseling, financial counseling, creation of financial instruments for innovation.
- Guides in different languages for entrepreneurs, training days, and exhibitions.
- Influence on decision-making by authorities (EU, Lapland Regional Council, etc.), project funding.
- Carbon offsetting for travelers – funds for the protection of old-growth forests.
-

On collaborative models among regional actors +

- Resolution of economic conflicts.
- + Resolution of land use conflicts (No fragmentation in land use).
- + No uninhabited properties.
- + Acceptance that reaching consensus may not be possible

Measures:

- Akwe kon, FPIC, negotiations with various parties, participatory planning.
- Prevention of the decline of traditional skills and their transfer to the next generations.
- Transition to a sustainable economy.
- Increase in self-sufficiency and security of supply.
- Environmental education for everyone.
- Inclusion of regional development groups and village associations, combining forces.
- Locals defining the maintenance of tourism and routes.
- Informational video for tourists (e.g., on flights and in hotels, distributed to businesses) on how to behave locally.
- Prevention of elderly isolation (Recreational activities, training in caregiving, establishment of a nursing home in Inari village).

<p>On the Adoption of New Technologies, Digitalization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Small-scale production solutions in energy production. + Energy saving/regulation. + Increase in small-scale energy production. + Procurements, information. + Easier adoption of new technologies. + Job opportunities for young people. 	<p>Measures;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New innovations, improvement of telecommunications, attraction of ICT experts. - Municipal energy advisor (digital and energy advice). - Finland buys back the Paatsjoki River basin and gains energy. - Increase in self-sufficiency, circular economy. - Small-scale production, small-scale forestry (sustainable forestry, energy wood collection, brushwood clearing). - Natural product industry and versatile use of natural products, integration into education, local production for schools (luovakka.fi). - Incentives (tax benefits). - Targeted procurement based on information.
<p>On skill requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Need for experts in reindeer meat processing and sustainable tourism production. + New education in technology, agriculture. + New university of applied sciences (AMK) branch in Inari. + Environmental education. + Saami language teachers (also for early childhood education). + Finnish language education for non-native speakers. 	<p>Measures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training, recruitment, financing. - Introduction of new degree opportunities. - Expansion of education to higher levels in Inari, creating a new educational path. - Municipal funding for language studies. - For example, Sakk organizes additional language education. - Timing and scheduling of public investments.
<p>On New Economic Models (Challengers to Linear Economy, Sharing Economy, Circular Economy, etc.):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Development of processing facilities in slaughterhouses. + Localized solutions in energy production, for example, block-specific solutions. + Increase in conservation. 	<p>Measures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consultation with industries, financing, information. - Funding, innovations, education, communication. - Additional funding from the state/EU for increased conservation.

6.2 Impacts and preparedness measures of the scenario "The land trampled by exploitation and masses" in different divisions in the Inari region

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does the scenario impact? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the key measures in this scenario? / What measures are taken to prepare for the realization of this scenario?
--	---

<p>On different industries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investments decrease - Equipment and methods age - Insecurity increases - Local ownership in tourism decreases - The downsizing of forestry leads to poor condition of forest roads - Economic downturn- Talous sakkaa + New livelihoods emerge + Resilience increases (self-sufficiency) + The downsizing of forestry positively affects tourism 	<p>Measures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Focus on sectors currently in the margins - Local business support, encouraging atmosphere, and education are needed to keep tourism locally owned - Investment in nature tourism - Activation of the entities and individuals affected by the scenario
<p>On Sámi culture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resources decrease - Culture further fractures, increasing uncertainty about who is and who isn't Saami and to what extent - The disappearance of Saami culture 	<p>Measures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adoption of a new Saami Parliament Act - Strengthening language education - Maintaining cultural connections across generations - Creating a space or means for those culturally in-between to also take joy in their own culture
<p>On raw materials and processing chains</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Various forms of forest use flourish if forestry is completely phased out - Wood shortage affects self-sufficiency - Reindeer deaths and diseases - Decline in the processing of raw materials - Bulk production, only raw materials for processing elsewhere - Stagnation, small-scale operations - Technological development (e.g., Motot) has eliminated the need for lumberjack work 	<p>Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reindeer herding and feeding - Construction of processing facilities (reasonably priced) - Encouraging forest management - Attracting investments - Increasing processing value
<p>On the profitability of businesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attractiveness diminishes - Large chains dominate, putting small businesses in a tight spot - Employment opportunities from businesses disappear 	<p>Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highlighting new innovations - Exploring financing alternatives - Promoting business collaboration and interconnected services
<p>On entrepreneurship and business structure (renewal)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decline in tourism and other livelihoods - Without investment, there is no confidence in the future + Facilitating business recycling 	<p>Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training/recruitment of new entrepreneurs - Activities for anticipating the future -

<p>On collaboration models among regional stakeholders - Reindeer deaths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Former collaboration models deteriorate + Collaboration strengthens, can be sector-specific, certain industries thrive 	<p>Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tightening collaboration among reindeer herders - Government supports and compensation - Developing new collaboration models -
<p>On the adoption of new technologies, digitalization:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reindeer deaths + New energy production models (solar, etc.) 	<p>Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing a meter for snow thickness and load-bearing capacity
<p>On competency needs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of language skills - Unawareness of local practices 	<p>Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Language courses (Finnish language) - Etiquette training
<p>On new economic models (challengers to linear economy, sharing economy, circular economy, etc.):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase in vacant houses 	<p>Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Renting out vacant houses

6.3 Impacts and preparedness measures of the scenario "Middle path – stability with local strenghts" in different divisions in the Inari region

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does the scenario impact? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the key measures in this scenario? / What measures are taken to prepare for the realization of this scenario?
--	---

On different industries

- + Sustainable nature tourism has increased
- + Reindeer husbandry continues
- + Collaboration is increasing
- + Stable growth
- + Increased winter feeding in enclosed yards can facilitate reindeer husbandry (e.g., regarding predators)
- + Tourism is attracting more
- Feeding reindeer with imported fodder
- Reindeer husbandry remains uncertain
- Tourism is a burden in some places

Measures

- Strengthening the optimism about the future among youth
- Urban planning
- Educational material for entrepreneurs (responsibility & sustainability)
- Harmonizing reindeer husbandry and tourism
- The municipality should be a good engine for industries
- Developing year-round tourism
- Developing fishing tourism
- Tourism marketing should be more clearly targeted to selected target groups

On Sámi culture

- + Sámi Parliament as an influencer
- + Inari's position as a Sámi cultural center strengthens, and the culture is vibrant
- + Language proficiency is a key to employment
- Neglect of the cultural heritage of fishing Sámi in Inari
- Continued uncertainty in cultural development

Toimenpiteet

- Service provision, funding, communication
- Improvement of linguistic services, consideration of Sámi diversity
- The key forum for this is the Sámi Parliament
- Maintenance of the vitality of Sámi culture (diversity and its preservation)
- Not overly relying on reindeer herding

On raw materials and processing chains

- + Increase in side industries
- + Meat prices are rising, positive for entrepreneurs, but not effective as an elite product
- Processing of wood is labor-intensive and unprofitable
- Insufficient material for the Kemi factory

Measures

- Commercialization of operations, innovation
- Sourcing wood from elsewhere
- Financing, innovation
-

On profitability of businesses

- + Increased summer tourism
- + Tourism brings additional income to reindeer husbandry
- Excessive tourism (nature suffering)

Measures

- Urban planning
- Marketing advice
- Business advice
-

On entrepreneurship, business structure (renewal)

- + New entrepreneurship through NATO – catering, maintenance, and other subcontracting
- + NATO brings new dynamics to the region
- + Construction of infrastructure; the Border Guard also needs to invest
- + Strengthening local identity

Measures:

- Business advice
- Strengthening collaboration with Norway
-

<p>On collaboration models for local actors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of decision-makers in the municipality - Collaboration between Sámi and other actors 	<p>Measures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ongoing dialogue, especially with local Sámi (not necessarily through the Sámi Parliament; multiculturalism forum) - Sámi culture needs to return more to its roots and diversify from its current mono/reindeer culture - Not too strong a focus solely on reindeer herding - If a separate body or council is needed for coordination, let it be established in a way that respects democracy and individual rights in its operations - Prefer a focus on community and cooperation within the community
<p>On adoption of new technologies, digitization</p> <p>+ Small-scale production in energy generation - Fully mechanized, business-oriented, artificially fed and environmentally burdening "efficiency reindeer herding," and a Sámi culture solely dependent on it, does not represent the future of the Inari region</p>	<p>Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New innovations - Improving telecommunications and increasing ICT skills - Exclusively using renewable energies; wind, solar, carefully considered water, and bioenergy utilization
<p>On skills development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Increase in sustainable tourism production - Endangerment of Sámi languages 	<p>Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training, recruitment, financing - Teacher training - Production beneficial to peoples and societies should involve research and development, aiming for sustainable production and well-being. - Language work, where the Sámi Parliament plays a significant role
<p>On new economic models (challengers to the linear economy, sharing economy, circular economy, etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Development of slaughterhouse processing facilities + Forms of small-scale energy production 	<p>Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consultation with industries, financing, information - Financing, innovation, training, communication - Forest areas must now be carefully managed. In the coming decades, the care of seedlings and continuous growth forestry are likely to be cornerstones of sustainable and selfsufficient forestry in the Inari region.

7.Summary

7.1 Conclusion

The value of scenarios lies in illuminating possible future developments to support current decision-making related to the future. A crucial premise in foresight is that the future cannot be predicted. Therefore, the future is open and uncertain, but efforts are consciously made to work towards potential future developments—whether desirable, probable, or containing threats—when producing and examining them. In the process of future work, the discussion and thought process itself are at least as important as the produced scenarios and whether they come to fruition or not.

The ongoing future process in Inari demonstrates a strong belief in the strengths of Inari, its nature, Sámi, and other local cultures, and the region's industries up to the year 2035. Tourism is considered the most significant industry for Inari's future, but it must be implemented in a way that does not jeopardize the region's nature or Sámi culture. Other possibilities can only materialize if threats are effectively addressed. Achieving consensus, maintaining the health of water bodies, and preserving the attraction of wilderness were identified as crucial aspects of change. Conflicting views on land use are feared to increase conflicts in the future, a challenge that should be addressed with solutions by various stakeholders now. However, every cloud is seen with a silver lining: in times of industry challenges, it is believed that it forces new innovations and increases resilience or adaptability.

7.2 Examination of the method

In this study mapping the future alternatives for the region, two commonly used methods in futures studies were employed. The underlying idea was that future questions should be addressed through an iterative process, meaning that the produced future visions would not be based solely on data collected at one moment but that the outputs could be regularly discussed throughout the future process. For this premise, a five-phase foresight process was designed (see Figure 1 on page 3), following the principles of the Delphi method. Anonymity of responses (respondents not identified during the survey phase), multiple rounds (in this case, a survey round and two workshops), and controlled feedback and commenting options (conducted through discussions in two workshops, with summaries worked on in between based on current results, the survey, and Workshop I) are crucial aspects of the method.

Comments were received during the March-April survey period about the difficulty of responding, particularly related to the formulation of questions (especially when a future statement involved more than one driving force or phenomenon, and a clear cause-and-effect relationship was not identifiable). Respondents also wished for more open explanation sections for their future visions.

The survey intentionally included both negative and positive future changes, but evaluating their importance/significance was perceived as challenging. The instructions aimed to clarify that responses were expected regarding how important or significant respondents considered

an individual change factor or phenomenon for the future of the Inari region. The importance or significance of the change direction itself was not requested to be assessed.

This difficulty could be better addressed in two workshops, where the emphasis could be placed on collectively discussing and interpreting the approach being examined at the time. In the first workshop, the focus was on selecting the most significant change forces in the Inari region, defined in the workshop as follows: Change Force = the driver of change, i.e., something that alters the current state (it could be a new technology, environmental change, etc.). The change forces were defined for their direction, after which the research group prepared scenario drafts for Workshop II.

Both participants from the survey phase and new participants attended the workshops. Especially as Workshop II approached, it was considered important to involve more diverse stakeholders (including youth, Sámi people, various industries, municipal decision-makers) for a comprehensive discussion on the future.

2.

Forestry scenarios in Norrbotten, Västerbotten and Lapland regions - based on an expert survey and workshop results

ArcticHubs project (<https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs>)

21.12.2023

Pasi Rikkonen, Taru Rikkonen, Esa Inkilä, Janne Miettinen, Gun Lidestav, Seija Tuulentie and Pasi Rautio

Table of contents:

1. Background	2
1.1 Framing of the Forestry scenario process	2
2. Material for the scenario construction	3
2.1 Forestry workshop material from Kukkolaforseen workshop	3
2.2 Utilization of the forestry expert survey material	4
3. Futures table representing the future developments presented in workshop discussions	6
4. Scenario narratives	12
5. Conclusions	16

1. Background

The ArcticHubs project, coordinated by the Natural Resources Institute of Finland and funded by the EU (<https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs/>), aims to develop sustainable solutions for harmonizing competing industries and land use practices in Arctic central locations, known as 'hubs,' and their surrounding environments. This project also takes into account the cultural aspects of indigenous populations, such as the Sámi in Fennoscandia and the Inuit in Greenland. The project focuses on key economic activities in the Arctic region, including mining, aquaculture, tourism, and forestry. These industries hold significant societal and economic value in the region, and the project also analyzes how they impact ecosystem services and the well-being of local communities. The ArcticHubs project involves participatory foresight work for a total of seven specified hubs to assess future opportunities, threats, and strategies for preparing for the future. In this report we focus especially on forestry in a situation where forest industry investments are increasing (in particular the bioproduct mill in Kemi), and therefore are becoming a strong socio-economic driver in the regions.

1.1 Framing of the Forestry scenario process

This is a draft version of imagining alternative forestry scenarios in Norrbotten, Västerbotten and Lapland regions, especially in a situation where new extensive investments by forest industry are taking place e.g. in Kemi. The data gathering for scenario construction was conducted by two main sources: first, the expert survey conducted in summer 2023, and second, the Kukkolaforsen workshop day 29th of August 2023. The foresight process of the project consisted of three phases. First, we locally met and discussed with key stakeholders, to identify factors and drivers influencing the future of the regions. Based on these discussions we prepared a survey that included future statements relevant to the regions and asked about key threats and opportunities. Considering the ongoing expansion of wood processing industries, we also conducted forest resource assessment on both the Finnish and Swedish counties. In the second phase, the results of the survey and the forest resource assessments and survey were presented for review in a workshop. Together with the workshop participants the most significant drivers of change were prioritized, and their future directions were discussed and drafted. Using this as a foundation, in the third phase the research team has drafted scenario outlines, which are further refined based on the feedback received (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Scenario process consisted of three phases.

2. Material for the scenario construction

2.1. Forestry workshop material from Kukkolaforson workshop

In the forestry workshop the first group assignment was aiming on defining and selecting of the most significant drivers of change for the forestry in Norrbotten, Västerbotten and Lapland regions. The starting point for this was the summary report on the survey results that based on the proposed opportunities and threats, views on future statements, their importance and/or significance assessment, and participant's own future views. The question asked was: which driving forces, changes and/or trends do you consider most significant or important for the forestry in Norrbotten, Västerbotten and Lapland regions?

Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
Green transition	Legislation/Policy	Climate change
Geopolitics	Demands for sustainability	Energy
(over)Consumption	Effects of climate change	Politics
EU (policies and legislation)	Land use conflicts mediation	Tourism
Climate change	Transition to more circular biobased economy	Biodiversity
Biodiversity loss	Polarization	Social change
Land use issues		Technology / Knowledge
Green industry like forest industry		Products
		Hope

Table 1. Summary of the most significant driving forces identified and presented by the three groups in the workshop (The similar drivers are colour coded)

For the basis of the scenario construction one key issue is to have enough divergence between scenarios in order them to be beneficial for further analysis (e.g. conducting impact assessments of scenarios in regions). This kind of thinking can help in imagining the future developments. In the following the selected most significant drivers are interpreted as extreme outcomes.

Figure 2. Key drivers and their diverse outcomes

The key drivers selected in the workshop assignment were the base for the scenario contents. The above-mentioned drivers (Table 1, Figure 2) form the titles for futures table in where the future developments are then described scenario by scenario (see Table 2.).

2.2. Utilization of the forestry expert survey material

Furthermore, future statements in the survey phase connected to these key drivers were identified, and the following list includes the relevant statements that were considered when describing the possible future developments.

Statements for public steering and decision-making

- The EU's biodiversity and old-growth forest protection goals has significantly reduced the availability of raw wood material.
- External regulation and agreements at the national, EU and global level affect more on how forests can be utilized than local goals and conditions.
- Society increasingly secures the harmonious use of natural resources in all aspects of sustainability.

Statements for livelihoods

- The importance of forestry increases as the need for raw wood material increases.
- There will be enough skilled forestry workforce available in the future.
- The importance of forestry as a source of employment is growing in Lapland/Norrbotten/Västerbotten.

Statements for land use interests

- The municipalities will have less opportunities to decide on land use planning.
- The local economic benefit is emphasized in the use of natural resources.
- The ability to pay will determine which land use interests have priority.
- It is becoming more difficult to reconcile the demands of different livelihoods and stakeholders on natural resources.

Statements for climate change

- Forest management produces too much carbon dioxide emissions.
- Large part of drained bogs are being restored.

- Climate issues are increasingly important for decision-making.

Statements for biodiversity

- Biodiversity issues are increasingly important for decision-making.
- The EU's biodiversity and old-growth forest protection goals has significantly reduced the availability of raw wood material.
- To secure biodiversity, clear-cuttings are not done.
- Clear-cutting has depleted the diversity of forest species
- Maintaining biodiversity on forest lands is economically profitable. **Statements for green transition and technology advancement**
- Green transition is a threat to forestry in Lapland/Norrbotten/Västerbotten
- Wind power is expanding in Lapland/Norrbotten/ Västerbotten (consensus question).
- In forestry, there are increasing amounts of functional methods of co-planning on land use and negotiations.
- Precise forestry operations (Lean forestry) increases and saves both resources and nature and reduces land use conflicts.

Statements for social and cultural change

- The right of public access remains an essential part of people's use of nature.
- The monetary value of other forest products than timber is increasing.

The following chapter three presents the futures table in where five scenarios are presented.

3. Futures table representing the five alternative future scenarios presented in workshop discussions

	1. Forestry growth conditioned by green transition	2. Local drawbacks from external land use control	3. Empowered northern communities	4. Climate and nature first	5. Locally conflicting land use interests
Public steering and decision-making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -New public investment programmes are increasing the forest growth -Also climate growth increases growth -The EU's biodiversity and old-growth forest protection goals reduce the cutting possibilities, but the sum of growth is larger than these limitations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -External regulation at the EU and global level restrict how forests can be utilized locally -EU decides to treat timber as a non-green energy within EU and use of wood and forest industry residues as energy decreases -Overall, geopolitical sabre-rattling causes continuous instability, especially conflicts of interests between China, Russia and Western world 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Society increasingly secures the harmonious use of natural resources in all aspects of sustainability. - Better and justice processes of decisionmaking - The local economic benefit is emphasised in the use of natural resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU tightens climate and conservation goals and regulations -Nature, climate, carbon sequestration and sustainability have to be taken into account in every decision - More funds on environmentally friendly and sustainable practices -Locals and indigenous communities involved in decision-making, but at the same time some decisions are made at EU-level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The biodiversity and old-growth forest conservation goals of the EU leading to disputes -Goals implemented reduced the availability of raw timber in certain areas -External regulations and agreements at the national, EU, and global levels weighted more than local goals and conditions on how forests can be used

<p>Livelihoods</p>	<p>-More jobs are created to forest sector and wind energy production</p>	<p>- The importance of forestry is affected by increased</p>	<p>- North tempts more people - Sustainable tourism</p>	<p>- Increased benefits on sustainable tourism, and nature-based</p>	<p>-The increasing demand for raw</p>
	<p>-There is lack of skilled workforce available for forestry -Technological advances supplement human workers in some work tasks</p>	<p>conservation, restoration and mitigation measures - The acceptability of forestry is questioned - Recreational use and tourism are strengthening - Fresh air, stillness and northern lights leads to increased interest in “pristine forest” and it creates more jobs than forestry industry value chain</p>	<p>- Growth and development of naturebased tourism - A society standing on many “economic legs” - Population growth & increased skills; plenty of jobs - Increasing demand for timber --> more jobs, better prices</p>	<p>livelihoods, less investments for mining and intensified forestry - New sustainable industries being built, for energy production and sustainable materials and products - Forests used more sustainable, allowing other livelihoods, and enhancing biodiversity and ecosystem services, as well as recreation</p>	<p>timber lead to landuse disputes - Disputes relate to how the use of forests is managed and how it affects the environment and local resources -Decrease in labor availability and employment opportunities -The workforce is shifting/transitioning from one industry to another</p>

<p>Land use interests</p>	<p>-Wind power production limits the potential of timber production, they both limit the potential of other land-use forms - The ability to pay determines, which land use forms have the priority</p>	<p>- Strict regulation on forestry causes strong polarization among different industries - The decision power of forestry weakens in regions and growing industries such as tourism strengthens. - Nationally there are a lot of efforts of increasing reconciling of land use disputes</p>	<p>- The right of public access remains an essential part of people's use of nature - Multi-purpose forestry/sustainable forest use; more sustainable and multi-use of forests - Sustainable utilisation of natural resources that consider the needs of all</p>	<p>- The new regulations and goals restrict land use heavily - Land is used sustainably and environmentally friendly - More land and forests being protected, forestry land used for multiple-use and sustainable forestry, no more intensified forestry - Carbon sequestration and ecological compensations influence land use</p>	<p>-Increased land-use disputes related to various factors, such as environmental conservation, economic interests, local needs, and external regulations. - If municipal decision-making authority is absent in land-use planning, it leads to disputes and conflicts, especially when local needs and interests do not have</p>
				<p>heavily, and maintaining biodiversity and carbon sinks has become economically profitable - The value of other forest products than timber is increasing</p>	<p>sufficient influence on decisions</p>

<p>Climate change</p>	<p>-Growth of forests increases -Forestry methods are adapted to changed conditions</p>	<p>- The state of environment improves mainly because of the benefits of strict policies in climate change mitigation - Large part of drained bogs are being restored. - Landowners gain economic benefits from carbon sequestration and ecological compensations.</p>	<p>- Climate change will make this area an attractive place, and a place for future food production for Europe - Increasing growth of forests - Active forestry increases climate benefits</p>	<p>- Because climate change and carbon emissions are affecting land use and decisionmaking, it reduced the amount of CO2 emissions, and we are staying under 2°C rise - Climate change is still affecting nature-based livelihoods, but there are less carbon release, and peatlands and other carbon sinks have been restored</p>	<p>-When forest management leads to excessive carbon dioxide emissions, it caused disputes and conflicts between environmentalists, the forest industry, and other stakeholders. - Disputes related to how land use is planned and how emissions are reduced. -Disputes concerned how wetlands were managed and utilized (restoration).</p>
<p>Biodiversity</p>	<p>-Forestry has reacted to biodiversity loss by segmentation of areas, some areas for wood production, some for</p>	<p>- The restoration and maintenance of biodiversity, environment, and nature increase</p>	<p>- Growing demand for sustainable forest management practices that enhance biodiversity</p>	<p>- Biodiversity is being thought in every action and decision, and its state is becoming better</p>	<p>-Biodiversity weight in decision-making resulted in land-use disputes, especially regarding forest land.</p>

	<p>conservation and some for multiobjective management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Biodiversity management has been upgraded, compensation programs with ecological goals are launched 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The EU's biodiversity and old-growth forest protection goals have significantly reduced the availability of raw wood material. - To secure biodiversity, clearcuttings are not done. - More funds are allocated to restorations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biodiversity issues are increasingly important for decision-making 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Revival and preservation of biodiversity, restorations for peatlands, forests and other carbon sinks are being made. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Balancing the interests of the forest industry and biodiversity conservation. - Disputes arose how forests should be managed and how to balance economic and environmental objectives
--	---	---	--	--	---

<p>Green transition</p>	<p>-The aimed scale of wind and solar power production has been set and follow some local and national prioritization program - Their scale has been fitted together with nature protection and timber production needs, and the possible increase in the power production lies mostly on the technological advancement of the power mills</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Green transition investments cause conflicts between those who gain and loose - International and national steering mechanisms do not support locally and regionally just green transition - Wind and solar power capacity is increasing significantly in regions. This generates local employment opportunities. - In some areas the land use pressure, especially for wind 	<p>- Unexploited opportunities in Lapland, e.g. carbon, landscape and nature value trading - Natural resources and large land area make it possible to implement activities that require extensive land us in connection with green transition</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Green transition did not go through as planned, because it was seen to be too destructive for nature - The overall consumption of resources is reduced - Therefore, there was not so much need for green transition - It was partly done based on sustainable forest use, existing mines for windmills, and effective recycling of materials. 	<p>-Disputes related to how forests and the forest industry should adapt to the green transition increased. - Increasing disputes how wind power projects are implemented and their impact on local land use, the environment, and the economy -Posed threats to alternative land use options by limiting available land for other purposes, such as causing the loss of</p>
--------------------------------	--	--	--	--	--

		<p>power and other industries causes problems, and it restricts the possibilities of forest use.</p>			<p>grazing areas for reindeer .</p>
--	--	--	--	--	-------------------------------------

<p>Technological development</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Resource efficiency in forestry and forest industry has increased (Lean forestry) -Participatory planning methods and landscape scale planning also in private forests is used - More negotiations are used, both between livelihoods and neighbors due to increased land use conflicts and new landscape-scale goals - Recycling is more efficient -Forest knowledge and data has upgraded (GIS) and is utilized 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The amounts of functional negotiations methods of coplanning on forestry land use are increasing. - As the restoration increases forestry operations adapt to it and save both resources and nature and reduce land use conflicts. - Demand for environmentally friendly products leads to improved raw material efficiency and recycling - Sustainable forest management practices that enhance biodiversity, ecosystem services, as well as economic benefits and multifunctionality are being implemented 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase in the use of wood as a sustainable material 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase in new technology on new sustainable material and products like biobased products - The overall consumption of wood has been decreasing, but wood is still used as a sustainable material. - Recycling is more effective by new technology. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -There are increasingly various methods for collaborative land-use planning and negotiations. - These methods enable the participation of different stakeholders, such as forest owners, environmentalists, and local residents, in land-use planning and decision-making - The goal is to reduce conflicts and find sustainable solutions.
---	--	--	---	--	--

Social and cultural change

-Some alternative forest products have more pronounced role in the overall production, timber forms still the main share of the value -Total consumption increases, despite the better resource efficiency and recycling

- The right of public access is an essential part of people's use of nature.
- The monetary value of other forest products than timber has increased
- Overconsumption is tackled by changing lifestyles, and by improving circular economy.

- Less conflict – more understanding
- More opportunities for participation
- Northern areas tempt more people and offer more jobs which has led to population growth

- There has been a huge change in lifestyles and consumption patterns within people and economies
- Economies are based on circular and biobased economies.
- There are more jobs to sustainable tourism, biobased industries and recycling.

-When the economic value of non-timber forest products increases, it affected land-use disputes between forestry and other interests - Increased disputes how forests and their resources should be used in an economically sustainable manner.

4. Scenario narratives

In the following the summarised scenario descriptions pinpointing the main drivers are presented. The scenarios are written in such a way that they represent those interconnected changes that the workshop participants brought up in the group work assignments. The cause-effect ways are described and development paths from 2023 until 2035 are described.

Scenario 1. Forestry growth conditioned by green transition

The growth of forests has increased in Northern Finland and Sweden due to new forestry investment programs and climate change. However, EU and global level biodiversity goals, old-growth forest protection as well as wind and solar power production have somewhat limited the availability of raw wood material for the forest industry. As a result, with a positive climate impact, the net effect for the wood raw material amounts is increasing. The pace of limitations is also, softened due to several reasons, for example prolonged transition periods for the protection goals and advanced energy production technology. In order to achieve the forest growth potential and aimed cutting levels, national and EU level programs - which aim to increased wood production, upgraded nature management and adapting forest management methods to changed climatic and pest control conditions in commercial forests – have been launched. These targeted programs are based on segmentation for the different purposes e.g. for the achieving biodiversity goals include compensation schemes both at the forest holding level, and landscape scale.

Based on the compensations, development of new methods for the biodiversity management in commercial forests and increased willingness of forest owners to maintain biodiversity in their forests, some new environmental goals have been achieved, but some species and forest characteristics are not recovering yet.

The increased cuttings, higher refinement level of products and more active biodiversity management have created more jobs in traditional segments as well as to novel businesses. Generally, this has led to shortage of skilled work force in both some areas and some tasks. In order to overcome these problems, recruitment programs and further training programs have been launched. At the same time automatization and Artificial Intelligence is introduced both in forestry operations and wood processing. Wood energy has been used widely, but due to advancing green transition, wood for energy use has started to reduce. The old energy units are used, but they are upgraded to produce not only hot water for district heating, but also electricity for the grid. The monetary value of other forest products than timber has increased, but timber is still the main forest product and forms the main share of the total value of forest products. The ability to pay determines, which land use forms have the priority. Therefore, forestry and electricity production determine the possibilities of other livelihoods and land use forms.

The forestry planning systems have been developed, and discussions and negotiations between forestry and other livelihoods such as reindeer husbandry and tourism, and they are continuously developing towards suitable solutions. Also, the forest data has upgraded, for example GIS-data about forest tree layer and biodiversity characteristics. This

has led to more precise selection of management methods and timing in forest operations and to improved biodiversity management.

Recycling is more efficient throughout the society. Resource efficiency in forestry and forest industry has increased, and Lean thinking is used widely. However, despite the better resource efficiency and recycling, the total consumption has increased. This continuously put pressure on efficient and fair land use management.

Scenario 2: Local drawbacks from external land use control

External regulation at the EU and global level restricts how forests can be utilized in Northern Finland and Sweden. EU has decided to treat timber as a non-green energy, and use of wood, and forest industry residues as energy has decreased. At the same time multiple use of forests and other livelihoods utilizing forests are increasing. In general, geopolitical sabre-rattling causes continuous instability, especially conflicts of interests between China, Russia and Western world.

The forestry industry is affected by increased conservation, restoration and mitigation measures. Simultaneously nature values, fresh air, stillness and northern lights lead to increased interest in "pristine forest", and it creates new jobs in green tourism more than in forestry industry value chain. The acceptability of forestry is questioned in society. The state of environment improves mainly because of the benefits of strict policies and available funding in climate change mitigation, restoration and maintenance of biodiversity. For example, large part of drained bogs are being restored. Landowners also gain economic benefits from carbon sequestration and ecological compensations and new climate friendly forestry practices and methods are used. However, the EU's biodiversity and old-growth forest protection goals have significantly reduced the availability of raw wood material.

The decision power of forest industry weakens in regions, and growing industries such as tourism, are strengthening. Furthermore, strict regulation on forestry causes strong polarization among different industries. A lot of efforts of increasing reconciling needs of land use disputes had to be implemented, and these negotiations were time consuming for industries. Also, green transition investments cause conflicts between those who gain and lose. International and national steering mechanisms do not adequately support local industries. On the other side, wind power capacity is increasing significantly in regions because of foreign investments, and the same goes also for solar power. This generates new employment opportunities within novel energy systems, but the control and profits remain outside of local communities.

As the peatland restoration increases, forestry has adapted and included operations in sustainable forest management practices. Therefore, forestry enhances biodiversity, ecosystem services, as well as economic benefits and multifunctionality. In addition, the increasing demand for environmentally friendly products guides forestry to improved raw material efficiency and recycling.

The right of public access is still an essential part of people's use of nature. The

monetary value of other forest products than timber has increased, and recreational use promote novel nature-based services. The policies towards circular economy presuppose changing lifestyles.

Scenario 3. Empowered northern communities

Society has increasingly secured the harmonious use of natural resources in all aspects of sustainability. Decision-making processes are better with more participation opportunities, and the processes take different views more into account in order to be more just. Technology has provided platforms and means to enhance the success of reconciliation. Mediation has also promoted transparency, better and fairer decision-making processes, stakeholder equality, and improved dialogue. This has led to a decrease in land use related conflicts. Local economic benefit is emphasised in the use of natural resources.

Society stands on many "economic legs" and northern areas tempt more people and offer more jobs which has led to population growth. Both work possibilities and environmental reasons have accelerated migration towards north. Climate change has made the area an attractive place – also for food production. The growth and development of sustainable nature-based tourism is central as people want to see pristine forests and experience fresh air and loneliness more all the time. Tourism also offers jobs for young people. Transition to a more biobased circular economy has fulfilled its promises and reduced dependence on fossil fuels, created local jobs, and promoted economic development. This development has boosted the economy and enhanced the quality of life in rural areas. The production and use of biobased products have generated local employment opportunities, such as in agriculture, forestry, and other industries.

Increasing growth of forests and demand for timber are benefiting forest owners which are getting more income from forests. However, multi-purpose forestry and sustainable forest use is emphasised, while active forestry increases climate benefits. Growing demand for sustainable forest management practices have also enhanced biodiversity, and biodiversity issues are increasingly important for decision-making. Sustainable utilisation of natural resources considers the needs of all people in society.

The right of public access has remained an essential part of people's use of nature. Still, natural resources and large land area have made it possible to implement activities that require extensive land use in connection with green transition and take advantage of unexploited opportunities, e.g. carbon sequestration, landscape, and nature value trading.

The fear of climate change has made people think about their lifestyles and they have moved to more sustainable way of life by e.g. reducing energy consumption and adopting more sustainable transportation methods. Also, conflicting opinions in society, when addressed properly, has its bright side as it can be a powerful catalyst in creating new innovations and solutions. Collaborative planning methods enable various stakeholders, including forest owners, environmental activists, and residents, to participate in land use planning and decision-making.

Scenario 4. Climate and nature first

In the year 2035, the development of northern Sweden and Finland are strongly influenced by actions on biodiversity and climate, and the regulations are influencing both on EU and local level. Sustainable practices, and the protection of biodiversity are now at the forefront of every decision-making process. Carbon sequestration and ecological compensations are heavily defining the livelihoods, industries, and land use. Acting as carbon sinks or storages, and maintaining biodiversity and ecosystem services, are being economically profitable in society. Locals and indigenous communities are actively involved in the decision-making, ensuring that their traditional knowledge is valued. The peatlands and other carbon sinks are restored, and old-growth forests conserved.

The green transition did not go through as planned, because it was seen to be too destructive for local nature. The overall consumption and way of life has reduced the need for more energy meaning that green transition basically has been implemented with the minerals from the existing mines and effective recycling, which enabled more windmills and solar power plants to be built.

Based on the recognition of limits to planetary boundaries, a total change in consumption patterns and the way of lifestyles has taken place. The economies are based on circular economy and effective recycling, and people are consuming less and adopting a more sustainable and environmentally friendly lifestyles.

The work on climate and nature have led to the flourishing of nature-based livelihoods and sustainable tourism. By the actions on carbon sinks and storages, the amount of carbon emissions has been reduced, and climate change has been mitigated, but it is still affecting the nature and nature-based livelihoods. However, the efforts on nature, restorations and conservations have improved biodiversity and the state of nature.

The forests are used diversely for different purposes like sustainable and traditional livelihoods, gathering, and recreational activities, as well as for forestry, but intensified forestry has shifted to sustainable forestry. Timber is mainly used for long-lived biobased materials and products. Also new sustainable industries for energy production and sustainable materials have emerged. Especially increasing jobs in sustainable tourism and new sustainable industries are attracting new inhabitants to the area.

Scenario 5. Locally conflicting land use interests

The biodiversity and old-growth forest protection goals of the EU lead to conflicts and reduce the availability of raw wood material in certain areas. However, forest use is influenced more by external regulations and agreements at the national, EU, and global levels than by local goals and conditions. Strict regulations in forestry cause strong polarization, and it leads to a sharpening of the debate where parties firmly adhere to their positions. Polarization slows down the decision-making process in land-use disputes, as disagreements become prolonged and difficult to resolve. Communication issues and misunderstandings arise in the flow of information.

The growing demand for raw wood material leads to more severe land use conflicts that are related to forest use management and how it affects the environment and local resources. The availability of labor and employment are also important factors for forest use. The workforce is transitioning and changing between industries, such as tourism and potentially the mining industry, which means that the forestry and forest industry are losing labor. This phenomenon reflects the continuous development of the economy and labor markets, as people adapt to new opportunities and changes in industries. The availability of labor in forestry has been challenging, and the aging workforce in the forestry sector is a cause for concern. When the economic value of forest products other than timber increases, it affects land use conflicts between forestry and other interests. The adaptation of forests and forest industry to the green transition continues to create conflicts. For example, the implementation of wind power projects and discussions about their locations remain divisive topics.

Land use conflicts are related to various factors such as environmental protection, economic interests, local needs, and external regulations. For example, the burden on reindeer herders has increased because they are required to deal with extensive environmental assessments. On the other hand, the pressure to significantly increase wind power capacity in regions, similar to solar power, has brought about its own challenges. Decentralization of decision-making power in land use planning has led to disputes and conflicts, especially when local needs and interests have not had sufficient influence on decisions.

Conflicts often revolve around land use planning and emissions reduction. Disagreements also concern other land use aspects, such as wetlands and how they should be managed and utilized, especially in terms of restoration. When biodiversity is emphasized in decision-making, it affects land use conflicts, especially concerning forest land. Balancing the interests of the forest industry and biodiversity conservation is a challenge. Conflicts also pertain to how forests should be managed and how to balance economic and environmental goals.

5. Conclusions

The constructed five scenarios raise both opportunities and threats how forestry could develop in Northern Sweden and Finland until 2035. In the following, the key issues in each scenario are summarised.

First, in the scenario 'Forestry growth conditioned by green transition' the key driver is the investment rate in forest industry that lean on increased investment programs enabling growth also in the green transition point of view. The key concerns are the pace and scale in which these could be launched. These are affected also by fore-to-come definitions in public policies, especially in environmental, climate and biodiversity goals.

Second, in the scenario 'Local drawbacks from external land use control' the key driver is external regulation affecting local decisions. The key concern is that forest industry is affected by increased conservation, restoration and mitigation measures, and the availability

of wood is decreased. Also, as the outside world is determining the ways forest can be used, the acceptability of forestry can also be questioned in society.

Third, in the scenario 'Empowered northern communities' the concerns have been successfully tackled, and society has increasingly secured the harmonious use of natural resources in all aspects of sustainability, and in fact the key driver in this scenario is sustainable and diversified way of using natural resources. Furthermore, collaborative planning methods enable various stakeholders, including forest owners, environmental activists, and residents, to participate in land use planning and decision-making.

Fourth, in the scenario 'Climate and nature first' sustainable and environmental-friendly practices are at the forefront of every decision-making process. This scenario would mean an extensive sustainability change in consumption patterns and the way of people's lifestyles, as well as private sector practises towards e.g. circular economy and effective recycling.

Fifth, in the scenario 'Locally conflicting land use interests' the key driver is polarization in society, and consequently increasing number of conflicts and unsolved disputes between different land-use interests. The origins of conflicts are related to various factors such as environmental protection, economic interests, local needs, and external regulations.

In ArcticHubs forestry scenario process the aim was to build scenarios based on invited expert knowledge from local to national perspective in a situation where raw wood demand is increasing in Norrbotten, Västerbotten and Lapland, and taking also into account how varying sets of other key drivers in society may evolve until 2035. Such alternative scenario information can be used further to interact and advise actors and policymakers in the field in a future-oriented manner. We tried to represent variance between scenarios that reflect different paths and drivers that the future may entail.

3.

Malå towards 2035

– results from a participatory process covering multiple topics in the ArcticHubs project

(<https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs>)

Gun Lidestav, Per Sandström and Stefan Sandström

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869580.

Malå Arctic report

Content

1. Introduction	3
1.1 Background and goal of the foresight work	3
1.2 Theoretical and methodological approaches	4
1.3 Lean forestry as a tool for mitigating current and future challenges in Malå	4
1.4 The Malå forestry hub	5
2. Presentation of the forecasting process step by step	6
3. Survey results	10
3.1 Summary of the most important opportunities	11
3.2 Summary of the most important threats	12
3.3 Assessment of the factors of change	13
4. Scenario descriptions	16
4.1 Scenario Focus on Diversity.....	16
4.2 Scenario Focus on Growth	17
5. Next step – actions to achieve a desired future	19
6. Concluding reflections	20

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and goal of the foresight work

Malå is one of the seventeen local sites of the ArcticHubs project where the consequences of an increasing global competition for natural resources poses major challenges, and where researchers together with local stakeholders are developing tools for global change adaptation and sustainable development. Concerning the specific tools presented in this report, i.e. a foresight work, Malå is one out of seven local sites (so called hubs), where perceived future opportunities and threats has been identified through surveys and in workshops with the goal to prepare for the future.

The Malå hub represents a complex land-use situation where forestry, mining, wind power developments, and infrastructure projects overlap with the land use needs of Sami reindeer husbandry. Thus, the introduction and development of a Lean Forestry concept, is an integrated part of the foresight work. This means that it is through an action-oriented approach and co-creation of knowledge, that the meaning of the concept in the specific Malå-hub context is develop.

Figure 1. The Malå hub: a circle with 100 km radius from the Setra sawmill, with the Malå

municipality in the center. In the circle there is 2 073 000 ha production forest

corresponding to 53% of the production forest in Västerbotten and the interior of

Norrbotten. 14 reindeer hearing communities are also operating in the hub area

(delineated with red): Ståkke, Östra Kikkejaure, Västra Kikkejaure, Mausjaur, Maskaure,

Malå (skogsamebyar) Luokta-Mavas, Semisjaur-Njarg, Svaipa, Gran, Ran, Ubmeje

tjeälddie, Vapsten, Vilhelmina norra (fjällsamebyar)

1.2 Theoretical and methodological approaches

Our work in Malå ArcticHub has been guided by our long-term experience of action oriented research and participatory strategies in general. The current work process is outlined in fig.2.

Figure 2. A theoretical and methodological description of the participatory process in Malå

1.3 Lean forestry as a tool for mitigating current and future challenges in Malå

In ArcticHubs, the concept of "Lean Forestry" is developed in the context of the overlapping and often competing land use interest and practices of primarily forestry and reindeer husbandry. While trees are the key resource for forestry and the terrestrial and arboreal lichens are key resource for reindeer husbandry systems, both industries seeks to ensure access to the own resource in a cost-effective manner. In this respect forestry has been more successful, and on the expense of reindeer husbandry. An intensification and standardization of forestry activities has brought about a doubling of annual harvest volumes and a densification of forest stands while the lichen-abundant forests has more than halved since the 1980ies. Thus, forestry issues, and in particular adjustments of forestry methods toward reindeer husbandry adapted forestry applications have been the topic during a series of meetings and workshops between SLU, Gran, Gällivare and Malå RHC. Current forest practices have been identified as too static with the same (heavy) methods applied independent on site conditions. The need to develop leaner methods specifically adapted to the unique conditions at each site have become the hope as well as request expressed by the RHCs.

One specific example of leaner methods revolves around how soil scarification is carried out. Current methods focus entirely on providing ideal conditions for the new-planted tree seedlings.

Less attention have been given to impacts on vegetation cover the bottom and field layers. As repeatedly expressed by the RHCs, the critically important and continually declining ground lichen resource are of dire need of improved and leaner soil scarification methods. Based on the outcome of a series of meetings and workshops reindeer husbandry considerations as part of the reforestation effort and specifically leaner and more precise application of soil scarification was selected as our specific case topic demonstrated through the Unmanned Forestry Machine (UFM) developed at Luleå University of Technology in cooperation with SLU and reindeer herding communities (RHC).

During the Malå workshop in May 2023 the first version of the UFM gentle soil scarifier was demonstrated to the participants. Follow up meetings will be organized during the fall of 2023 to further improve and fine tune these methods. This is also to generate broader understanding about future exploitation of different systems origin from the development of the UFM some dissemination events are planned for. Through different collaboration initiatives e.g., with Bracke Forest, Komatsu Forest, the Swedish cluster of forest technology etc. discussions are ongoing about how to increase the TRL for the autonomous lean forestry systems developed in Arctic Hubs and other related projects.

1.4 The Malå forestry hub

From the forest industry perspective, the hub is defined by the Setra sawmill situated in the town of Malå and its timber procurement area. At present, the timber procurement area comprised the forestland within a radius of 100 km from the core, i.e. the sawmill, meaning that the forestry hub stretches beyond the municipality borders. In total, are 14 reindeer herding communities that more or less overlaps with the current procurement area of the sawmill. Considering the nearby expansion of the sawmill, from 350,000 m³ saw logs to 700,000 m³, the procurement area will also enlarge. Consequently, the forestry value chain will be impacted. A brief overview of the current flow of wood resources is presented in Fig.3.

Figure 3. Current flow of wood resources generated by the Setra sawmill in Malå.

2. Presentation of the forecasting process step by step

The forecasting process for the project has so far (March 2022 – November 2023) been carried out in six steps. A final workshop (#3) will be held in May next year with the aim of developing the meaning and application of the Lean Forestry concept, as a very specific tool for implementing sustainable forest management in reindeer husbandry areas. (Fig 1).

Figure 3. A chronological description of the participatory process in Malå

In parallel with the interviews with five local experts, we prepared ourselves by thoroughly reading the local development strategy for Malå municipality 2030, the regional analysis of the value chain of the wood industry in Västerbotten (see fig 4), and a report analysing the sustainability of forest reindeer husbandry in Malå. Through these five key informants, we also

attained valuable information on who to invite for the coming workshop. Considering the increasing demand for timber in the region (Västerbotten and Norrbotten, and thus increased conflicts with other land uses, we realized that it was essential to prepare and present forest resource assessments as a basis for the workshop discussions. Therefore, in the 1st Workshop we introduced results from SKA22 (Swedish forestry impact analyzes 2022) refer to productive forest land in Norr- and Västerbotten counties, and simulations of four future forestry and forest development scenarios based on different assumptions about the future. These were i) Today's forestry (BaU), ii) Focus on Diversity, iii) Focus on Growth, and iv) Combination of Diversity & Growth, and with the assumptions regarding management practices according to table 1, and the outcome regarding harvesting possibilities according to fig. 5.

Figur 5. Kubikmeter sågad volym år 2020 i Västerbotten. Källa: Enkät

Figure 4. Volume (m3) sawn wood in Västerbotten 2020. Source: Walberg Roslund, C. 2022. Från skog till träförädling. Träindustrins värdekedja i Västerbotten. Skogsprogrammet Västerbotten. (modified version of the figure presented in the workshop)

Table 1. Assumptions regarding management practices according Today's forestry (BaU), Focus on Diversity, Focus on Growth, and Combination of Diversity & Growth in Norrbotten and Västerbotten (translated from the table presented in the workshop)

	Today's forestry (BaU)	Focus on Diversity	Focus on Growth	Combination of Diversity & Growth
Set asides	1.5 M ha	2.2 M ha	1.5 M ha	1.9 M ha
Cont. Cover Forestry	0.22 M ha	1.5 M ha	0.12 M ha	0.26 M ha
Fertilization	7 100 ha/yr	-	57 600 ha/yr	17 000 ha/yr
Browsing	12%	10%	5%	5%
Planting	86%	40%	90%	90%

SKA22-scenarierna - Avverkning AC&BD

Figure 5. Harvesting possibilities in Västerbotten and Norrbotten for Focus on Growth, Combination of Diversity & Growth, Focus on Diversity, Today's forestry (BaU) (as presented in the workshop)

Based on the discussions during the workshop (#1) that gathered representatives from forestry, reindeer husbandry, public sector and consultants (in total 16 local stakeholders) scenarios of Focus on Growth, and Focus on Diversity were identified as the most interesting, but that they should be reworked to cover the current and future procurement area of the Setra sawmill in Malå. Further, the more general discussion during the workshop aided us to specify additional factors and drivers affecting the future of the Malå-region. However, as there was no representation from any nature conservation organisation (although invited but there is no local section in Malå), we organised a separate meeting with the local section of a an ENGO (Naturskyddsföreningen) in the city of Skellefteå (8 participants). An additional workshop was also carried out with four Malå municipal planning representatives. Taken together, these discussions and meetings provided a battery of co-created statements for the next phase, i.e. the survey to stakeholders and experts in the Malå region. In addition, questions on key threats and opportunities of the region was asked.

With us researchers and the chair of Malå municipal board as sender, the survey was sent out to 88 stakeholders/experts in the middle of April. One month later, and after one reminder, we had received 32 completed answers, and the survey was closed. When the results of the survey was presented at the 2nd workshop end of May, the participants advised us to make an additional effort to receive more responses, as they perceived that some perspectives were not properly represents. Thus, a 3rd exhortation was sent out beginning of June. Beginning of August, another 7 completed answers were received, and the survey was finally closed with a response rate of 44%.

During the 2nd workshop, the two scenarios Focus on Growth and Focus on Diversity, drafted by the researchers based on survey results on key threats and opportunities in combination with the Malå-region specific forest resource assessment (fig 6 and fig 4), was presented, discussed and modified by the 15 participants.

Figure 3. The areal distribution of forest management according Focus on Growth and Focus on Diversity within a distance of 80 and 160 km from the Malå Setra sawmill. (as presented in the workshop).

With the growth-enhancing measures in Focus on Growth (left graph), the target volume of 700,000 m³sub is available within 70 km on all land and 100 km on Sveaskog's holdings. The corresponding distance for Focus on Diversity (right graph) is 80 and 170 km respectively.

Figure 7. Harvested volumes of pine saw logs/year for the coming 15 years by distance from the Malå Setra sawmill according to Focus on Growth scenario and Focus on Diversity scenario. Dashed lines indicate the target volume for the predicted expansion of the Malå Setra sawmill (as presented in the workshop).

With regards to the *lean forestry* concept, visions new cutting-edge technology for gentle and precise forestry practices was discussed together with research partners from Luleå University of Technology (fig 8). The possibilities of developing and applying the technology/lean forestry in gentle soil preparation on lichen-rich forest lands, was identified as the most interesting option, in particular by the reindeer herders perspective. Thus, it was agreed that the LTU researchers' should return with the machine for a workshop out in the forest in the autumn. However, the because of the storm Hans that hit the Malå-region 8 August all available resources (manpower, machinery etc) had to focus on taking care of the storm-felled forest (>500.000 m³ in an area of almost 100.000 hectares), and restoring destroyed reindeer herding facilities before the winter. Thus, the fifth stage, turned into a further development of the extended survey results, followed by public presentations Malå Future Summit and Fair (30 participants at the Breakfast meeting, and several hundred local Malå citizens of all ages). Thanks to this sixth stage, we have been able to receive further inputs from stakeholders and the general public.

Figure 8. Demonstration of first version of the UFM to workshop the participants.

3. Survey results

The survey was carried out on the Maptionnaire survey platform and included two separate sections. In section 1, the future possibilities and threats of the Malå region were mapped by open ended questions. Respondents were asked to list, in their opinion, first the three most important opportunities and then the three most important threats to the positive development of the region in the 2020s until 2035. Section 2 presented 71 statements about future changes in the Malå region until 2035 organised in seven themes; Society and economy, Reindeer husbandry and Sami culture. Forestry, Mining, Natural environment. The different statements related to the future were evaluated in two different ways: first, an answer was asked for how likely it is considered that the statement will come true, and secondly, for how important or significant this statement was seen for the future development of the Inari region.

As by 8 August a total of 39 respondents provided complete answers of the survey, whereof 26 men and 13 women. Five respondents were 26-50 years old, 25 were 51-65 years old and 8 were + 66 years old. When asked to describe the knowledge, experience and interest in the areas that apply to survey by distributing a total of 100 points, result shows as in figure 9.

Figure 9. Summary of respondents' knowledge, experience and interest in the areas that apply to survey. From left to right; Society and economy (red) Reindeer husbandry and Sami culture

(blue) Forestry (green), Prospecting and mining (purple), Energy production and distribution (turquoise), Natural environment (orange).

3.1. Summary of the most important opportunities

There is a bundle of opportunities for a positive development in Malå based on the richness of natural assets (minerals, soil, water and forests) and the ongoing and intended investments in the exploitation and processing of those. The major investments in mining and the sawmill is a guarantor of jobs, competitiveness, innovations and confidence in the future. Yet, these resources has to managed properly i.e. with consideration to the environment for people and nature. This means that caution should be applied in allowing new mines as they may have a negative impact on the quality of the water resources. Introduction of a leaner forestry management practice that support a multiple use of forests for industrial purposes as well as nature tourism, reindeer husbandry. The refinement of "green products" will in turn create more divers jobs opportunities in the Malå region, which can make young residents to stay others to move in. The expansion of Setra's saw in Malå involves both increased further processing of timber but also increased heat production with greater opportunity to connect more customers to the district heating network. This is part of the broader opportunity statement aiming for a more efficient use of already developed electricity supply. Here, and for the sake of increased sustainability it is needed to invest more resources and a greater willingness to take risks for innovations. Other significant opportunities mentioned are:

- Improved infrastructure in Malå-region through re-industrialization and the green transition
- An attractive municipality with child- and elderly care, school, shops, a rich social and cultural life, many clubs and room for increased population.
- The taxing power of the municipality can be maintained or increased
- Access to great nature experiences for residents and tourists
- Cooperation between different stakeholders
- A good and respectful dialogue between reindeer husbandry and other land users/industries to secure the possibilities to continue with reindeer husbandry.

All in all, the industrial transition creates the opportunity for Malå, among others, to invest in society and take the next step in social development.

3.2 Summary of the most important threats

Perhaps the biggest concern is how to agree on how to understand sustainability; what the nature's carrying capacity is, what climate change will bring about, and then adapt our common demands and actions accordingly. The time pressure on local/regional adaptation of the new industrial boom in the north is worrying, as it requires a continued/increased exploitation of land for mines, wind farms, roads and industries with negative environmental impact in the region. No one seems to have an overview of the cumulative effects of the new wave of exploitation and electrification. It changes the conditions for Malå municipality and put high requirements from the EU/state for a small municipality to adapt. Specific risks mentioned in this context are

- Lack of local unity, which affects communication, marketing and cooperation with the outside world.
- Reduced local influence in overall decision-making processes.
- The negative image of the sparsely populated area and lack of self-confidence of the residents that shadows the opportunities of the region.
- Negative population growth and lack of skilled personnel in both industry and public service all sectors
- The industrial transition makes reindeer husbandry impossible
- That Malåsågen is downsizing due to a shortage of timber.

All in all, the industrial transition also involves risks for the region and its inhabitants as well as for the local authorities due to the speed, the lack of overview, and local scope for action.

3.3. Assessment of the factors of change

In the survey, the experts were asked to rate on a scale of 1-5 how important or significant the individual change factor or phenomenon is perceived for the future of the Malåregion. The statement that was considered most important by the experts was "The forest is an important key to the solution of both the climate crisis and the preservation of biological diversity" which scored 4.71, and the one that was perceived least important was "Excavated wetlands to be restored", which scored 3.35. This suggests that all factors covered by the statements are measured to be of importance for the development of, either as an obstacle or an opportunity. When the statements were presented to the local public at the Malå Future Summit Fair, both agreements and disagreements with the expert opinions were recorded. The statement that received most agreements by the public was "There is already enough with wind power in Malå. (15 agreements and 3 disagreements), while "The ability to pay shall determine which land use interests have priority" received most disagreements (6 disagreements, 0 agreements).

Table 2. The importance/significance of change factors according to survey respondents on a scale of 1-5, and the number of agreements or disagreements from local public during the Malå Future Summit fair.

Co-created statements on Society and economy, Reindeer husbandry and Sami culture, Forestry, Mining, Energy, Natural environment	Mean score by experts	No. of agreements; disagreements by local public
The forest is an important key to the solution of both the climate crisis and the preservation of biological diversity.	4,71	1; 0
Forestry has an important role in the sustainable use of the forest resource.	4,65	5; 1
A sustainable use of natural resources requires that a greater proportion of the value along the value chain stays/is returned to the areas where they are extracted.	4,63	4; 0
The public right is an inalienable part of people's relationship with nature.	4,52	7; 0
A holistic approach to energy supply is needed.	4,50	4; 1
Abandoned mining areas should be restored to forest land.	4,45	1; 0
The use of residuals from the sawmill (chips and bark) is important for energy supply and heating in Malå.	4,45	4; 0
Doing the right thing from the beginning and in accordance with nature is a prerequisite for smart forestry (Lean Forestry).	4,44	2; 0
External regulations and agreements at national/EU/global level affect how the forest can be used more than the local objectives and conditions.	4,43	0; 2
The planning of new or the expansion of existing mines leads to major conflicts.	4,42	1; 0
There is already enough with wind power in Malå.	4,42	15; 3
Active forestry contributes to climate benefits.	4,38	1; 7
A varied natural and cultural landscape is a major quality and attractiveness factor in Malå.	4,38	6; 0
The environmental impact of wind power remains to be resolved.	4,36	3; 0
The forest delivers value beyond revenue from wood raw materials.	4,35	1; 0
The wind and hydropower companies' compensation to the local community, for example in the form of development funds, is sufficient.	4,33	0; 4
Forestry is of national interest and therefore superior to reindeer husbandry as a national interest.	4,32	0; 0
No new mines should start until there is an environmentally friendly extraction technique.	4,32	3; 0
The mining industry is important for other businesses in Malå.	4,29	5; 0
The importance of forestry is increasing because the demand for wood raw material is increasing.	4,27	2; 0
The power lines should be able to be used better to create more climate benefit.	4,27	4; 0
The comprehensive planning is the municipality's main strategic tool for sustainable land use.	4,27	0; 0
Society's task is to ensure that all natural resource utilization takes place in harmony with all sustainability perspectives.	4,25	4; 0
Fellings in the Malå region can increase without reducing the timber supply.	4,25	0; 0
Nature sets the limits of the economy.	4,25	2; 1
Let each industry bear its environmental costs.	4,25	?
Good consultation processes with other land users are a prerequisite for a functioning reindeer husbandry.	4,24	2; 0
Not all land use interests can be accommodated and therefore prioritization is necessary.	4,23	1; 0
The non-resident ownership is a threat to economically, ecologically and socially sustainable forestry.	4,23	1; 0
When different national interests are pitted against each other, reindeer husbandry must come first.	4,22	1; 0
Good consultation processes are a prerequisite for smart forestry (lean forestry).	4,21	0; 0
A viable mining industry contributes to a good road standard.	4,21	0; 1

The ever-increasing energy consumption must be exchanged for a much more efficient and reduced energy use.	4,17	2, 1
The environmental impact of hydropower remains to be resolved.	4,16	3, 0
It is not possible to reconcile the claims of the various industries/interests on the natural resources.	4,14	1; 1
Sami culture is fundamentally dependent on a viable reindeer husbandry.	4,12	4; 0

Co-created statements on Society and economy, Reindeer husbandry and Sami culture, Forestry, Mining, Energy, Natural environment	Mean score by experts	No. of agreements; disagreements by local public
In the municipality, there are working methods for negotiations and co-planning around various wishes regarding land use	4,11	0; 1
A green transition involves extensive investments in new infrastructure for energy transmission e.g. more power lines and charging posts.	4,11	0; 0
When different national interests are pitted against each other, the nature conservation interest must come first.	4,11	1; 0
Existing mines are sufficient for Sweden's needs and therefore no new mining should be allowed.	4,10	0; 0
Prospecting is not a threat to nature and the cultural environment.	4,05	0; 1
A changed climate makes it more attractive to live in Malå.	4,04	6; 3
When different national interests are pitted against each other, the mining industry must go first.	4,04	1; 1
The municipality has too limited opportunities to decide on land use.	4,00	0; 0
The municipality has a coordination responsibility to monitor the social values of the forest and ensure citizens' access to natural environments through, for example, hiking trails.	3,96	7; 0
Sami cultural environments/remains are threatened by other land use (land preparation, wind farms, mining areas, roads).	3,96	2; 0
Preserve the beauty and experience values of nature.	3,96	11; 0
The mining industry is a prerequisite for the green transition.	3,94	1; 2
The rules of the economic and financial system must be adapted to the climate goals.	3,94	7; 0
Climate change is a threat to reindeer husbandry.	3,93	4; 2
Reindeer husbandry has an important role for the sustainable use of forest land.	3,90	0; 0
Heavy transport has a negative impact on the habitat along the road.	3,89	0; 0
The environmental impact of hydropower remains to be resolved.	3,89	2; 0
Climate and biodiversity issues are increasingly important to the balance between different claims	3,86	1; 0
Today's forestry emits too much CO2.	3,86	2; 2
Today's forestry practices endanger the survival of reindeer husbandry.	3,86	2; 0
Continuous cover forestry favors both the availability of lichen and biodiversity.	3,83	1; 1
Without coordination between different forest owners, we cannot achieve good efficiency in terms of provisions/protection for biodiversity.	3,83	1; 0
When different national interests are pitted against each other, the energy supply must come first.	3,83	0; 0
Today's forestry practices lead to reduced lichen grazing.	3,77	2; 0
The Sami right of use to land and water is property protected and thus constitutionally protected in the same way as ownership.	3,77	3; 0
The municipality has a coordination responsibility to develop natural resources through active use of these to contribute to increased photosynthesis and carbon storage.	3,76	0; 0
The status of the Forest Sami reindeer husbandry needs to be strengthened, for example through the formation of a centre.	3,75	0; 0
The municipality should be an experimental area for forestry adapted to reindeer husbandry.	3,75	2; 0
Abandoned mining areas should be restored to reindeer grazing land.	3,73	3; 0

The green transition poses a threat to forestry in Malå.	3,68	4; 0
The Sami culture is an under-used asset for the municipality.	3,67	2; 0
The ability to pay shall determine which land use interests have priority.	3,60	0; 6
Clearcutting depletes the species richness of the forest landscape.	3,57	4; 0
Smaller watercourses shall be restored so that their natural functions are restored.	3,56	1; 0
The effects of a changing climate are a threat to living conditions in Malå.	3,55	0; 0
Forestry must be carried out without clear-cuttings.	3,52	2; 2
Continuous cover forestry is a prerequisite for keeping real forests and producing quality timber.	3,52	1; 2
Using the forest land for wind power is more profitable than timber production.	3,52	1; 2
Excavated wetlands to be restored.	3,35	0; 0

4. Scenario descriptions

4.1 Scenario Focus DIVERSITY - 2035

The Malå region has not been caught up in the race for large investments, but has instead profiled itself through the development of various social functions for an ecologically sustainable restructuring of industry and management of the region's natural resources. Fundamental is citizens' awareness of the planet's limitations and the unsustainability of current production and consumption patterns of both food and energy. Therefore, the local/regional food supply has also increased both from existing farmland and from the forest (berries, game, and reindeer). The only energy we can sustainably use is what can grow annually on the planet together with a well-thought-out use of solar energy in a sustainable way in harmony with nature. Business is based on renewable raw materials and an increased local processing of these, closed cycles of sewage sludge and compost material. Some land exploitation (e.g. mines, wind power, infrastructure) is unavoidable but must take place with consideration for nature, other land users and social values. All permits include pre-compensation measures and post-completion restoration. Laws and international conventions are implemented. In existing operations, continuous energy efficiency improvement takes place. Multiple use of forests, partly logging-free methods for both raw material supply (biomass, sawmills and further processing) and carbon sequestration in living trees. Good opportunities to run reindeer husbandry, nature tourism and other industries with a connection to nature, e.g. fishing, partly thanks to a good dialogue and cooperation between the land use stakeholders in the area and partly to a developed cooperation with universities and research. The availability of fine nature experiences for both temporary visitors and permanent residents has contributed to increased tourism and immigration. State, region, municipality and business cooperate in terms of development of necessary infrastructure and equal supply of skills locally.

The threats to the above scenario are that we in the Malå region have not managed to achieve a consensus on what sustainability is/means and that we have not managed to raise awareness and increase the confidence of the residents about the Malå region's possibilities. This makes us vulnerable to external overarching political and market-driven decision-making processes. Concretely, it can mean a shortage of raw materials for local companies due to

environment/climate-related restrictions and continued export of raw materials to other parts of Sweden and the world instead of local processing.

Society and economy

- The region's development is positive and is based on a locally rooted strategy for sustainable management of natural resources and human capital
- Conflicts between land use interests have been replaced by dialogue and cooperation.
- Immigration, education and research have increased the region's attractiveness

Forestry

- Logging on 39% of the forest land, no logging on 21%. Benefiting ground lichen on 10%. However needs to be increased aiming for 1986 state. Reserves make up to 14%, voluntary reserves 10% and consideration areas 6%, but often not suitable for reindeers, • Lower growth due to less intensive forestry
- All available growth is harvested
- The target volume of 700,000 m³ is available within 80 km on all land and 170 km on Sveaskog's holdings

Prospecting and mining

- Only underground mines where the transport has also been adapted to the conditions and needs of the local environment

Reindeer herding and Sami culture

- Improved availability of reindeer pasture (beneficial ground cover) that corresponds to the reindeer's natural needs
- It is possible to live on reindeer husbandry

Energy

- Energy consumption should be reduced but not likely to happen
- No new wind power, but current plants should be made more efficient

Tourism

- Increased nature based tourism
- Better organized and regulated to avoid conflicts (e.g. dog sledging)

4.2 Scenario with a Focus on GROWTH - 2035

New industrialization and the green transition in the North have also strengthened the region's competitiveness and the infrastructure (road network and broadband) has improved. Active forestry and the processing of "green products" are fundamental, but the extraction of minerals

also contributes to the development of society. More of the value creation stays in the region from the extensive investments in sawmills/wood processing and mining operations that have generated new jobs, immigration and increased tax power. The attractive business climate, including investments in innovation work for sustainability, stimulates business establishment, local entrepreneurship and creates conditions for the municipalities to invest in community services and take the next step in community development. This means an investment in the creation of attractive living environments both in the urban areas and in the countryside, with the possibility of broadband via fiber for remote work, small business and some self-sufficiency in food, which also strengthens crisis preparedness and the local economy. Construction of senior housing has contributed to migration chains/generational change and thus moving into the villages as well. Thanks to the upward spiral created by the new industrialization, house prices are increasing, which also signals that it is somewhat exclusive to have a cottage or house in the region. A rich club life also contributes to the attractiveness.

The direction and pace of the transition is also beyond the region's control, which also means that public investments in housing, roads, etc. (including decision-making processes) do not meet the needs. At the same time, the combined effects of new industrialization in the form of developed infrastructure, forest felling and hydropower, etc. together with climate change, constitute a real threat to the survival of reindeer husbandry. The availability of skills/labour is a problem for both the growth of business and community services, including politics.

Society and economy

- The community economy is developing positively and thus also community services
- Conflicts between land use interests have been replaced with a respectful dialogue and cooperation.
- Immigration, education and research have increased the region's attractiveness
- A strong association life and culture have an increased role in community building

Forestry

- Logging on 77% of the forest land, no logging on 1%. Reserves make up 10%, voluntary
- provisions 5% and consideration areas 7%.
- The target volume of 700,000 m³ available within 70 km on all land and 100 km on Sveaskog's holding
- Higher growth due to more intensive forest management
- All growth on the cultivated area is felled
- Optimization of available resources

Prospecting and mining

- Being developed

Reindeer husbandry and Sami culture

- The industrial transformation makes reindeer herding impossible
- An important growth factor for society and business
- The Sami culture is unique and thus has a prominent role in the profiling of Malå the region

Energy

- Expansion/modernization of hydropower
- Increased deliveries of hot water to the district heating network
- More energy efficient vehicles
- Alternative fuels (hydrogen)
- No new wind power

Nature

- Innovative technology provides less negative impact on the using nature and thus increased biodiversity

Tourism

- Industrial restructuring promotes the hospitality industry

5. Next step – actions to achieve a desired future

The previously describe scenarios with regards to the forest resource and future harvesting potential, including expert opinion expressed in workshops and the survey, are based on the conditions before the storm Hans on the 8th of August. In less than an hour, 583 000 m³ was damaged and in need for harvesting. The core area includes 4250 hectares of almost 100% windrow stands of all age classes, but in total some 93 000 hectares were impacted. A great number of reindeer heading facilities were also destroyed. Harvesting teams from different companies in all Northern Sweden were mobilized to help out with the recovery of the storm-damaged timber before the winter. However, it is estimated that some of the timber cannot be recovered until next summer because of the snow conditions. By then, the full impact of the storm, also in terms of future harvesting potentials, will also be known. This in turn may imply that an alternative harvesting scenarios should be developed in case the local stakeholders ask us to do so.

Figure 10. The effect of the storm Hans illustrating the core area of impact, based on analysis of change in Sentinel.

Regardless of the storm, the overlapping and often competing land use interests of forestry and reindeer husbandry, has been a recurring theme throughout the foresight process. This has been further underlined by the DPSIR study. While forestry has doubled timber production, lichen availability has halved. Thus, adjustments of forestry management methods toward reindeer husbandry adapted forestry applications will become an even more important issue when the production at the Setra sawmill in Malå will magnify. It is in this context the vision of "Lean Forestry" will be outlined and concretized as tool for implementing sustainable forest management in reindeer husbandry areas. At the final workshop in the forest (May 2024) next year, the meaning and application of the Lean Forestry in reforestation will be outlined.

Maj 2024

Workshop 3
– Vad innebär
"Lean Forestry" i
Malå-regionen

Lean forestry – verktyg för framtidens skogsbruk i Malåbygden

This project has received funding from the European Union under the Marie Skłodowska Curie Grant Agreement No. 101019718. The content does not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union, nor does it constitute an endorsement or approval by the European Union of the views or information contained therein.

6. Concluding reflections

To carry out co-creation of knowledge through in a participatory process that involves multiple topics and perspectives is both challenging and rewarding. Challenging because you/the research team has to be sensitive to the responses from the participants and based on the progress of the process, also very flexible. The possibility of adapting the forecasting approach and implementation of the Delphi method to the Malå hub situation, has therefore been crucial for success. By applying an action-oriented research approach, we believe that the outcome of the process will be rewarding both for the Malå hub participants and for us in the research team. Valuable indicators of this are;

- Largely the same people/participants have stayed interested and involved in the different stages of the process.
- The participants have initiated and promoted additional activities, e.g. to re-open the survey and for them to motivate non-respondents to complete the survey.
- The statements developed (co-created) and put forward in the survey are considered important to most of the respondents.
- To invite us to present the results to the local enterprises at the monthly breakfast event "GoMorrøn Malå.
- Through the Malå Future Summit we received new valuable knowledge from the general public in Malå.
- Invite us and LTU to a meeting with Forestry and Reindeer husbandry Consultation Group to discuss the potential application of the Unmanned Forestry Machine within the concept of Lean Forestry.
- To engage in the development of the Immersive Game Experience through Game Design workshops with Malå students

As overall concluding reflections, we would like to put forward that:

- The results are not from researchers own findings but from a truly participatory process
- We have moved from knowing there are issues to knowing about issues
- We believe such co-creative processes contribute to continued stakeholder engagement and function as an important capacity builder
- We believe co-created solutions are better implemented than top down developed solutions. Being a part is an important part.

4.

Future scenario report Suðuroy, Faroe Islands. ArcticHubs.

Report prepared by Ragnheiður Bogadóttir, ragnheidurb@setur.fo

In the Suðuroy case, the research team has endeavored to engage the local community in ways that are respectful to time expenditure of participants and the social entanglements of smaller communities with the themes addressed in the ArcticHubs project. The future scenario work has been based on material collected throughout the project period. The aim of the future scenario work has been to identify and articulate future visions and knowledge from local experts and stakeholders, especially in tourism and fish farming, but to also allow alternative perspectives from broader civil society. To accomplish this, data material for the future scenario work has been collected through five main rounds of data collection, each round of results feeding into the following rounds:

1. Stakeholder workshops (four workshops in total) with municipal administration staff (September 2021 and March 2023). The local municipal authorities were initially and prior to the workshops contacted about possible research collaboration and agreed to this. Number of local participants in the workshops were between 3 and 6.
2. Survey (Maptionnaire) open to the public in Suðuroy (March 2022). The web-based survey was constructed around main themes of the ArcticHubs project in collaboration with stakeholders. The survey was shared through the available social media communication channels of the local municipalities. **95** respondents submitted their responses.
3. Expert interviews with local and non-local experts on tourism and fish farming (Spring and summer 2022). In all **12** informants participated in the interviews.
4. Workshop and survey (Maptionnaire) with young upper-secondary school students on Suðuroy (March 2023). Contact was established through the leadership of the upper-secondary school, who hosted the workshop during school hours. Around **80** people participated in the workshop, and 73 of the workshop participants also submitted their responses to the survey.
5. Final questionnaire round (Maptionnaire) (November 2023). The questionnaire was sent to **53** participants by email. Participants can be divided into two categories: the first category (26) have been identified as experts or stakeholders, and they have participated in the earlier research process in expert interviews or stakeholder workshops. The second category of people (27) have participated in one of the two previous Maptionnaire surveys and have provided their email contact upon the completion of the survey.

6. Future scenario presentation workshop (September 2024). This consisted of two rounds. First round was arranged at the upper-secondary school in Suðuroy with approximately **90** participants, and the second round was public with approximately **10** participants.

4.1 Scenario work process in Suðuroy, Faroe Islands

The future scenario work process in the Suðuroy hub can be divided into the five data collection rounds listed above. The contextual background informing the future scenario work in Suðuroy, came out of the work in WP1 and WP2. In WP1 the official and national future strategies for aquaculture and tourism were mapped through analyzing grey literature such as Governmental agency reports, general parliamentary debates, and expert interviews (with government ministers and governmental agencies on tourism and aquaculture). In WP2 environmental data was collected, providing the ecological context. One main outcome from this part of the project was to identify social, political and environmental drivers and trends as they were perceived at the national Faroese level.

In the first and second data collection round, workshops were organized in Suðuroy, and a survey was designed and carried out, with future related questions as well as questions about the effect on people's lives and well-being of tourism and aquaculture today in Suðuroy. The first workshops took place in September 2021. Present at these meetings were administrative staff of the municipality including staff at the local tourism offices (workshops took place in two municipalities). The aim with the initial workshops was to open discussions about the themes of the ArcticHubs project, global drivers and local consequences, and how these trends are manifesting in Suðuroy. Also, a preliminary draft version of the survey was presented to facilitate coproduction, and the feedback from the workshop participants was incorporated into the survey. The survey was web-based and people in Suðuroy could access it through a link. The invitation to the survey and the link was shared through social media channels of the municipality. To facilitate the reiterative process, people were encouraged to write their email if they agreed to being contacted for further participation. 19 out of the 95 respondents who submitted their response also submitted their email contact. These 19 respondents were reengaged in the final data collection round.

The future related questions of the survey asked to what degree their imaginaries of the future in Suðuroy were positive/hopeful or negative/pessimistic. Also, respondents were asked to prioritize what industries they believed the municipalities should encourage in the future, and to what degree; fisheries, aquaculture and tourism. Other questions were related to the effects of these industries on their communities and well-being today.

The largely quantitative results from the survey were complemented with in-dept interviews with local experts on aquaculture and tourism. Also, as our results at this point showed that respondents and participants so far had close to exclusively been middle-aged or older, a second workshop and survey was organized to engage with youth and youth's future perspectives. 8 out of the 73 respondents who submitted their response also submitted their email contact. These 8 respondents were reengaged in the final data collection round. The youth workshop was organized so that the research team first introduced the relevant themes, and the rationale behind research questions. Then, students were presented with the link to the survey, and filled in the survey using their phones

or other devices. Following that, the survey results were immediately presented to the students (only the quantitative results were shown, not individual comments of course). The final workshop sessions facilitated student feedback to the results and collective interpretation and discussion.

The final data collection round of the future scenario work reengaged participants in the previous workshops and surveys to focus specifically on the opportunities and threats they see for their communities today and towards the year 2035.

4.2 Opportunities and threats in fish farming and aquaculture

The primary **opportunity** for aquaculture today and in the future lie in the natural assets, in the environmental conditions that are so well suited for farming fish (salmon). Since these assets are so dependent upon sustainable production, sustainability needs to be seized as an opportunity.

Opportunities for aquaculture lie in broadening and diversifying aquaculture instead of focusing exclusively on fin fish farming. Multi-trophic aquaculture could be developed to be more in line with the sustainability goals (climate and biodiversity).

Looking ahead offshore fish farming is identified as an opportunity for fish farming and local communities in two respects. Going offshore is necessary if the industry (production volume) is to grow further. Second, moving fish farming out of the fjords would enable recovery of the fjords, biodiversity could be regenerated, and sustainable and regenerative activities, also alternative economic activities, in the fjords could be established.

Changing consumer behavior in relation to greater focus on sustainability and climate change mitigation can be turned into an opportunity if production is, or is perceived to be, sustainable.

Threats for fish farming in the Arctic is pollution and other environmental consequences. Further growth of fish farming in the fjords, and the noise and pollution close to inhabited places, represents a threat.

Climate change presents a direct threat in the form of more extreme weather and weather events. This presents particular challenges if fish farming is to go offshore. Also, changing oceanographic conditions, temperature and acidification are a treat to fish farming. Indirectly, climate change is changing and affecting consumer behavior, not always in ways predictable. If farmed fish is considered unsustainable market value drops and undermines the industry.

Political opposition to the growth of the fish farming industry is also considered a threat.

4.3 Opportunities and threats in tourism

Tourism is the new big opportunity for development, since the fisheries and fish farming industries have been bought up and taken over by outside investors. Tourism can be developed through local initiative and local participation and control is high and well as the revenues being retained in the local area.

Opportunities for tourism lie in developing niche tourism products that secure a high revenue low-impact industry, for instance business tourism. At the same time, also when it comes to developing

niche tourism such as business tourism, it is still nature that is attracting tourists, and this is where the opportunities lie, experiences in nature! Preserving and protecting nature is therefore crucial.

Another opportunity stressed lies in better planning. Initially local planning, but also more regional and national discussion and control over the development of tourism. This requires coordination and foresight so that overcrowding in certain places is avoided and as well as vacancy in others. If properly planned, many more tourists could visit, because there are so many sites that can be attractive where they could be distributed.

Climate change presents an opportunity to develop domestic tourism. To incorporate tourism into already existing infrastructure and practices, thereby enhancing existing institutions and local well-being.

Threats. Mass tourism is a threat also because of the resulting erosion of biodiversity. Climate change is a threat because of consumer behavior and the flight miles/carbon footprint of long-distance tourism.

Tourism enterprises that have been developed by local entrepreneurs are becoming profitable, and are then bought up by outside investors, meaning locals lose control.

Certain nature and wilderness areas are branded and assessments over whether nature can carry the arriving numbers have not been adequate, and local landowners and other stakeholders have not been heard and consulted in advance. This results in degradation of nature, local conflicts, and bad publicity on top. Local people thereby lose access to their own local nature (in summer), and antagonism between local tourism stakeholders and other users of land becomes a problem.

4.4 Scenario narratives

The island of Suðuroy is the southernmost island of the Faroe Islands and approximately 8% percent of the Faroese population live in Suðuroy. The Faroes have experienced very rapid economic development; GDP per capita in 2022 was 407,000 DKK, corresponding to approximately 50,000 Euro, and real GDP growth in 2022 was 5,4%. The primary sector, fisheries and fish farming, account for between 90 and 95% of export value, and in recent years tourism has been promoted and developed to become the “third leg” of the Faroese economy.

Historically, Suðuroy was the center of the Faroese industrialization, but after the mid-twentieth century, Suðuroy has increasingly moved towards a peripheral status also reflected in lower average income. One of the main characteristics of the (Arctic) periphery is that resource extraction increases, while the local communities struggle with social cohesion and declining population. This general and overarching historical trend presents local communities with the challenges of balancing economic development and foreign investment with local sustainability and resilience. This is also the case in Suðuroy, where discussions are ongoing about how to adapt to global change, and often these discussions are characterized by the notion that development is a question of either “jumping on the train” or being left behind.

The purpose with the future scenario work in Suðuroy has been to identify and articulate different perceptions and visions about present and future threats and opportunities for positive development and adaptation to global change and global drivers in Suðuroy. The aim of the process has been to

construct future scenario narratives, providing ground for consensus, while also highlighting the inherent political tensions of such processes.

4.5 Materials for scenario construction

The materials for the scenario construction have been collected throughout the ArcticHubs project period and consist of expert interviews, environmental data, online surveys, and workshops (see above).

From the processing and discussions of the collected materials, four future scenarios could be delineated that represent the most dominant imaginaries: 1) Business-as-usual, 2) Isolation and recession, 3) Alternative sustainability, and 4) Technofix to current problems. Some are considered more likely than others, and some more utopian. During the work process, however, the acceleration of climate change and its more visible consequences, the changing political situation in Europe (war in Ukraine), and the sudden chock of the covid19 pandemic has brought renewed attention to local resilience and self-sufficiency and a concordant uncertainty regarding the stability of economic and political conditions that have seemed almost natural for a long time.

4.6 Scenario narratives 1,2,3, and 4

Scenario 1: Business-as-usual. Suðuroy has continued on its development trajectory and has been succesful in attracting some level of outside investment. These investments manifest locally in the form of large industrial infrastructure. Production requires land and coastal resources and space. It also requires large volumes of material and energy input. The subsea tunnel that was constructed meant that these input materials can be transported to the island, and the output produce can be exported. Ecological (including carbon) footprints of the local economy have increased significantly because of this. To address this problem, large public and private (industry) investments have been made in green energy infrastructure, which are very visible in the landscape and have become a cause of conflicts with other forms of landuse. The local green energy production means the local industries can show a reduction in their carbon accounting. Population numbers are relatively stable, because outmigration of the local youth is balanced with a growing foreign workforce.

Scenario 2: Isolation and recession. The proposed tunnel to Suðuroy never became a reality. Economic recession and a partial collapse in the fisheries export industries meant that political priorities changed. Because of the high transport costs to and from the island, the large international industrial actors decided transport costs of production were too high, and they made no new reinvestments. Tourism has grown a lot on the national level, but because the only way to travel to Suðuroy is ferry transport, Suðuroy is not able to attract a large enough number of tourists to upkeep more than a few stable year-round jobs. Population has not grown, and the ageing population has created problems in the basic welfare services.

Scenario 3. Alternative sustainability. New sustainability legislation, the political and environmental situation, and a matured understanding of sustainable development enabled an alternative trajectory in Suðuroy. The proposed sub-sea tunnel to Suðuroy never became a reality, and the large

international industrial actors decided transport costs of production were too high. Attention to the environmental consequences of large-scale fish farming in the fjords meant restrictions were put on the scale of production. A concurrent collapse in the fish farming industry as a consequence of a regional and devastating fish virus outbreak together with increasing sea lice problems meant that alternatives had to be developed. Fortunately, local and expert knowledge and expertise in the area combined to establish new industrial process that were founded on nature-based solutions thinking rather than on high material and energy throughput. The investment in green energy production in the beginning of the period towards 2035 means that Suðuroy is self-sufficient in renewable energy.

Scenario 4. Technofix to current problems. Technological development finally managed to solve some of the problems that were hindering positive development in Suðuroy. The sub-sea tunnel was constructed, increasing mobility and accessibility, and the electrification of the transport sector and the huge investments in renewable energy meant that carbon footprints did not increase with increasing mobility. The marine related industries found solutions to the problems with pollution by moving production out of the fjords and up on land and offshore. This meant that production could be further expanded, and because of the improved technological solutions, monitoring of production has been digitized and can be managed long-distance. Labor for the industry is largely a migrant workforce, and the people in Suðuroy can commute to work other places in the Faroes. Suðuroy attracts a growing number of tourists who come on day-trips to visit some of Suðuroy's iconic landscapes.

5.

Nuuk's future year 2035

Future workshop with complex topics and broad participation from the local community.

Lively and nuanced group dialogues across insights, interests and needs.

The research activity with future workshop is part of the EU-funded research project ArcticHubs no 869580 (<https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs>)

Report by researcher and project manager Kristine Lynge-Pedersen

PINNGORTITALERIFFIK
GRØNLANDS NATURINSTITUT
GREENLAND INSTITUTE OF
NATURAL RESOURCES

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869580.

INDHOLDSFORTEGNELSE

1. BACKGROUND TO FUTURE WORKSHOPS	
1	
2. DESIGN OF WORKSHOP	
1	
2.1. Composition of conversation topics	
1	
2.2. Group composition with participants from different societal positions	
2	
2.3. Consideration of language	
3	
2.4. Notes and report	
3	
2.5. Joint gathering session at the start and end of workshop evening	
3	
2.6. Press release and radio interviews	
4	
2.7. Evaluation of the design.....	
4	
3. FUTURE SCENARIOS FROM WORKSHOPS 1 AND 2	
5	
Opportunity scenarios and wish scenarios	5
Threat scenarios	11
3.1. SUMMARY OF FUTURE SCENARIOS	14
4. CONCLUSION	
17	

1. BACKGROUND TO FUTURE WORKSHOPS

The Greenland Institute of Natural Resources is part of an EU-funded research project ArcticHubs no. 869580 and participates in the working packages *Tourism* and *Indigenous Peoples*. We use different participatory research methods, where different actors together create solutions that can be used to adapt to new economic activities such as tourism.

By engaging Greenlandic actors, solutions and initiatives can be developed that respect and are adapted to the needs and culture of the local population.

The ArcticHubs project conducts future workshops in seven different countries/locations to collect local actors' suggestions for future opportunity scenarios, threat scenarios and the most desirable future scenarios and what it takes to realize the desired scenarios.

2. DESIGN OF WORKSHOP

2.1. Composition of conversation topics

The 7 countries that carry out physical future workshops will all work with the year 2035 and with topics opportunities and threats for the future and the most desirable future scenario for the year 2035, and all will hold physical workshops with participants from different positions in society. Each hubs have the opportunity to adapt the workshop to the local context and the researchers' resources.

In Nuuk, researcher and project manager Kristine Lyng-Pedersen chose to use a simple version, where the participants' physical meeting was put in focus and supplementary online study was deselected. The personal attendance with active participation in group dialogue was put in focus, and therefore there were no introductory and time-consuming presentations, and the groups rather did not present presentations in the forum.

In order to initiate the group dialogue, dialogue forms were prepared for both workshops. For workshop 1, the following 5 open conversation topics were included in the dialogue form:

- Local tourism. Opportunities, threats and business as usual and the drivers behind them.
- The local Greenlandic culture. Opportunities, threats and business as usual and the drivers behind them.
- The local hunting and fishing industry. Opportunities, threats and business as usual and the drivers behind them.
- Climate change. Opportunities, threats and business as usual and the drivers behind them.
- Nature- and culturally sustainable business development. Opportunities, threats and business as usual and the drivers behind them.

In the planning phases, only the first two topics, *Tourism* and *The Local Greenlandic Culture*, were chosen as talking points, but in case the dialogue should standstill/stall, the other three topics were added.

For workshop 2, the following 2 conversation topics were included in the dialogue form:

- The positive and negative effects of 1) The opportunity-oriented future scenario, 2) The threat-oriented future, 3) The BAU-oriented future scenario.

- Most desirable future scenarios and measures/Actions for realization

The dialogue form was attached to the invitation so that participants could prepare.

It was planned that the groups themselves should appoint a note taker and the co-facilitators should step in and make sure that the group dialogue followed the dialogue form – At each group table there were A3 sheets of paper with the conversation topics and space to take notes. The cofacilitators took notes and took a listening position to create speaking time for the participants. As the co-facilitators were external consultants and had limited insight into the ArcticHubs project, researcher and project manager Kristine Lynge-Pedersen was available to all three groups and circulated around to the groups.

2.2. Group composition with participants from different societal positions

The aim was to create a cross-cutting new societal dialogue on future scenarios. Therefore, participants from several levels of society were invited; the national, regional and local levels, as well as cross-cutting areas; tourism sector, the culture sector and fishing sector.

Researcher and project manager Kristine Lynge-Pedersen identified the following categories of actors:

1) Elected national and municipal politicians, 2) Administrators at national and municipal level, 3) Interest groups (11 identified as relevant), 4) Tourist operators, 5) Cultural operators, 6) Experts, 7) Ordinary citizens.

For reasons of space and resources, representatives from the different categories were selected. Two of the national politicians in the areas of tourism and culture were invited. Three municipal politicians were invited. 11 interest groups focusing on culture, hunting and fishing as well as nature and the environment. A wide range of local tourist operators ranging from accommodation facilitators, eateries, sailing operators etc. Cultural operators such as artists, writers, linguists, cultural centre and museums, etc. Expert in indigenous peoples' rights and Greenlandic culture and individual ordinary citizens. In addition, gender and age distribution were taken into account in identifying potential participants.

Invitation letters were sent out to a total of 89 participants, of which 35 signed up. The majority could attend both workshops, few could only attend one of the two. A few cancelled on the day, few did not appear. Thus, a total of 30 representatives of society participated. 1 Naalakkersuisoq for Business and Trade, 3 administrators from the municipality, 2 administrators from the SelfGovernment, 9 representatives from 5 interest groups (KNAPK, NAPP, Ocean North, Qaannat kattuffiat, Nuup Kangerlua Ikinngutai, WWF), 5 tourism actors, 6 cultural actors, 4 citizen representatives. There were 23 and 21 participants respectively at the two workshops. Thus, it was not an open event, but in the invitation letter the invitees were given the opportunity to recommend other relevant participants, and some were recommended, and they were sent an invitation. Since the workshop was to be held at the start of the reindeer hunting season, Tuesdays were chosen as meeting days, so hunting at the weekends was taken into account. In addition, the evening time was chosen so that the event did not collide with the participants' work duties. Ordinary citizens and association representatives have rare opportunities to participate in non-workrelated events during working hours. It is hard to actively participate in an evening event after a long working day, therefore daytime is otherwise preferable.

In order to ensure the opportunity of facilitating a dialogue across areas, interests and wishes, the registered participants were distributed into pre-composed groups. When different insights,

experiences and interests meet, nuanced understandings, creative ideas and broad solutions can be created. It was clear to observe that the group participants formed new insights and new acquaintances and new opportunities for collaboration.

Meeting time was excluded from group dialogue. Therefore, no time was spent on presentations. The participants sat in one particular group both evenings, which was an advantage as some had time to get to know each other and build relationships.

2.3. Consideration of language

The official languages of Greenland are Greenlandic and Danish. Some citizens are monolingual, speak either only Greenlandic or Danish and other citizens are bilingual or more. The Danish language is often used in public dialogues.

In order to create flow in the group dialogues, simultaneous interpretation was deselected. Instead, participants were asked to state their language preference when registering, so that Greenlandic-speaking and Danish-speaking groups could be formed, respectively. 2/3 of the participants chose to participate in a Greenlandic-speaking group, so two Greenlandic-speaking and one Danish-speaking group were formed, each of which was placed in their own room.

The consideration of language preference was received with great pleasure and the dialogues quickly flowed and groups skipped the coffee break, and some wanted to continue the dialogue all night long.

Of course, there were also downsides to language considerations. A Danish-speaking participant wanted to hear what the Greenlandic-speaking hunters and fishermen expressed. This was solved by a Danish-speaking hunter moving to the Danish-speaking group during workshop no. 2.

2.4. Notes and report

The groups' notes were compiled and subsequently sent out to the participants so that they could make additions. Two took the opportunity and submitted comments and additions. The groups did not give presentations to each other, but notes were circulated afterwards. One participant commented that it was good that the notes from the other groups were circulated. The optimal solution would have been to send transcripts of the recorded audio files to the participants, so that everyone could gain full insight into the dialogues of the other groups. Transcriptions had also been useful for report writing. Due to lack of resources, no transcriptions were prepared.

During the joint closing round in the joint forum, a wish was expressed that a report should be written with recommendations to be handed over to decision-makers in the municipality.

Researcher and project manager Kristine Lynge-Pedersen formulated a draft report. The draft was sent to participants, who were given the opportunity to make additions and comments, which are incorporated into this final version. The report was published on the Greenland Institute of Natural Resources website accompanied by a press release.

2.5. Joint gathering session at the start and end of workshop evening

Both workshops were held at the Greenland Institute of Natural Resources on Tuesday 22 and 28 September 2023, from 19-21:30. Both times there was a joint meeting at the start, where the facilitators gave a welcome speech and presented the evening's program, and a few questions were answered. A joint closing ceremony was also held, where participants in the joint forum could ask questions or comment.

Several participants handed out praise and compliments on the well-planned event, and some criticism was expressed, with one calling for more control of the group dialogue and one expressing having been influenced by project manager Kristine's visits to the group.

2.6. Press release and radio interviews

In connection with the sending of the invitation letter to stakeholders, a press release was issued. Journalist Frederik Lund from KNR radio responded and contacted researcher and project manager Kristine Lynge-Pedersen to do a radio interview. Kristine Lynge-Pedersen asked for accompaniment of participants from the workshop, as the purpose of the event was to put their voices into play and it is therefore important to get their voices on the air. Thus, tourist operator Miiti Geisler and Fisker & catcher Lars Mathæussen participated. Kristine talked about the design of the workshop and the purpose. Miiti and Lars explained why they wanted to participate in the workshop.

A follow-up radio interview was held when the two workshops were completed, where researcher and project manager Kristine talked about the process and briefly presented some of the results. Three workshop participants participated in the interview. Chairman Nikkulaat Jerimiassen from national organization KNAPK, civil servant Nuka Møller Lund from the Self-government's department of Hunting and Chairwoman Johanne Tobiassen from the nationwide Qaanaat Kattufia. The three participants mentioned what they had contributed in terms of messages and what they got out of the workshop.

Both radio interviews were broadcast on the radio program Eqqartortigut. The first radio interview was broadcast on Friday, August 25, and rebroadcast on August 27. The second radio interview was broadcast on September 4 and rebroadcast on September 10.

2.7. Evaluation of the design

The design of the workshop covered several needs. It was mentioned that there was a need for a cross-cutting dialogue, and it was the first time for many to participate in a public dialogue on future scenarios with a broadly composed topic. The holistic approach, with the topics of conversation; Tourism, culture, fishing and hunting, climate change and sustainable business development created a new and different lively dialogue.

The participants represented different areas of society and their insights, interests and needs helped to create a nuanced dialogue where new understandings were formed, new relationships were created, and new ideas were shaped.

The interests of the participants were, of course, reflected in their formulated scenarios. Had it been a different composition of participants, it would probably have given a different content to the scenario formulations.

Mutual respect and responsiveness dominated the group dialogues and discussions about who is right or wrong were largely absent from the dialogue.

The willingness to speak was extensive, but the meeting time short, so a wish was expressed for a continuation, and it was proposed that similar workshop be held on an ongoing basis, also in other cities.

One participant evaluated the workshop as follows: "I would like to commend you for introducing a method that has not been used before. You have put actors together for a dialogue that has not been done in the past. With respect and inclusiveness for what has been said, it is a fine arrangement".

Another participant evaluated the workshop as follows: " Thank you for the workshop and thank you for sharing all your work with us. The participants gathered at the workshop were new and different

from the tourism workshops I have attended, and it was an eye opener for me. Having hunters and the government at the same table was a refreshing experience. I have "known" and "felt" what the hunters are thinking and have tried to talk to my colleagues in the tourism industry about the hunting profession a few times, but talking to the hunters directly in this way was really good for me. I would love to participate again. Working across different industries is so important for our sustainable future. I keep my fingers crossed that one day you can also come to the smaller communities like Qaanaaq. Thank you for facilitating this conversation. It's not easy to "set something in motion" as in "that's the big part of the work" – not only for you, but also for the rest of us. I hope we keep in touch."

3. FUTURE SCENARIOS FROM WORKSHOPS 1 AND 2

The text below is a summary of the many views, wishes and ideas expressed in the group dialogues. The dialogues did not follow the dialogue forms slavishly, and as was expressed by several participants, the themes are naturally connected and were therefore difficult to mention individually. Some future scenarios therefore contain several topics of conversation.

In order to anonymize the participants, no senders are specified and rather no quotes have been included.

Some views or wishes were directly opposites, while others had the same message, but were simply formulated in other words. Contradictions were expressed in the fact that some participants are positive about the opportunity scenario with foreign investors and the introduction of international tourism concepts, while others prefer Greenlandic ownership and culture-based Greenlandic tourism concepts. Thus, opinions are divided on investment issues, with some seeing foreign investment as a necessary opportunity, while others see it as a threat to the local anchorage of the tourism industry. Both external investment funds and local Greenlandic ownership are desirable, so it is likely that (tourism) development will take shape from the two divergent directions.

Desired scenarios about the local culture were expressed in different words and phrases. Whether it was about revitalizing elements from the original Inuit culture or further developing modern Greenlandic culture, many formulations contain a desire for the future of a country with a strong culture and a people with a proud identity.

Business as usual matters were discussed in limited terms and are therefore not mentioned in the summary. Likewise, realization initiatives were not always mentioned in relation to wish scenarios, but where a formulated wish scenario may well be interpreted as a realization measure/initiative. For example, a wish was formulated for the government to create loan facilities for local Greenlanders in order to ensure a locally anchored tourism industry. This wording can equally be perceived as a realisation measure/initiative to ensure local anchorage of the tourism industry.

Many began their statements by saying that it is important to safeguard and protect nature and culture, and a widespread desire was expressed for tourism to be locally anchored with local residents as important drivers. These shared values had an impact on the group dialogue.

The lively group dialogues were widespread, and this meant that the dialogue topics for workshop 1 and workshop 2 were articulated during both workshops. Wish scenarios were expressed during both workshops 1 and 2, just as threat scenarios were expressed at both workshops.

Opportunity scenarios and wish scenarios

Local tourism

1) Broad support for holistic tourism development

The participants have a common interest in the development of tourism. Both in Nuuk, but also in the rest of the country. Many were concerned that nature and culture were adequately protected, and several product development opportunities were also addressed. However, it was striking that the talk about product development, job creation and new income opportunities was linked to cultural and natural considerations.

Accusations that the other party is too unnuanced because he or she is either strongly concerned with, for example, income opportunities or nature conservation can threaten good coexistence and holistic development. Therefore, there is also an appeal for a balanced, equal and holistic approach, where economic, natural and environmental, social and cultural considerations are given equal weight. However, the desire for a balanced balance between the various considerations was supplemented by dubious and worrying shakes.

2) Year schedule of tourist activities – when and where

Several expressed a wish that a well-coordinated year schedule should be developed with overviews of various tourist activities, which should be organized in a way that ensures good coexistence between the different actors. For example, there is no hiking tourism in the locals' favourite hunting grounds during the hunting season. Tourist activities are organized based on seasonal weather conditions to create year-round tourism. For example, snow-based tourist activities are offered during the winter season. The diverse local culture is used much more and cultural and art activities are offered both to a local audience and tourists. A culture-based tourism industry will improve the economic conditions of cultural operators and artists. The local fishing and hunting industry is also integrated into the tourism industry as a supplier of fresh food to eateries and offers fishing and hunting trips. Food tourism and cultural events are enjoyed by locals and tourists alike. A year schedule with experience offers that are aligned and coordinated with other business activities and local Greenlanders' use of resource areas.

Local original or first users of nature need overviews of tourist activities so that they can be prepared for additional activity in the immediate area. This also for security reasons.

3) Joint coordinated cruise tourism and other tourist activities

Planning of cruise tourism takes place in consultation with other nature and fjord/land users, especially Greenlandic fishermen and hunters. The Government of Greenland establishes a working group across relevant areas and interest groups and relevant actors, where cruise tourism and other tourist activities are coordinated and regulated annually.

4) High-quality dissemination manuals

Local people with local knowledge are invited in working groups so that together they can prepare dissemination manuals, so that authentic and high-quality stories about nature, the environment and culture can be told by guides and other tourist operators. The local community also benefits from these high-quality dissemination products.

5) Tourism Act

From several positions in society, the desire for a new tourism act is expressed, as a supplement to the existing legislation and signed conventions. It created joy and hopes when it was announced that

the Self-Government is in the process of developing a new tourism act. Several appealed to the new law to ensure locally anchored tourism that is gentle and protects nature and culture.

6) Tax and fee arrangements

Tax is introduced on admission to the country. This will also have an impact on who will visit the country. Genuinely interested and considerate tourists are supposed to be willing to pay the entrance fee.

In relation to the desired scenario with an entrance fee, it was briefly discussed whether instead of entrance fee high-quality experience products should be developed at high prices. Both efforts are desirable.

There is also a widespread desire for additional taxes to be imposed on cruise tourism. Taxes must help cover the development and maintenance of infrastructure, nature and culture.

7) Restriction of tourism and zoning of the country:

A widespread wish scenario is that tourist activities are restricted, and areas of movement are also limited. Among other things, in the form of zoning of the country, where zones are designated for tourist activities, zones that are exempt from tourist activities and zones for multi-activities with good coexistence between different resource users. The proposed nationwide, involving, work on the designation and mapping of the different zones can be used in municipal management plans.

Conservation measures were also mentioned as an opportunity to protect special or vulnerable natural conditions. In relation to protected land areas such as the Unartoq hot springs in South Greenland, one can consider whether the surrounding fjord should also be protected.

8) Community dialogue on how favourite areas for traditional use should be accessed

If locals' favourite hunting and fishing areas are to be used for e.g. hunting or fishing tourism, then the wish scenario is that you should start by involving the local original/first users of the area and inquire if they want to supplement their use of the area and start offering hunting or fishing trips? The original/first local users can be trained to serve tourists if they have an interest in, for example, hunting and fishing tourism. It is important to approach the areas used by the locals with respect for the original/first users.

Some say that locals misunderstand the concession concept, while others say that new tourism operators do not respect and involve the original/first users in development initiatives. Regardless, there is a need for a community dialogue on how to deal when new actors want to use favourite areas for new tourist activities, even though the areas have been favoured by local original/first users for generations.

9) Control and monitoring

There is a call for monitoring of tourist activities and more control and management of tourist flows. In that relation, it is mentioned that the country's large geographical size, with its small monitoring authority, makes it problematic to monitor the geographically dispersed tourist activities.

10) Loan options for locals to ensure local anchoring of tourism

Today, many Greenlanders interested in tourism are without start-up capital. A desire was expressed for the public authorities to create good framework conditions for local residents, in order to

provide local ownership and culture-based authentic tourism development. Specifically, loan options without pledge or collateral were proposed.

In the anchoring dialogue, it was further discussed how to use certification concepts that support authentic culture carriers – permanent indigenous local Greenlanders – without it becoming an ethnic issue. A certification to support the prefer of including of local Greenlanders in tourism development.

11) Spread the tourist flow and spread the earnings to many

A wish was expressed that the tourist flow should be spread throughout the country and that income opportunities should be spread to many actors. It should not only be in Ilulissat and Nuuk that individual boat owners should earn big on fjord sailing by cruise tourists.

The desire to spread also concerns an attempt to avoid a tourist boom and mass tourism in small communities as well as rapid wear and tear on material infrastructure and other public service units.

12) Diverse culture

There is broad agreement that action must be taken to both preserve and restore some values and traditions from the original Inuit culture and at the same time to develop the dynamic modern Greenlandic culture. The diverse Greenlandic culture will flourish and stand stronger, and the intergenerational knowledge and experience transfer will be carried out in families and between residents and newcomers.

Some tourists demand the genuine original Greenland, and this can be met by local tourist operators offering experience elements that are based on both the Inuit culture and the modern Greenlandic culture. There is a desire to accommodate both the conservatives and the modern in the stories about Greenland, both in terms of marketing and in experience offers. The new narratives must flourish, starting from the roots.

However, there is a displeasure in foreign media portraying Greenland and its population as the noble wild descendants of Inuit culture. There is a desire for foreign media to present a more diverse picture of today's Greenland.

The local Greenlandic culture

A desirable future scenario describes a development where the economic revenue needs are met in harmony with Greenlandic cultural values and traditions. External investors and tourism actors will play an active role. International tourism concepts will be introduced, but authentic Greenlandic tourism concepts will be preferred by both local and external tourism operators and future tourists. External tourism operators integrate and root their tourism activities in the local community and recognise cultural values.

13) Strengthening the diverse Greenlandic culture

There is a common interest in using and strengthening the Greenlandic culture, both the original Inuit culture and the modern Greenlandic culture in the tourism industry, but also regardless of the tourism industry.

Inuit culture must be a subject in primary school and the learning objectives are both increased knowledge and practice skills in some of the Inuit culture's most important survival skills, such as the use of seal and qajaq and skills in preparing local food in the form of smoking and drying. Elements from the Inuit culture is considered obvious experiences for both locals and tourists. A wish was also expressed to introduce (husky) sled dogs and dog sledding in Nuuk.

14) Skind sewing houses

By 2035, several popular leather sewing rooms have been established and there is a high demand for leather clothing for everyday use. Traditional cooking methods and skills in skin sewing have been revitalized in collaboration with Inuit kinsmen in Canada. There will continue to be sewing of national costumes.

15) Artists and cultural actors will be key players in the tourism industry

Cultural associations are often contacted by tourist operators who inquire whether the association can convey Greenlandic culture to tourist groups. Of course, this must be paid for, every time. Cultural associations are already in dire straits and need mutually rewarding collaborations.

There is common agreement that existing cultural institutions, cultural actors and artists must be involved in a structured way in tourism development. There must be more theatrical performances, more art exhibitions, more storytelling evenings, more food events, etc. for both tourists and locals. Artists can contribute to the development of signs and other types of information products.

The colonial harbour is considered an obvious cultural gathering place and there is a desire for a new Visitor Center, where the many tourist activities are advertised, and the place can also be used for cultural events.

The maintenance of cultural elements and the Greenlandic language requires protective measures to be applied. It is encouraged that culture-based development is ensured through legislation and certifications.

16) Tourism as a subject and more tourism education

If future generations are going to establish roots in the tourism industry, tourism subjects must be introduced in primary and secondary education. More tourism courses must also be developed, including lessons on product development, planning and logistics, etc., to ensure that young people occupy important positions in the tourism sector.

In addition, tourism operators need to carry out more initiatives with knowledge and experience transfer between older and younger tourism operators to ensure continuity of well-established tourism capacity.

17) Community dialogue on how new drivers affect locals ways of life

Some are more positive and open to new (business) opportunities, while others want to protect existing ways of life and revitalize some cultural values and traditions. Regardless of whether you are a supporter of one or the other, there is widespread agreement that the use of nature will continue to be a natural part of the way of life.

With the new global drivers such as new business opportunities and new weather conditions, Greenlandic society must be clear with itself, as a country and as a people, what it is ready to renounce and what needs to be done to preserve important parts of the culture, ways of life and natural conditions. There is an urgent need for a social dialogue on how new external drivers affect living conditions and how the population should relate to these.

Local hunting and fishing

A widespread desired scenario is that the local hunting and fishing industry will continue to be an important culture-based industry in Nuuk by 2035. During both workshops, a widespread desire was

expressed that fishing and fishing areas should be respected and not disturbed by tourist activities.

18) Professional structural conditions strengthen the local hunting and fishing industry

The desired scenario is that a structure and improved framework conditions have been found which support the hunting and fishing industry. Improved structural conditions, including a professional and veterinary-approved purchasing point for rough processing of fresh raw materials will strengthen the local hunting and fishing industry and make it attractive to younger generations. The facility is to be located on the site opposite the current marketplace. A professional trading place for the rough processing of fresh raw food will support the development of trade agreements with local eateries that prioritize menus with seasonal Greenlandic dishes.

A future scenario is that Greenlanders and local newcomers who today prefer to eat international dishes or have grown up with non-Greenlandic dishes will find it valuable and attractive to eat reintroduced Greenlandic dishes in 2035. Of course, there will be international food dishes, but dishes based on local ingredients are preferred.

There is great potential for development in food tourism, and the fishing and hunting industry will be a well-regarded important partner in this development. Another possible scenario is that local fishermen and hunters supply raw materials to the cruise ships, and local chefs serve Greenlandic dishes on board the cruise ships. The third possible scenario is that the local coastal fishing and hunting industry enters into new trade cooperation, which takes advantage of the new export opportunities that will arise when the international airport in Nuuk comes into operation.

19) Increased equal cooperation with fishermen and hunters

There will be space and respect for the different professions and constructive solutions will be found so that no profession is restricted because of another priority profession. There is and always will be a deep respect for fishing and hunting traditions, and despite developments and new ways of life, hunting and fishing will continue to be a natural part of the locals way of life.

Commercial fishermen and hunters have a valuable knowledge of nature and traditional forms of use. Some new tour operators ask up to e.g. the whales' whereabouts to develop whale watching. But when hunters ask for payment for the shared valuable knowledge, the operators turn their backs. This is unacceptable and professional, reciprocal and equal working relationships must be developed.

20) The municipality's fishing plan

The year-long planning of the municipality's fishing plan is implemented by 2035.

Climate change

21) Increased consumption of local foods

In the global climate discussion and Nordic forums, there is an appeal for increased consumption of local food and less imports of long-distance transported (CO2 emissions) food. These trends will strengthen the Greenlandic food tradition and the use of local ingredients.

Less sea ice and year-round tourism

Previously, it was not possible to sail Kapisillit all year round due to winter sea ice. Today, however, Kapisillit is navigable all year round, which means that year-round tourism can be developed. The future scenario is that year-round tourism in Kapisillit and the fjord will be the draw for developing year-round tourism in the city of Nuuk.

Sustainable and regenerative business development

Considerate use of nature and culture can be understood in many ways. Some want the relatively untouched nature to be preserved and tourism to be restricted, and where, for example, nature clean-up projects are carried out with tourists. Other players want to introduce new tourist activities and see many potentials in nature use and resource utilisation and focus on product development with inspiration from other countries.

In the nuanced group dialogues, opportunity scenarios were formulated with a particular focus on a balance between exploitation and preservation of natural and cultural conditions.

22) Not only sustainable but also regenerative

Tourism must not only be developed in a sustainable way, with a focus on gentle use of resources, job creation and new revenue opportunities. Tourism must also have a regenerative effect on both culture and nature. For example, the tourism industry can use reintroduced revitalised cultural values and traditions from the Inuit culture. In relation to nature and natural resources, tourism operators can arrange nature restoration projects with tourists.

23) Expensive travel destination targeted adventure tourists

Greenland has a large food pantry both at sea and on land, so nature must be taken care of. It must therefore be expensive to travel to the country. In this way, we avoid mass tourism and attract the segment group we want – adventure tourists who are nature- and culture-friendly.

Threat scenarios

Local tourism

24) Lack of regulation, coordination and overview of tourist activities

Several of the participants expressed concern about the current situation of lack of regulation and control over the rapidly increasing tourist activities, which are carried out by external operators who are not knowledgeable about Greenland. Lack of joint coordination leads to clashes of different activities in certain land or fjord areas. A lack of a publicly available overview creates unexpected situations. Lack of regulation and monitoring of the rapidly increasing tourist activities was referred to as risky and that it is only a matter of time, then environmentally polluting accidents will occur and, in the worst case, personal injuries.

25) Opening the country to foreign investors

It was expressed that it is perceived that Greenland is being opened up more to foreign investors and that outside actors are invited to "a big self-service table". At both workshops, the desire for increased regulation, limitation and control of tourist activities was expressed repeatedly and with various concrete proposals such as; tax importation, zoning of the country, joint coordinated development.

And actors at the various levels of society were encouraged to take a more critical view of global drivers and how local communities and ways of life are affected by these external drivers.

26) Local anchorage or spectator of the development

If the upcoming tourism legislation does not prioritize anchoring the tourism industry in the form of local ownership, then development opportunities will be given to foreign investors and players who come with their international concepts and run away with the profits. If that becomes the scenario,

the tourism industry will create powerlessness among the local Greenlandic population, as they will be in a spectator position to a rapid development controlled by external driving forces.

The expression of a desire for a locally anchored tourist industry is not the same as being inhospitable and averse to foreign actors. It is an expression of a desire to protect nature, the environment and Greenlandic culture. And a desire for tourism to benefit Greenland and its residents. The tourism industry must contribute to the good life in the local community. It was pointed out that this is not a particularly Greenlandic wish, and that similar wishes for local anchorage and meaningful tourism are a trend in many other countries.

27) Rapid pace of development will risk pushing local anchorage aside

The pace of development was reported with divided opinions. Some appealed for rapid capacity development, preferably in cooperation with foreign investors, so that the Nuuk destination can be ready to receive the expected many tourists when the new international airport is ready. Others appealed for a cautious and adapted pace of development, where legislation ensures local anchorage and good framework conditions for Greenlanders. The pace of development should be adjusted to balance these opposing wishes and needs are balanced.

The local Greenlandic culture

28) From an embarrassed people to a proud people

In the cultural dialogue, negative aspects were also mentioned. Some Greenlanders are ashamed of their cultural identity and being Greenlandic and seek recognition from outsiders. If these Greenlanders leave this negative self-image, then self-respect will arise and insight into the Greenlandic culture will flourish. Instead of internal divisions, it is a wish that local Greenlanders develop mutual trust in each other and establish constructive cooperative relations.

Alongside building a strong and proud people, it is still important to have a view out to the rest of the world, as Greenland is not the navel of the world.

29) Unique handicraft products or mass-produced souvenirs

Artists who perform unique handmade works of art and handicrafts work under poor and unhealthy framework conditions that endanger the preservation and development of high-quality art and cultural products. The threat scenario is that mass-produced cheap souvenirs from the East are chosen if Greenlandic artists are not recognized, supported and integrated into the tourism industry.

Local hunting and fishing

30) Catch and fishing quotas and bans can have unintended consequences

Attention must be paid to the consequences of fishing and hunting quotas and periodic bans on cultural eating habits. Young people do not learn to eat the protected species. For example, many young people do not know about eider or humpback whales and have not tasted them, as they have been protected for a number of years.

31) From hunting to halibut fishing and now what?

Many hunters have moved from the hunting profession to halibut fishing in a short period of time, and are we now going to see that local fisherman, or their descendants, opting out of the fishing industry and opting for the tourist industry? When we choose our new path, what we opt out of "drown". We have already seen that we can easily leave our traditional way of life. External drivers

easily penetrate everyday life, but how can we be better at adapting the changed conditions to our cultural values and desired way of life?

Many announced that the tourist industry should not be targeted as the country's future mainstay industry. The tourist industry must be complementary to the main industry fishing and must therefore be carried out in a nature and environmentally friendly manner. Because if the tourist industry is not enough (success), we will not manage to survive by eating our few earned dollars and pennies. And if we no longer have pure nature, then we have nothing to survive on.

The downside of the rapid development in Nuuk is that some youth groups do not get out into nature. Do not go hunting, fishing and berry picking. Young populations that do not have the opportunity to learn to gather resources in nature are a point of attention that needs to be taken care of.

32) We do not own, but borrow the right to use land and fjord areas

Some Greenlandic families believe that they have a claim on a certain land or fjord area, because they have come to the favoured area for generations to collect food supplies. In other areas, new tourist activities are carried out and where some, both external and local tourist operators behave as owners or have first rights to the use of these land and fjord areas. This form of owner-oriented interaction with nature does not harmonize with the principle of collective common ownership of the land and natural resources.

Everyone, both external/newcomers and local users of nature, should participate in a public dialogue on how the principle of collective joint ownership of the land and its natural resources should be understood and adhered to, otherwise the users of natural resources will not have a common understanding, common approach and common accepted practices.

If the tourist industry's use of natural resources (land and fjord areas) is prioritized and weighted higher than the indigenous peoples' use of nature for traditional activities, then there is a risk that elements from the original Inuit culture will be disregarded and, in the worst case, left behind and lost. There is a need for a public dialogue on how ILO Convention 169 on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples should be understood and complied with, when decisions are to be made about the use of natural resources and when Indigenous Peoples' ways of life are affected by changed forms of use and other changes. (Local hunters and fishermen and other locals whose way of life or business practices are based on elements of the Inuit Indigenous culture).

33) Lack of reciprocal considerations will create conflicts of interest

Some see good opportunities in creating synergy and cooperative relations between the local fishing and hunting industry and the tourism industry. Both professions use the same resource base, and if resource use is not coordinated considerably, conflicts of interest can easily arise. The trick will be to organise the various activities in such a way as to create good coexistence between the original and culture-carriers users and the new tourist operators.

The choice of stakeholders, in an involvement process, must be everyone who is affected/will be affected by the development initiative, and therefore has a stake in the initiative. New initiators/initiators/entrepreneurs are important, but affected parties are equally important in an involving development process.

34) The Navy's unnecessary navigation in the fjord

The Navy's ships carry out noise pollution, which can cause disturbances on marine animals. As there is no (safe) reason for the Navy's sailing in Nuup Kangerlua, this should be stopped.

Climate change

No threat scenarios regarding climate change were formulated.

Sustainable business development

35) Waste in nature

The increasing tourist activity leaves waste in different ways and in different quantities. From toilet paper along walking routes and ballast water from cruise ships, to CO2 emissions from both air and sea traffic. In addition, there is underdeveloped municipal infrastructure, where several settlements have neither standardized environmentally friendly waste management nor sewerage, and locum bags are disposed in primitive manner. There is a widespread desire for all actors to try to reduce waste generation and increased use of mitigation measures, and for waste management to be done in an environmentally friendly way.

3.1. SUMMARY OF FUTURE SCENARIOS

The design of the workshop

The design covered several needs: The participants mentioned that the cross-cutting dialogues with complex topics were needed, as it created a new, nuanced, and holistic dialogue. The language consideration, where the participants could speak their preferred language, created lively participation and flow in the dialogue. The meeting time was short and several called for more similar cross-cutting social dialogues, also in other settlements.

Local tourism

By law, tourism development must be managed and locally anchored: The Tourism Act must ensure locally anchored authentic tourism. Based on the Tourism Act, tourist activities are regulated so that they are carried out in a safe and nature- and culture-friendly manner. The law ensures control of the development, and the supervisory authority carries out supervision of tourist activities, in order to reduce risky conditions.

Taxation: Different types of taxes are to be introduced for the development and restoration of infrastructure, culture and nature.

Holistic and equitable approach: Tourism development must take a holistic approach in which economic, nature and environmental, social and cultural considerations are treated equally. Tourism development balances between cultural conservation and cultural development, as well as nature conservation and nature exploitation. In this way, a tourism industry is created that promotes healthy environments and creates good lives.

Foreign investors and local owners: Capacity development with foreign investment is necessary and welcomed, at the same time good framework conditions must be created, e.g. in the form of loan opportunities for local Greenlanders in order to create locally-owned tourism industries. Actors at all levels must take a critical look at how new drivers affect the local community.

Adjusted pace of development: Foreign investors are ready to participate in capacity development of the tourism sector, local interested parties call for more supportive framework conditions to ensure

locally-owned tourism industry. The pace of development should be adjusted to balance these opposing wishes and needs.

Dispersed development: Spread the flow of tourists out into the country to avoid the tourist boom and mass tourism in the small communities. Spread the earnings to many so that it benefits the local community.

National Organisation for Tourism: Tourism operators should set up a national organisation of tourism operators to ensure a community-integrated tourism industry. A national organization with underlying local branches that accommodate and coordinate the interests and needs of different actors. The organization has both one common voice and several voices, depending on the situation.

Coordinated annual cycle/overview: A well-coordinated annual cycle with various tourist activities must be developed, which ensures good coexistence between different resource users and business activities. Tourist activities must be organised according to seasonal weather conditions in order to generate year-round tourism. The Annual Cycle/Overview is publicly available, so everyone can get an overview of where and when tourist activities are carried out. This is also for security reasons.

Working groups to regulate cruise and other activities: Coordination and regulation of cruise tourism and other tourism activities is carried out in consultation with various stakeholders, to ensure good coexistence and nature- and culture-friendly tourism. Authorities shall establish working groups across relevant areas of authority and relevant stakeholder organisations and relevant actors.

Zoning and mapping: In order to ensure nature- and culture-friendly tourism, the number of tourist activities is limited and traffic areas are restricted. Among other things, in the form of zoning of the country, designating a) zones for tourist activities, b) zones that are exempt from tourist activities and c) zones for multi-activities with good coexistence between different resource users. In addition, d) locals' use of favourite land and fjord areas for traditional activities must be mapped and described. The mapping work with descriptions of the zones is carried out with broad stakeholder involvement. The mapping of the different zones can be used in municipal management plans.

Working groups for dissemination manuals: It is recommended that working groups consisting of knowledge persons be set up for the preparation of dissemination manuals. This is to ensure authentic and high-quality information about the culture, nature and environment.

Competence building: Tourism subjects and more tourism educations such as logistics must be established to ensure that Greenland's youth competently occupy important positions in tourism development. Knowledge and experience transfer is carried out between older and younger tourism operators in order to provide continuity of well-established tourism capacity.

The local Greenlandic culture

Culture protection measures and certification concepts: Apply measures to strengthen both Inuit culture and modern Greenlandic culture. Introduce certification concepts to support the use of authentic culture carriers in the development of a culture-based tourism industry. This must be practiced in a way that does not become an ethnic issue.

The cultural sector is integrated into the tourism industry: professional cooperation agreements with payment arrangements are established between the cultural sector and the tourism industry. Cultural institutions, cultural associations, cultural actors and artists develop more and new experiences based on both Inuit culture and modern Greenlandic culture. Both tourists and locals enjoy these experiential offerings. The diversity of culture is strengthened and flourishes because the cultural sector is integrated into the tourism industry. The culture-based tourism industry strengthens the population as a proud people with a strong culture.

Gathering places and gathering building: Use the colonial harbor as a cultural gathering place and create a Visitor Center where tourist activities are advertised.

Fur and leather sewing houses and fur and leather clothing: There is a desire to establish more fur sewing houses with good framework conditions to strengthen the preservation of the national costume and support the development of fur and leather clothing for everyday wear. Additional support schemes ensure the revitalisation of traditional skills in fur and leather treatment and sewing. Possibly in collaboration with Inuit kinsmen from Canada.

Unique handicrafts or mass-produced souvenirs: Artists who perform unique handmade works of art and handicrafts products must be recognized and their framework conditions improved. Handicrafts are in demand by locals and tourists alike, and by 2035 they will continue to be of high cultural importance to both locals and tourists. Otherwise, there is a risk that the souvenir shops of the future will have to import mass-produced cheap souvenirs from the East.

Inuit culture as a school subject: Inuit culture must be a subject in primary school and the learning objectives are both increased knowledge and practical skills in some of the Inuit culture's most important survival skills, such as the use of qajaq and the preparation of seal and other raw food in the form of smoking and drying. It is important to strengthen the identity of young people based on the roots.

In addition, there is a desire to introduce (husky) sled dogs and dog sledding in Nuuk.

Public dialogue on desirable way of life(s): With the new business opportunities, Greenlandic society must be clear with itself, as a country and as a people, about what it is ready to renounce and what needs to be done to preserve important parts of the culture, ways of life and natural conditions. Therefore, more public dialogues need to be held on this in order to find common areas for action.

Local hunting and fishing

Uplifting structural features: The local hunting and fishing industry, like the cultural sector, must be integrated into the tourist industry as an important player. Equal cooperative relationships with payment schemes must be established. Both the cultural sector and the hunting and fishing industry will have improved structural conditions that support and strengthen their activities and development opportunities.

A professional and veterinary-approved handling/procurement point shall be set up for the rough processing of fresh food. The improved structural conditions make the industry attractive to younger generations and the conditions will support stable trade agreements with eateries, and the local fishing and hunting industry plays an important role in the development of food tourism and the revitalization of traditional food dishes. The local fishing industry can supply raw food to the cruise ships, and local chefs can prepare and serve Greenlandic dishes on board. Furthermore, new fish trade agreements based on aircraft exports can be developed when the international airport becomes operational.

Climate change

Locally produced food rather than imported: The local community must take an active part in the global climate discussion about less imports of long-distance transported food (transport with CO2 emissions) and respond by preferring climate-friendly locally produced food or local raw food from the new professional marked place.

Constructive adaptation solutions: Changing local weather conditions such as less sea ice opens up for year-round sailing and the opportunity to develop year-round tourism in Kapisillit. Such constructive adaptability must be cultivated.

Sustainable and regenerative business development

Exploitation and restoration of nature and culture: Tourism must not only be developed in a sustainable way, with a focus on gentle use of resources, job creation and new new earning opportunities. Tourism must also have a regenerative effect on both culture and nature. For example, the tourism industry can use reintroduced and revitalised cultural values and traditions from Inuit culture in experience offers. In relation to nature and natural resources, tourism operators can arrange nature restoration projects with tourists.

More new community dialogues

New public dialogues will be held on:

- 1) how external drivers affect local living conditions and what needs to be done to preserve important parts of culture, ways of life and natural conditions.
- 2) how to deal with land and fjord areas favoured by local indigenous users, if these areas come into play for tourist activities.
- 3) how the principle of collective common ownership of the land and its natural resources is to be understood and complied with, otherwise the users of natural resources will not have a common understanding, common approach and common accepted practices.
- 4) how the rights of indigenous peoples (ILO Convention 169) are to be understood and complied with when making decisions about the use of natural resources that will have consequences on indigenous peoples' ways of life - The local hunters and fishermen or other local Greenlanders whose way of life or business practices are based on elements of the Indigenous Inuit culture.

4. CONCLUSION

The research activity with future workshop was referred to by the majority of participants as needed and successful because it consisted of a new design with;

- Composite groups across areas of society
- Language considerations where participants could speak in their preferred language
- New and different composition of topics of conversation
- Focus on group dialogue and no time-consuming presentations

The results from the two workshops are manifold;

- The lively and nuanced group dialogue is a fine result in itself
- The participants shared their experiences and knowledge in the group dialogue. They let their different insights, experiences and interests meet, and with these nuanced understandings, creative ideas and broad solutions were created. In addition, new acquaintances and new burgeoning cooperative relationships were formed.
- The 35 formulated future scenarios are both holistic and simple, abstract and concrete.

The participants must therefore be greatly thanked for their lively participation and valuable contribution. KNR's radio journalist Frederik Lund must also be thanked for covering the the future workshop with two radio interviews. Five participants from the workshop participated in the radio interviews and with their distinctive messages they helped create a socially relevant radio feature.

Last but not least, we thank the co-facilitators Evi Kreutzmann, Sørine Steenholdt and Thora M. Hansen for facilitating the group dialogues in an inclusive and dialogue-promoting way.

6.

Coexistence between natural resource-based industries in Varangerfjord

ArcticHubs project (<https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs>)

Varanger scenarios by Audun Iversen, Roy Robertsen, Katrine Eriksen and Anja Striberny

Table of contents:

Background	2
Varangerfjord HUB	2
Framing of the Varangerfjord scenario process	4
Involvement of different stakeholders	5
Material for the scenario construction	6
Workshop material.....	7
Utilization of the workshop and survey material	8
Scenario table	9
Scenario narratives	16
Scenario 1: Green growth	16
Scenario 2: Arctic Urbanity	17
Scenario 3: The Traditionalist trap	18
Scenario 4: Blue desert	19
Scenario 5: Emerging Coexistence	20
Conclusions	22

Background

The ArcticHubs project, coordinated by the Natural Resources Institute of Finland and funded by the EU (<https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs/>), aims to develop sustainable solutions for harmonizing competing industries and land use practices in Arctic central locations, known as 'hubs,' and their surrounding environments. This project also considers the cultural aspects of indigenous populations, such as the Saami in Fennoscandia and the Inuit in Greenland. The project focuses on key economic activities in the Arctic region, including mining, aquaculture, tourism, and forestry. These industries hold significant societal and economic value in the region, and the project also analyzes how they impact ecosystem services and the well-being of local communities. The ArcticHubs project involves participatory foresight work for a total of seven specified hubs to assess future opportunities, threats, and strategies for preparing for the future.

Varangerfjord HUB

The fish farming hub in northern Norway is Varangerfjord. Varangerfjord is part of Troms & Finnmark County. There are 4 municipalities in Varangerfjord HUB populated with 18 240 inhabitants (in 2023). The municipalities are Sør-Varanger, Vadsø, Vardø and Nesseby. The Varangerfjord (Northern Sami: Várjavuonna, Kven: Varenkinvuono, Finnish: Varanginvuono) is the easternmost fjord in Norway. The fjord is located in Troms og Finnmark county between the Varanger Peninsula and the mainland of Norway. The fjord flows through the municipalities of Vardø, Vadsø, Nesseby, and Sør-Varanger. The fjord is approximately 95 kilometers long, emptying into the Barents Sea. Its mouth is about 70 kilometers wide, located between the town of Vardø in the northwest and the village of Grense Jakobselv in the southeast. In the Varanger hub we find the only municipality in Norway within the strict definition of an Arctic climate (the region North of the 10 °C summer isotherm, where average daily summer temperatures in the warmest month do not exceed 10 °C).

The biggest municipality in the Varangerfjord HUB is Sør-Varanger with 9850 inhabitants, followed by Vadsø (5593), Vardø (1933) and Nesseby with 864 inhabitants (Statistics Norway, 2023). An important backdrop is the demographic situation, with population decline and an aging population.

Figure 1 Population development in municipalities in Varangerfjord. Source: SSB (Statistics Norway)

The number of companies in the municipalities differ from around 150 in Nesseby to over thousand in Sør-Varanger. In terms of company structure, Nesseby and Vardø have more companies in agriculture, forestry and fishing (where fishing is dominant). Sør-Varanger and Vadsø have a more diverse company structure. By 2020 there were 728 employees working in aquaculture in Finnmark. The aquaculture value change includes smolt (juvenile) production, grow out production, and slaughtering and processing of Atlantic salmon. In the Varangerfjord HUB the main activity is in Sør-Varanger municipality, which hosts 48 workers. Vadsø and Nesseby municipalities have 2 and 3 workers, respectively. Lerøy Aurora Ltd owns and operates farming and processing related to aquaculture in Varangerfjord.

Conditions are generally good for salmon aquaculture in Varanger, with low temperatures in the winter compensated by ideal temperatures and long daylight in summer. Farmers have achieved good results, with low mortality and limited problems with lice and disease. The carrying capacity¹ of sites are relatively low though, due to relatively shallow waters and moderately strong currents. The result is a, depending on the location, low water exchange rate that in turn leads to an accumulation of organic material from fish faeces and uneaten feed below the net pen. The bacterial decomposition of such organic material decreases the amount of available oxygen in the water, and under anoxic conditions sulphate is reduced to toxic H₂S gas. To prevent and control these negative impacts in net-pen aquaculture

¹ By carrying capacity we here refer to the ability to produce a given quantity without deteriorating water quality below threshold levels, as indicated in Figure 2

production, regular monitoring of bottom sediments are required by the Norwegian law. With low carrying capacity at each site, more sites are needed to produce a given quantity.

Figure 2 Results from trend monitoring of bottom conditions under and in the immediate vicinity of aquaculture facilities in Varangerfjord (scale: 1= very good, 2=good, 3=bad, 4=very bad). Source: Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries.

Framing of the Varangerfjord scenario process

This is a draft version of Varanger scenarios conducted by three main sources of gathered data: A PPGIS-survey reached 412 people in the region, there were two wider audience workshops held, in Bugøyenes in May 2022 and in Kirkenes in June 2023, while a scenario shaping workshop were held in Kirkenes in November 2023, followed by interviews with stakeholders not able to attend.

The foresight process thus consisted of four phases. First, in the Bugøyenes workshop, factors and drivers influencing the future of the area was identified, with views presented from both researchers and stakeholders. In the Kirkenes workshop, results from the PPGIS survey was also presented and discussed. In the scenario shaping workshop all drivers identified in workshops and survey was discussed, the most significant drivers of change were prioritized, and their future directions were discussed. The research team then drafted scenario outlines, which were further refined based on the feedback received (Figure 1).

Figure 3 Scenario process consisted of three phases.

Involvement of different stakeholders

Close to 50 people have participated in workshops and interviews during the process. This includes presentations, interviews and dialogue related to the scenario process.

Table 1 Number of stakeholders and background in workshops and interviews

Aquaculture producers	6
Business Consultancy	1
Business development agency	3
Communication	1
Directorate of Fisheries, Norway	2
Fishermen	3
Fishery producer	3
Fishing Tourism Business	1
Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries	1
Municipality stakeholder	4
Sami Diggi	5
Scientist	12
SeaSami NGO	1
Tourist agent	3

The main heading for the process has been **Coexistence between nature-based industries in the Arctic**. Different topics and perspectives have been presented and discussed during the process; these are the titles for talks given during the Bugøynes and Kirkenes workshops:

- The seafood industry in the north – coexistence a prerequisite for development
- Ripple effects from fisheries and aquaculture in Troms og Finnmark county
- Ripple effects of fishing tourism in Finnmark

- Global driving forces or Norwegian politics – what matters the most for business development in the Arctic, Finnmark and Varangerfjord?
- Seafood as a basis for development in Finnmark. How do new industries such as aquaculture and fishing tourism interact with established traditional activity, and what political challenges exist in a Norwegian and global perspective?
- Varangerfjord has been chosen as the HUB in our EU project Arctic Hubs – how to coexist and develop this?
- Coexistence and potential for aquaculture development in Varanger
- The importance and future of fisheries in Varanger
- Business development in Varanger – what do we do now?
- Coexistence between aquaculture, fisheries and fishing tourism – seen from the perspective of the Sami Parliament
- Coastal zone plan work – a basis for successful coexistence and coordinated use of the sea. Status of ongoing planning work in Varangerfjord
- How to acquire new knowledge – develop technology and create a win-win situation. Measurement of fish around facilities and new methods for catching this.
- Arctic Hubs – coexistence as a prerequisite for industry development
- The future of Arctic business development
- The war In Europe – What are the impacts on development in the Arctic region?
- Experiences from Varanger Municipalities on coastal planning processes
- Coexistence between traditional and new Industries in Varanger
- Pink Salmon - a new food resource in arctic Norway
- Global driving forces for Arctic development– what is most important for business development in the Arctic
- Indigenous business and activity in the future Arctic
- Arctic identity Lab
- How to coexist and develop this. Social License to operate (SLO) and Company Social Responsibility (CSR)
- The use of Public Participation GIS (PPGIS) – participation tool for public opinions Fisheries, aquaculture and tourism
- Future scenarios for business development the arctic areas, Eastern Finnmark (Varanger) and Lappland (Finland and Sweden) (45 min)

Material for the scenario construction

In this section we present some of the results from the **PPGIS survey**.

Workshop material

For scenario construction one key issue is to have enough divergence between scenarios in order for them to stimulate to further analysis, for instance conducting impact assessments of the various scenarios for the region. Thinking systematically about possible future developments may improve the understanding of what may shape our common future.

In the following the selected most significant drivers are interpreted as extreme outcomes.

	TOWARDS SUSTAINABILITY	TOWARDS UNSUSTAINABILITY
POLITICAL	Decision-making power locally/ regionally	External control
ECONOMIC	Economic stability	An economic crisis
SOCIAL	Positive population development	Rural exodus
TECHNOLOGICAL	Technology solves environmental issues	Traditional technology
ENVIRONMENTAL	A functioning ecosystem	Ecosystem collapse
LEGAL	Sámi land natural resources rights recognised	Sámi land natural resources rights ignored

Figure 5 Key drivers and their contrasting outcomes

Utilization of the workshop and survey material

Many of the statements in the PPGIS survey reflected the drivers identified. During the workshops a range of issues were raised. In the scenario table we have included (to the left) the most important drivers identified, either by the researchers, stakeholder or experts, and discussed. They are sorted after the PESTEL model.

Before moving on to the scenarios, we will present a common backdrop for all scenarios (also by the PESTEL model):

Political	Varanger is characterized by its position as a neighbour to Russia. Possibilities lie in a large export market and as a transport hub should the Northeast Passage become important. Development in South-Varanger was quite dependent on the Russian market. Now other possibilities are sought, where the development of aquaculture is one. Local decision-making versus central decisions.
Economical	Local economy lacks resilience, a trend of depopulation in Varanger. Small population, need of qualified workforce. Ripple effects from aquaculture are substantial in other regions in Norway.
Social	Aquaculture is an emerging industry in the area that may give opportunities, but triggers conflict. The future aquaculture development will be dependent on its social license to operate (SLO). Co-existence with other industries without conflict A negative demographic development has been identified as a key driver of the future development of Varanger fjord. Birthrates are decreasing in rural areas. Different municipalities are competing to attract people and industries (fisheries/processing/aquaculture, public sector, defence). Gender balance and age structure important indicators. Some municipalities in Norway struggle to attract aquaculture workers to "settle": commuting is common. Many young people are commuters.

Technological	Infrastructure needed to achieve green shift. Technological development to solve environmental problems and enable aquaculture growth. Trade-offs: expensive, space, and physical installations will have other type of impacts on the environment. Higher energy demands, more complex to operate. Possibilities to control remotely (workers replaced by machines). Architectural solutions needed.
Environmental	<p>The current average winter and summer sea temperatures in the production area 13 that includes Varanger fjord are 4 °C and 10-11 °C, respectively (Albretsen and Asplin, 2021).</p> <p>The Varangerfjord ecosystem is going to respond to environmental change and directly affect access to natural resources.</p> <p>Milder winters with higher temperatures lead to better growing conditions for salmon in the North, positively affecting aquaculture development in the Varanger hub, but simultaneously put more pressure on the coastal area. Eutrophication may become a problem with more aquaculture and a warmer climate. Ecosystem services depend on responses of seafood stocks to climate. Invasive species can become novel resources.</p>
Legal	<p>The right of public access remains an essential part of people's use of nature.. Norwegian legislations (The Aquaculture Act, The Food Safety Act, The marine resources act, The energy act)</p> <p>The municipalities will have less opportunities to decide on land use planning.</p> <p>The local economic benefit is emphasized in the use of natural resources.</p> <p>The ability to pay will determine which land use interests have priority.</p> <p>It is becoming more difficult to reconcile the demands of different livelihoods and stakeholders on natural resources.</p>

Scenario table

This chapter presents the futures table in which five scenarios are outlined. The key drivers selected during the scenario process are the base for the scenario contents. In the table, drivers are presented in the left column, sorted by the PESTEL framework. The outcome of each driver is described in the table for each scenario. All these drivers were considered when describing the possible future developments, but the different possible effects of a driver may result in different contributions to the different scenarios.

<p>Scenario names/headings</p> <p>Drivers:</p>	<p>Scenario 1</p> <p>Green growth</p>	<p>Scenario 2</p> <p>Arctic urbanity: (attracting young people, knowledge industries, culture)</p>	<p>Scenario 3</p> <p>The traditionalist trap</p>	<p>Scenario 4</p> <p>Blue desert: Loss of ecosystem services</p>	<p>Scenario 5</p> <p>Coexistence between aquaculture and fisheries</p>
<p>Political</p> <p>Local vs national power</p> <p>Market vs regulation</p> <p>Sami rights</p> <p>Geopolitics</p> <p>Trade policy</p> <p>EU legislations: Green Deal</p>	<p>Obtaining SLO in Varanger: Dialogue, knowledge seeking and sharing, communicate to build reputation</p> <p>EU legislation and strategies boost the Norwegian activity and legislation regarding the objective to zero emissions. The fishing-</p>	<p>Politicians make decisions on premises of the young people (tax relief, free kindergarden, remission of study debts)</p>	<p>Traditional fisheries prioritized. Sami rights important, rights to local coastal vessels</p>	<p>Moratorium on fishing and aquaculture; geopolitical conflicts persist</p>	<p>Local politics achieve a good balance in the planning process and facilitates dialog between the industries.</p> <p>Shift from reliance on eastern market to building a resilient local economy with local actors.</p>

and aquaculture industry makes progress.

The social licence to operate (SLO) activity have been successful and the aquaculture in Varanger expands and new sites and sea areas are open for production in coexistence with traditional and new fisheries.

<p>Economic</p> <p>Growth in</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aquaculture? - Fisheries? - Tourism? - Public sector? - Defense? <p>Local and global market (demand/supply)</p> <p>Recession</p> <p>Exchange rates</p>	<p>Major structural shift in aquaculture: diversification, new species, LTA</p> <p>Economic growth of aquaculture and associated technology providers are rising in Varanger due to demand of technology.</p>	<p>New industries (e.g. digital arts) emerge and are more attractive.</p> <p>Aquaculture growth as today (SQ), with ad hoc and limited response to environmental challenges</p>	<p>Fisheries continue to decline, increased number of fishermen, but with only small coastal vessels, catching primarily in high season, most of the catch is shipped further to Båtsfjord for processing</p> <p>Little aquaculture to replace lost jobs/reduced</p>	<p>Restriction of aquaculture activities due to lack of SLO and loss of market share.</p> <p>Collapse of fisheries.</p> <p>Varanger region mainly a military base.</p>	<p>Contribution of both industries to local economy.</p> <p>Economic growth through aquaculture technologies (e.g. sludge collection and re-use)</p> <p>Exploit synergy effect (e.g., slaughter at sea,</p>
--	---	---	--	--	---

Taxes
Access to capital

The salmon production is rising (20.000 metric tons), providing total of 200 employers. The ripple effects are substantial and creates a lot of indirect positive effects, like new inhabitants, new supplier companies, new schools and a demand for service institutions.

Tourism expands and fishing tourism are sustainable and regulated.

Fishery stocks in Varanger are stable and the king crab stocks is back to normal level (2020) and provides local revenue

aquaculture production. Slaughterhouse closed down due to limited activity, slaughtering by boat, landed and packed in Troms.

Stagnation/ declining economy

Some tourism? Based on sami storytelling? fishing industry linked to fishing tourism

Energy sector uses area to produce renewable energy
Varanger fjord no longer attractive for tourists

common export strategies for fish based on the local brand, processing facilities, bait for crab fishery?)

Few larger actors may be beneficial in terms of easier coordination.

	for fishermen with crab quota.				
Social	Education possibilities locally for fisheries and aquaculture with focus on co-existence	Cultural change: increased pride in the Arctic, in the Finnmark identity, the sami culture, the melting pot of the three traditional cultures. Also embracing the Russian and global influences from people coming to experience this	Reduced population. Base of the population pyramid severely narrowed due to missing of young people. Less people at work.	Depopulation lead to a closure of kindergardens, schools, public health service, and offers for freetime activities (sports, etc.) in rural areas. Kids are send to boarding schools.	Education possibilities locally for fisheries and aquaculture with focus on co-existence
Livelyhoods					
Demographics					
Education	Education possibilities and new technologies result in more attractive jobs for men and women		Gender misbalance; lack of women.		Strengthening local identity as seafood region. Fishing tourism destination (fishing at sea, in the rivers, exhibition center at aquaculture sites, learning about Sami fishing)
Health			Healthcare services struggling		
Culture/ identity					
Indigenous traditions					
Health services: quality and availability	Strengthening local identity as seafood region. Fishing tourism destination (fishing at sea, in the rivers, exhibition center at aquaculture sites,	Young people seek urbanity, but also to ride the snowmobile – unique combinations	Former residents visit the Varanger fjord region during holidays and vacations		

learning about Sami
fishing)

<p>Technological</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Remote controlled fish-farms Remote working possible Major technological improvements in aquaculture Hydrogen as fuel Renewable energy Artificial intelligence Technology for recirculation circular bioeconomy 	<p>Major technological improvements in aquaculture leading to significant reduction of impact</p> <p>The fishing fleet is carbon neutral and the aquaculture vessels are electric.</p> <p>The zero waste and recirculation system are fully integrated</p> <p>New aquaculture technologies including closed, semi-closed, and land-based systems, offshore open new possibilities to reduce negative environmental impacts (spreading of disease and parasites, pollution through chemicals)</p>	<p>Strong identity, culture and urban qualities: attracts people working remotely (lives in Kirkenes, works in Tokyo, New York or Rio de Janeiro)</p>	<p>Weak culture: workers from local firms work and live in more urban areas. Aquaculture production remotely operated</p>	<p>Wind power is expanding in Varanger</p> <p>Improvements in aquaculture technology reduces impact on fisheries.</p> <p>Technologies that benefit both industries, e.g., environmental monitoring</p> <p>IMTA (and other circular solutions) makes it possible to deliver and process other species in the region – less reliance on seasonal raw material from fisheries</p>
---	--	---	---	--

	and organic waste, prevention of escapes interbreeding with wild salmon).			
Environmental		Focus on preserving the unique landscapes	Increasing pressure on wild fish and crustacean stocks from fisheries and fishing tourism	Ecosystem change may involve establishment of new species and emigration of local species. Potential consequences can be of destructive character through the introduction of novel pathogens, parasites, and toxic algae blooms, and jellyfish invasions that threaten fisheries, tourism, and aquaculture.
Biodiversity	New species commercialised – pink salmon are caught by local fishermen.		Climate change affects spawning and migration patterns	Reduced environmental impact from aquaculture will be the main driver.
Genetic interchange(?)			Seal invasions due to climate change	
Climate change	Pink Salmon is suitable for aquaculture, and are a developed industry in Varanger 2035		Viable pink salmon fishery	
Lice and disease				
Eutrophication				
Freshwater run-off, increased input from agriculture, and increased release	Climate change enables sustainable transport of sea food via the north-east passage			
Organic waste from aquaculture production				
Feed				
Air freight				

Legal Sami rights	Sámi rights are implemented in coastal planning. The	Bigger focus on enforcing Sámi rights		New mechanisms are implemented to resolve the knowledge
EU legislations Environmental requirements for the fishing fleet Environmental requirements for the fishing fleet and AQ companies	municipality still are in lead of planning processes and local knowledge are crucial. Only environmental certified fishing vessels and aquaculture companies can operate.			ownership controversy. Who produces and owns knowledge that forms grounds for decision-making and cooperation between the industries? How to make all partners agree on the facts?

Scenario narratives

In the following the summarised scenario descriptions pinpointing the main drivers are presented. The scenarios is mainly written to show what Varanger might be like in 2035, and what brought it there. The scenarios are written in such a way that they represent those interconnected changes that the workshop participants brought up in workshops and that was found in the PPGIS survey. The cause-effect ways are described and development paths from 2023 until 2035 are described.

Scenario 1: Green growth

EU legislation and environmental strategies boost the Norwegian activity and legislation regarding the objective to zero emissions. The fishing and aquaculture industry have made significant progress. The social licence to operate (SLO) activity have been successful and the aquaculture in Varanger have expanded to new sites and opened new sea areas for production in coexistence with traditional and new fisheries. New aquaculture species has emerged, and both Pink salmon and King Crab aquaculture sites are part of the commercial activity in the region. A strong economic growth is an important spin off effect, as associated technology providers are rising in Varanger to cater for local demand of technology. The salmon production is rising (20.000 metric tons), providing a total of 200 employees. The ripple effects are substantial and creates a lot of indirect positive effects, like new inhabitants, new supplying companies, new schools and a demand for service institutions. People have developed a positive view regarding the future, tourism in general have expanded and fishing tourism is sustainable and well regulated. The natural fish stocks in Varanger are stable, with the king crab stocks back to a normal level (like in 2020) and provides local revenue for fishermen with crab quota. Sámi rights regarding fishing are implemented in coastal planning. The municipality still are in lead of planning processes and local knowledge are crucial. Only environmentally certified fishing vessels and aquaculture companies may operate in the region. New aquaculture technologies include closed, semi-closed, and land-based systems, offshore open new possibilities to reduce negative environmental impacts (spreading of disease and parasites, pollution through chemicals and organic waste, prevention of escapes interbreeding with wild salmon, and so on).

Education possibilities and new technologies result in more attractive jobs for women and the previous de-population in the region has been reversed. Green transition has changed the situation and created new interesting jobs both in the traditional natural resource-based industry, but not least in the supplier industry and services. Management increased focus on sustainability in the fisheries and aquaculture industry have led to an increased demand for specialists who can manage sustainable practices and certification programs. Technology specialists have a crucial competence for monitoring the sea, to document best practice and survey critical CPI's (Critical Performance Indexes). Green transition has also strengthened local identity. The zero waste and recirculation system are fully integrated.

Scenario 2: Arctic Urbanity

Varanger has succeeded in attracting younger people to work and to settle in all communities around Varangerfjord. Young people seek urbanity, but also to ride the snowmobile; Varanger attracts people by offering unique combinations of urban life and the arctic outdoors, with skiing

possibilities, and with kiting and kayaking, summer and winter alike. The focus on wildlife has also strengthened attitudes towards preserving the unique landscape.

Varanger has seen a strong cultural change, almost an awakening. This is manifested in an increased pride in living in the Arctic, based on a stronger Finnmark identity, and the "melting pot identity" of three traditional cultures: the sami, the kven and the Norwegian culture. The region also embraces the Russian and global influences from people coming to experience live in this region.

Culture and arts played a vital role in transforming the region. New industries based on arts emerge, making the region more attractive. Around 2025 inhabitants realised that the assets of the Varangerfjord region and Finnmark were under-communicated, even though many of the greatest story tellers of Norway were living in Finnmark. Marketing of the many great original film locations in the region started, attracting European and American film producers, as well as international artists to the region, and made the region a magnet for young people. And culture has also spread outwards: the "baalkaffe" and the distance unit "one kaffekok" is now familiar in the international coffee vocabulary.

A stronger local education in art, culture and other creative studies, reflecting the unique cultural heritage of the area, was vital in creating this new sense of pride and identity. Teaching the language and the culture was also instrumental in integrating the many new workers at Kirkenes Processing, that expanded to full-year employment a few years ago.

In the first five to ten years after Covid19, society in general made leaps in promoting footloose labour. The strong identity, rich arctic culture and urban qualities in Varanger attracted people working remotely to live in Varanger, while their offices are found all around the globe, from Tokyo to New York and Rio de Janeiro. With the opportunity for government jobs to work at regional hubs ("Statens småhus"), a further number of relatively young people was attracted. The wider variety of work available made it easier to attract couples in need of two jobs to make the move. Political decisions stimulating living in peripheral regions is still important for attracting young people , including tax relief, free kindergarden, remission of study debts and so on.

Scenario 3: The Traditionalist trap

In 2035 the results of prioritizing traditional fisheries and fishing tourism over aquaculture are starting to be visible, with aquaculture production at historically low levels. To compensate for the lost jobs when aquaculture slaughtering and processing moved out of Varanger, an increasing

pressure on wild fish and crustacean stocks from fisheries and fishing tourism became evident. Sami rights have grown in importance, and more fishing rights lead to local more coastal vessels and an increased number of fishermen, but with only small coastal vessels, catching primarily in high season, most of the catch is shipped further to Båtsfjord for processing.

There is now little aquaculture to replace lost jobs in fish processing. The slaughterhouse in Varanger closed down due to limited activity, slaughtering now is done by boat, with salmon landed and packed in Troms. The economy has seen stagnation and decline, as often happens in a vulnerable system lacking a plan B. Investment in green technology (away from fossil fuels), is also lacking.

Tourism is stronger though, based on sami storytelling, a strong cultural identity and the unique Varanger landscape. The open landscape inspire tourists and artists alike. Even at sea, the open landscape is loved by tourists, leading to a strong increase in fish tourism. Unfortunately, this has put an even stronger pressure on local fish stocks. Fishermen are concerned that fishing tourism can have adverse effects on local fish populations, for example halibut. On the other hand, novel species, for example pink salmon and may also bring new economic opportunities, as once the Red king crab did.

With reduced employment in aquaculture, and no new industries, the region has experienced further reduction in population. The trend showing a reduced base of the population pyramid, severely narrowed due to out-migration of young people, has continued. This means also less people at work, and a gender misbalance with lack of women. Reduced population and reduced tax income has also affected public services, with healthcare bodies struggling to offer expected care.

The ideas from some years ago, about developing a stronger Arctic Urbanity, more or less failed, resulting in a weak culture: even workers from local firms work and live in more urban areas. What is left of aquaculture production is now remotely operated. Varanger has now become a region which former residents visit during holidays and vacations.

Scenario 4: Blue desert

This scenario represents a worst case combination of a changing climate, geopolitical instability and overexploitation of natural resources. Once a region rich in natural resources and a hub for aquaculture, seafood production in Varangerfjord is not any longer a viable industry. Wild fish and crustaceans have declined severely, and fishermen, aquaculture, and decision makers have spent more time on assigning blame to each other, than finding solutions that could have prevented the outcome.

Locations with previously intensive aquaculture in the Varangerfjord have become so-called dead, hypoxic zones. Aquaculture production above the carrying capacity, and insufficient fallowing periods between production cycles, has resulted in eutrophication and accumulation of mud in the sediments in the relatively shallow fjord. In the end, the hypoxic zones became problematic for wild fish and conflicts between aquaculture and fishermen worsened. Eventually, the hypoxic locations created also problems for salmon aquaculture, leading to a continuous search and authorisation of new sites. As a final consequence, aquaculture production was restricted to closed-containment and land-based systems. The ecosystem Varangerfjord has become unstable: because of eutrophication and higher ocean temperatures, toxic algae blooms and jellyfish invasions occur on a regular basis. This, together with overfishing, and an invasion of Arctic seals due to the melting sea ice in the Arctic has resulted in a severe decrease of the local fish and red king crab stocks. Spawning stocks of cod and capelin have largely disappeared. Other wildlife that is dependent on marine resources such as sea birds, and marine mammals have lost a major part of their food sources. In response to the severe environmental situation, politicians have declared a moratorium on fishing and net-pen aquaculture in the area and it may take several decades until the ecosystem has recovered. The denied access to traditional resources procure abandoning of small fishing villages and loss of cultural identity. The global competition for finite resources has exacerbated the conflict with Russia and a main function of the Varanger region has become a military defence base. Therefore, Varangerfjord is no longer attractive for tourism.

Scenario 5: Emerging Coexistence

Varanger in 2035 experience more efficient and productive coexistence of fisheries, aquaculture (and other industries) in the region, where cooperation has created strong synergy effects. Constructive dialog between aquaculture and fisheries actors were instrumental in achieving this. One of the key controversies preventing dialog was the lack of common knowledge basis, especially relevant for knowledge on environmental interactions and impact. There are different institutions providing knowledge for for instance municipality planning processes, which may result in contradictions and therefore mistrust. Such issues of mistrust was successfully remedied by "ownership" to the processes and dialog locally and on higher political levels.

The improved trust was achieved by local political actors with a clear coexistence agenda, instead of prioritising one's own sector. During the mid 2020ies, inhabitants realised that efficient cooperation is necessary to build a resilient local economy in a changing geopolitical situation, where reliance on an eastern market became a source of great vulnerability. Local authorities played a key role in facilitation of cooperation by creating meeting places and additional incentives for aquaculture and fisheries actors.

However, economic incentives were not provided by the state or municipality only. Coexistence and cooperation between two (or more) sectors should be inherently profitable. Possibilities for increased profitability occur due to technological development. For example, environmental monitoring technology was developed locally with demand from both fisheries and aquaculture actors. Slaughter at sea represent a possibility for fisheries sector to participate in aquaculture activity. Processing technology tailored to the needs of both farmed and wild fish producers were also developed.

Logistics can also be a source of improving efficiency by combining the needs of aquaculture and fisheries sector. In this scenario, processing and marketing/export is integrated. A successful combination of processing was a key for creating year-round workplaces, that are less dependent on the seasonality of fisheries and aquaculture. More species will also be produced in the years closer to 2040, as the aquaculture sector is now developing and adopting IMTA systems.

For the food system to work in the described way, skilled people are needed. Establishing education institutions in the region was an important prerequisite for the seafood industry to grow. Multidisciplinary education programs, offering competence within biology, technology, economics and management of the seafood sector contributed to inflow and retaining of young people and creating a cultural identity of the region with a strong seafood element.

Cultural identity related to fish and seafood also influenced tourism. Fisheries and aquaculture businesses contribute to the development of this type of tourism and provide diverse opportunities to learn about and experience seafood: sea and river fishing, exhibition centres and other facilities are combined.

In the years after 2023 the aquaculture industry gradually achieved a higher SLO (social license to operate), through a strong sustainability focus, first of all in the sea phase of aquaculture, where improved technology reduced impact on both sea bed, sea fisheries and anadromous stocks. Creation of workplaces in the processing industry was also instrumental for the SLO. Investments in local social environment (education, sport, infrastructure) is facilitated by municipalities.

Conclusions

In ArcticHubs Varanger scenario process the aim was to build scenarios based on stakeholder and expert knowledge, from both local and national perspectives, which illustrate how varying sets of drivers in society may evolve until 2035. Such alternative scenario information can be used further to interact and advise actors and policymakers in the field in a future-oriented manner. We sought to represent variance between scenarios that reflect different paths and drivers that the future may entail.

The constructed five scenarios highlight both opportunities and threats in regions. In the following the key issues in each scenario are summarised.

First, in the **scenario 1** the key driver is green transition. The need for new solutions have resulted in economic growth and optimism in the regions. The population have not increased, neither decreased but are stable in the region. Varangerfjord is the starting point for transportation of goods through the east passage, from west to east. Both fisheries and aquaculture have developed positive.

The key concerns are global warming and temperature increases in the sea. This have impact for wild fish stocks and winter tourism.

Second, in the Arctic Urbanity scenario the key drivers are identity and culture, and a willingness to exploit these for growing the region. This represents a vision of how peoplecentered change may drive development.

Key concerns are not explicit, but would center around industries developing work places interesting enough to attract young people, and make them settle.

Third, in the Traditionalist Trap scenario the key driver is the preservation of traditional industries, restricting the growth of new industries with labour that is younger, more educated, more female and more year-round.

Fourth, in the Ghost Town scenario, the key drivers, an increasing demand for food and economic growth and climate change, are putting too much pressure on the ecosystem in Varangerfjord. The outcome of an environmentally unsustainable use of the Varangerfjord resources is a loss of ecosystem services that has implications for the economic and social situation, as well as cultural identity. At the same time, the increased demand for finite resources drives geopolitical conflicts, transforming Varanger into an important military defence hub.

Fifth, in the Emerging Coexistence scenario the focus is on the processed leading up to a social license for aquaculture, and thus a successful coexistence between the now and old industrie. This scenario represents a development towards efficient and productive

coexistence of fisheries, aquaculture and other industries in the region, where cooperation creates synergy effects.

Literature

Albretsen, J., & Asplin, L. (2021). Fysisk oseanografiske forhold i produksjonsområdene for akvakultur-Oppdatering september 2021. Rapport fra havforskningen.

7.

Future scenario 2035

Westfjords Hub report

Rannveig Ólafsdóttir, Michael V. Bishop, Anna Guðrún Edvardsdóttir

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869580.

1. Background

WP5 focuses on integrating and implementing the results from WPs 1-4 to assess the future outlook of the hubs and our regions under consideration. The Westfjords Hub is located in the southern part of the Westfjords peninsula in the Northwestern part of Iceland and consists of two municipalities, namely Tálknafjarðarhreppur and Vesturbyggð, which in November 2023 agreed to merge into one municipality. This new municipality will be operational in March next year. Traditionally, agriculture and fisheries were the main contributors to income, but have been declining during the past decades. In the last few years, the sectors of aquaculture and tourism have emerged as thriving industries and are expected to continue to do so.

Since the 1990s, this area experienced a significant population decline which impacted every socioeconomic aspect of these remote communities along with public services and residents' quality of life and future perspectives. Most of the land area in the Westfjords hub consists of a 250-600m high barren plateau carved by glaciers over the past million years. Only coastal areas and lower valleys are settled and cultivated. The area is characterized by its remoteness and seasonally difficult access posed by harsh weather conditions, despite the building of tunnels and bridge to better connect the region with other areas and the capital. However, since 2010, the depopulation trend seems to have come to a halt, as tourism, aquaculture and other industries become gradually more important in the area and provide employment opportunities in the area.

The aims of this task, i.e. 5. 1, were to:

- 1) explore the different outcomes associated with “what if” inquiries based on the materials provided by WPs 1-4.
- 2) establish shared visions for the future development of the hubs and their surrounding areas by building scenario narratives depicting potential futures.
- 3) enhance the adaptability of the hub regions in response to forthcoming social, economic, and environmental changes to create more resilient communities.

2. Data and methods

Mixed methodology was used to reach the aims of this task, including experts' interviews, on-site workshops, and online PPGIS surveys. Data collection began in 2021 with expert interviews, and an open PPGIS survey using Maptionnaire. On-site workshops were organized in 2022 and 2023, which laid the groundwork for the final Maptionnaire surveys, which were crafted and distributed in November and December respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Overview of the progress of the Westfjords scenario process

2.1 Experts' interviews (2021)

Interviews were taken with both local and non-local experts in the fields of tourism and aquaculture summer and fall 2021, with a specific emphasis on examining how global drivers are influencing these industries (tourism and aquaculture) as well as their forecasting impacts in Iceland and the Arctic.

Experts interviewed were:

- Þórdís Kolbrún Reykfjörð Gylfadóttir, minister of tourism
- Guðmundur Ingi Guðbrandsson, minister of Environment
- Bjarnheiður Hallsdóttir, chair of The Icelandic Travel Industry Association
- Þorleifur Þór Jónsson, account manager, Business Iceland (Íslandsstofa)

-
- Elías Gíslason, director, Icelandic Tourist Board
 - Einar Kristinn Guðfinnsson, chair of The Association of Companies in Aquaculture
 - Sigurður Pétursson, director and owner of Arctic Fish, a fish farming company
 - Kristján Þór Júlíusson, minister of fisheries, aquaculture, and agriculture

The interview framework used was identical for all ArcticHub participating countries. The interviews were all conducted via zoom, and took from 40-60 minutes. They were then transcribed, coded, and summarized. The major outcome of tourism and aquaculture were used as a basis for developing future scenarios.

2.2 On-site workshops (2022 & 2023)

A total of four on-site workshops were held in the Westfjords hub, two in September 2022 and two in November 2023. Our target groups were:

- 1) Focus group related to the PPGIS survey, (September 2022). Two representatives were nominated from the following groups: the younger generation (aged 18-25), the older generation (aged over 65), the middle-aged or working-age population, the population of foreign origin, and two representatives from each of the two industries, i.e. tourism and aquaculture, resulting in a total of 12 participants ranging in age from 25 to 70 years and equal distribution of genders.
- 2) High school students (young residents aged 16-18) (September 2022)
- 3) Residents of foreign origin (Polish) (November 2023)
- 4) Focus group related to the future scenarios building, comprising a total of 8, both experts and local residents (November 2023)

The first two workshops centered on public participation and were associated with the PPGIS Maptionnaire survey carried out in 2022. The latter two workshops were directly associated with this future task and were conducted in the following manner:

- Two on-site workshops were held in Patreksfjörður 22nd and 23rd of November 2023, aimed at discussing the planned future topics (threats and opportunities) and formulated statements. Facilities in the community center were kindly provided by the municipality.
- A total of 13 residents participated in the workshops. Some of them belong to the same focus group as conducted previously in other WPs. However, due to weather conditions, several guests were not able to attend the workshop.

-
- Participants included 3 representatives of the public sector, including the mayor of Vesturbyggð, 3 representatives from the private sector (encompassing aquaculture and tourism), 2 representatives of senior citizens, and 5 representatives from residents of foreign origin (comprising employees in fish farming, fish processing factory, and in kindergarten).
 - The workshops commenced with participants engaging in individual tasks, involving the identification of opportunities and threats, and the evaluation of statements. The subsequent segment of the workshop included group activities, during which participants shared their individual thoughts and assessments from the initial phase. Each group then collectively determined the three most significant future opportunities and threats for the regional development of the area, ultimately ranking them in order of importance.

2.3 Online Surveys (2021 & 2023)

Three online surveys were prepared and set up in Maptionnaire, integrating the insights and feedback gathered from the workshops.

- 1) The first one focused on public participation of residents in decision making with respect to land use. The survey link was posted by municipalities on June 11th, 2021, and an email to the organizations was sent out on June 16th to evaluate the respective impacts of distribution channels. A reminder was sent out to the municipalities on June 29th and to the organizations on July 5th. Answers were collected until July 8th, 2021.
- 2) The second one dedicated to opportunities, threats and statements on future developments in the Westfjords hub (i. Vesturbyggð) was released on November 23rd, 2023 – see preliminary results here below.
- 3) The third one also focused on future developments and related statements in the wider Westfjords region, improved based on the previous two surveys, will be released by the end of December 2023.

Forecast survey building: Drivers, trends and change factors were identified from previous studies. To align topics with partner countries for comparison, the **future topics and statements** were refined based on the insights gained from the Inari Delphi study. A focus group framework was developed, specifically addressing the region's future threats and opportunities, as well as future statements.

3. Results

3.1 Results from the future workshop

The initial results of the groups work are presented in the table below:

Group 1	Group 2
Opportunities: <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Fish farming2. Tourism3. Infrastructure---4. Innovation – technique5. Fishing	Opportunities: <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Proliferation of specialist jobs2. Strengthening transportation (accessibility)3. Strengthening culture and service
Threats: <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Lack of infrastructure2. Climate change3. Prejudices (f.ex. due to negative news on fish farming)---4. Lack of funding5. Depopulation	Threats: <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Inadequate transportation2. Monotonous businesses/employment3. Image - discount in environmental matters

3.2 Preliminary results from the on-line future survey:

On the 5th of December, a total of 38 had submitted full answers, 44 unsubmitted and 165 bounce visitors. For the item on opportunities, about 43 people answered (see graph below).

The below answers are obtained from these early results:

PART 1 - Opportunities and Threats for Vesturbyggð.

Themes related to **opportunities** (each respondent could write up to 3 opportunities).

Health	3
Culture	3

Keywords mentioned in relation with threats to local development in Vesturbyggð area. In total, 101 threats were mentioned by 37 respondents.

Ongoing: Analysis of respondents added opportunities and threats (open question)

Table X Summary of opportunities and threats (to be added to the big table in the big doc)

Theme (opportunity/threat)	Nature	Climate change	Natural resource use	Global investments	Demography	Indigenous issues
Westfjords, IS	conservation, attraction, clean air and sea	warmer ocean temperature, ocean acidification, rise in sea level, more extreme weather condition	coexistence between fisheries and aquaculture, conflicts in land use and sea space	foreign ownership in aquaculture	slow population growth mostly due to increased aquaculture, widening gender gap	

PART 2 – Perceived likelihood for the validity of statements in Vesturbyggð by 2035 (1/Red: Very unlikely; 5/Green: Very likely)

Statements related to Aquaculture (note: labels are for number of respondents, not percentages)

Statements related to Tourism for number of respondents,

(note: labels are not percentages)

Ongoing: Analysis of the open questions (respondents' own statements and comments).

Table X. Keywords of the Westfjords region's scenarios

Hubs	Region	Name of the scenario	Keywords
Aquaculture and tourism	Westfjords	Transportation infrastructure development - a pivotal factor for the region future prosperity.	Better roads, maintenance, increased access, connections with other settlements, reliability, security, tunnels under the mountains/fjords, national policy, harbour developments, air travel infrastructure, public transportation system, pedestrian and cyclists, lack of funding.
Aquaculture and tourism	Westfjords	Community-based controlled development of industries	Social License to Operate, public participation, Corporate Social Responsibility, destination branding, image of the Westfjords, sustainable practices, setting limits in size (e.g. cruise ships) and numbers, establishing standards and requirements, suitable infrastructure, moderate speed of change
Aquaculture and tourism	Westfjords	Interaction of economy, infrastructure and transportation	Strong global companies in aquaculture, small family owned companies in tourism. Lack of infrastructure and unstable transportation threatens viability of industries and livelihoods
Aquaculture and tourism	Westfjords	The viability of the communities	Demographic issues, such as widening gender gap, women and young people move away threatens the viability. Monotonous economy; mostly jobs in primary production in fisheries and aquaculture. Jobs that require education and specialization needed. Far away from more urbanized communities with more service and cultural activities. Large group of inhabitants of foreign origin living in the communities that do not participate in communities' activities. Opportunities in involving the group of foreign origin into the communities. In the long run a more sustainable approach in community development is needed.
Aquaculture	Westfjords	Aquaculture-driven community development	Development of aquaculture on land / off-shore, fish processing facilities and plants, further processing of sea-products, increased value creation, diversity of employment and business opportunities, vulnerability to

			climate change, incentives for sustainability, reputational damage and prejudice from ill-practices can affect the markets.
Tourism	Westfjords	Tourism-driven community development	Development of tourism infrastructure, accommodation, transportation, services, restaurants, cruise ships, excursions, fishing, retreat, workcation, geothermal resorts, hotel development, wellness tourism, landscape therapy, wilderness tourism, national parks and nature trails, recreational areas, cultural heritage, local food and drink products, seasonality and precarity of jobs often low-paid.

8.

Youth future workshop – Arctic future until 2035

Report

ArcticHubs project

Taru Rikkonen, Esa Inkilä, Pasi Rautio, Seija Tuulentie, Stefania Cardinale, Niina Kautto and
Jaana Sorvali

21.12.2023

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869580.

Arctic youth future workshop – Arctic future until 2035

Location: Inari, Finland

Date: 16.-18.8.2023

Figure 1. Participants in the Youth Future Workshop in Inari, August 2023. Photo: Niina Kautto/LUKE

ArcticHubs project (<https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs>) is an EU's Horizon program funded and Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke) led project, which aims to develop sustainable solutions for harmonizing competing industries and land use practices in the central locations of the Arctic, known as "hubs", and their surrounding environments. The project takes into account also the indigenous cultures and livelihoods, and it focuses on key economic activities in the Arctic region, including mining, aquaculture, tourism, and forestry, and how they impact ecosystem services and the well-being of local communities. The project seeks to resolve conflicts over local resources and land through the use of new adaptive and sustainable tools and approaches. These tools include Public Participatory GIS (PPGIS), Social License to Operate (SLO) and Future scenario work. As a part of this, the aim of the ArcticHubs project is to develop means for local citizens to participate in discussion and decision making of land use in relation to different industries.

The ArcticHubs project involves participatory foresight work for a total of seven specified hubs to assess future opportunities, threats, and strategies for preparing for the future. As part of the ArcticHubs project's future work, a joint Arctic youth workshop was held in Inari, Finland. From the 16th to the 18th of August 2023, 14 young people, aged 19-29, from Finland, Sweden, Norway, Iceland, and Greenland gathered together at the side of Lake Inari to talk about the threats and opportunities of the Arctic. Their purpose was to work on potential future developments, and to forge a collective understanding, as well as to unravel challenges, and the possibilities on the horizon of the Arctic.

This event was a joint initiative by ArcticHubs and ACAF projects. ACAF ("Youth and indigenous peoples' involvement in climate change adaptation in the Arctic and Barents region"; <https://www.acaf.fi/>) is another project coordinated by Luke and it is supported by the Ministry for Foreign Affairs of Finland. The workshop was organized with the Sámi Education Institute, a partner of the ArcticHubs project based in Inari. With a shared goal of addressing the complex issues facing the Arctic region, the workshop facilitated dialogue between indigenous

youth and those from the majority population, fostering a holistic understanding of the challenges that need to be tackled.

The workshop included activities designed to spark discussions, encourage networking, and facilitate innovative thinking. Participants began by introducing themselves and sharing insights from their respective home villages, showcasing the rich diversity and unique perspectives of the workshop. The workshop included three stages: 1) defining the most important threats and possibilities in the Arctic by 2035, 2) creating threat and opportunity scenario stories to the Arctic by 2035, and 3) concretizing how to avoid or reach these scenarios.

Figure 2. Youth Future Workshop. Workshopfacilitator Seija Tuulentie presenting the aim of the workshop to the participants in Lassin Laavu, Inari, Finland. Photo: Taru Rikkonen/Luke.

Figure 3. Youth Future workshop participants by the task. At the back, one of the facilitators, Jaana Sorvali. Photo: Seija Tuulentie/Luke.

The event featured a keynote speech by a local Northern Sámi rapper Áilu Valle, who brought a fresh and resonant voice to the discussions. In addition, the workshop featured practical experiences, to learn about different realities of the Arctic. A visit to the Sámi Education Center and a trip to the Juutua river highlighted the cultural and environmental aspects of the region, providing a deeper context for the conversations.

Figure 4. Youth Future Workshop also included activities, like visiting the River Juutua. Photo: Seija Tuulentie/Luke.

After the workshop, the research group has formulated this report with the drafts of scenario descriptions based on the workshop data. This included combining the different scenario stories from the workshop groups. After that the report was sent for participants for comments, and an online meeting was arranged, to discuss the results and the scenarios, and the participants could still influence them and suggest changes. After that, the workshop report will be distributed to the decision-makers in ArcticHubs localities in different regions.

Figure 5. Youth Future Workshop included socializing and getting to know youth from different parts of the Arctic. Niina Kautto discussing with the participants. Photo: Seija Tuulentie/Luke.

Figure 6. The participants had also a chance to listen our keynote speaker, local Sámi rapper Áilu Valle's rap performance. Photo: Taru Rikkonen/Luke.

Key insights from the workshop:

Migration from Northern regions: many are drawn by opportunities such as education and work that may not be readily available in Arctic Northern remote areas. This exodus presents both challenges and potential opportunities for local communities.

Climate-induced migration: the workshop also shed light on the rising concern of climate refugees. As environmental changes escalate, communities could be displaced due to deteriorating living conditions.

Diverse Arctic realities: it was evident that diverse areas of the Arctic present distinct characteristics and challenges. For example people from Greenland often access higher education from outside the island, like from Denmark.

Vast distances: a common threat woven through the conversations was the geographical vastness of the Arctic, and the need for innovative solutions to bridge these considerable distances.

Arctic future 2035 - Threats

Figure 7. The word cloud for key threats (key threats and scenario stories).

Threat scenario story based on the key threats and discussions

Name of the scenario: "What have we done; crisis of everything"

The impact of climate change, characterized by extreme weather events and other issues, is pushing the Arctic closer to its tipping point. The changes cause more health problems, new viruses, while nature and nature-based livelihoods are suffering. This has led to an increasing number of endangered and extinct species, contributing to the loss of biodiversity. At the same time, traditional knowledge and culture are fading away. Climate change introduces uncertainty and challenges, making it difficult to predict natural disasters and raising questions about disaster response and costs. Climate change is pushing people toward the Arctic in search of better conditions from other parts of the world, but this migration has its challenges, because these vulnerable areas cannot tolerate so many people. This has resulted in international and internal conflicts escalating. Simultaneously, rural areas are dwindling as people move to urban centers, leaving older generations with fewer opportunities.

Simultaneously, the transition from industrialism to consumerism has increased the demand for energy and resources, negatively impacting local and indigenous communities. Mass tourism has overcrowded "must-see" places, lacking the necessary infrastructure, and it profits at the expense of local communities and the environment. Technological interventions such as carbon capture, hydropower, and wind power are being used, but interactions with nature have also escalated conflicts over natural resources. Economic uncertainty and a concentrated economy have led to polarized views and harmful values like individualism and selfishness.

How to avoid the scenario

Main points: listening to indigenous peoples, focus on education and science, sustainable technology and recycling, regulate the mass tourism, localized decision-making, legally set targets

To avoid the threat scenario, it is important to recognize the existing problems, and to focus on education and evidence-based decision-making. A redirection of funds toward education and sciences is crucial, for example educating awareness about nature and self-sufficiency is essential to help people become conscious of their needs and reduce unnecessary consumption. At the same time, local and indigenous communities should be strengthened and given more influence on their affairs.

There should be greater accountability for companies, policymakers, and others when natural disasters occur. These actions should be coupled with increased investments in the environment, culture, and education, while diverting resources away from not that essential sectors like the military. Simultaneously, investments in research related to, sustainable technology and recycling, should be emphasized. It is important to make sure that the people stay in the area, by creating more opportunities for remote work, and focusing on the health of the communities.

Arctic future 2035 - Opportunities

Figure 8. The word cloud for key opportunities (based on key opportunities and scenario stories)

Opportunity scenario story based on the key opportunities and discussions

Name of the scenario: "The Arctic Dream"

In the year 2035, the Arctic is flourishing through better politics and decision making, and a healthier planet. The key to create long-term solutions is that collaboration and politics are intertwined, promoting open communication among different groups, including indigenous and local people being heard more. This approach empowers local voices, allowing communities to have a greater say in their living environments. There is also a growing

commitment to improve education at all levels. Focusing on common challenges, such as addressing the ecological crisis, illustrates how people should solve problems rather than cause them.

Simultaneously, as the use of fossil fuels diminishes, pollution decreases, leading to a cleaner and healthier Arctic. Overall consumption is being reduced, communities are becoming self-sufficient, and people take better care of their environment. The increase in remote work attracts residents back to communities, strengthening them and enhancing work-life balance. In the context of communities, the increasing availability of jobs leads to community growth. All together this results in a healthier and happier population.

In such a flourishing environment, the position of indigenous peoples is bolstered. Nature conservation becomes a focal point, and businesses adjust their practices to align with sustainable development principles. Collaboration to protect nature fosters a greater appreciation of the environment. Simultaneously, efforts to resolve international conflicts and wars gain momentum. All of this culminates in a harmonious relationship between people and nature, promoting equality, self-determination, and indigenous governance within the backdrop of a healthier and more diverse natural world.

How to reach the scenario

Main points: Young leadership, voices of local and indigenous peoples being heard, stop overconsumption and live responsibly, stronger communities, education

In order to reach this scenario, raising awareness of climate change and sustainable practices is vital, emphasizing informed choices. Focus on education on nature, self-sufficiency, climate change, and early leadership is also key. Promoting cultural education, particularly among the majority population regarding minority cultures and histories, enhances understanding. Advocating for local policy changes and science-based political decisions, including indigenous peoples' voices, with nature playing a significant role, is critical.

Governments should collaborate to address common issues, aiming for greater equality and considering diverse perspectives. Spreading awareness and reducing reliance on oil and fossil fuels, while investing in science, is paramount. Embracing a nature-respecting, less-consumptive lifestyle is essential for the desired future. Promoting resource recycling and closed-loop systems reduces environmental impact and supports sustainability. Promoting sustainable and nearby tourism, as well as educating the tourists, are ways to combat the mass tourism.

The promotion of remote work is a way to keep and get young people to the small villages, possibly adopting models like the Norwegian approach of erasing student loans. Community reliance is crucial, as strong social networks reduce the need for mental health services and offer support.

Conclusion

Youth from the Arctic discussed about the most significant threats and possibilities, and other factors to take in the account in the future of the Arctic by 2035. The main concerns were the climate change and its effects, natural disasters, people moving (either out from the remote areas, or to the Arctic in search of a milder climate), mass tourism and its effects, increased consumerism, and conflicts. The main opportunities were education and research, taking better care of the planet, and bolstering the position of indigenous peoples. It was seen, that there is a need to make better politics and decision-making together with locals, youth and indigenous peoples. All this contributes to an aim to achieve a harmonious relationship between people and nature.

What to do?

The Arctic youth discussed about how to get to the dream Arctic of 2035. It was seen very important to focus on education and raising awareness, as well as on research and science. Education on sustainable practices, nature, climate change, cultures and histories are important on all levels, and by this it is possible to do better politics by informed and sciencebased decisions. Better politics also needs open communication with the voices of the local, youth and indigenous peoples. In order to take better care of the planet and the environment, it is also important to stop polluting and change to a less-consumptive lifestyle, focus on efficient recycling and switch to a circular economy. The youth wanted the companies and decision-makers to have a greater accountability when disasters occur. To combat the challenges of tourism, it was seen important to focus on sustainable tourism and to educate the tourists. Also promoting remote work and making communities stronger by that was seen important to the life in the Arctic.